

**EFFECT OF EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE ON TRANSFORMATIONAL
LEADERSHIP OF PHARMACEUTICAL MANUFACTURING FIRMS IN SOUTH
EAST, NIGERIA**

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PG/EPh.D/2020/0037**

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**A THESIS SUBMITTED IN PARTIAL FULFILMENT OF THE REQUIREMENTS
FOR THE AWARD OF DEGREE OF DOCTOR
OF PHILOSOPHY (Ph.D.) IN MANAGEMENT SCIENCES
ENUGU STATE UNIVERSITY OF SCIENCE
AND TECHNOLOGY**

DECEMBER, 2023

ABSTRACT

The study examined the effect of emotional intelligence on transformational leadership of pharmaceutical manufacturing firms in South East, Nigeria. The specific objectives were to: ascertain the relationship between self-awareness and intellectual stimulation; evaluate the relationship between relationship management and idealized influence; examine the relationship between social skill and employee's Individual consideration and evaluate the relationship between motivation and employee inspirational motivation of pharmaceutical manufacturing firms in South East, Nigeria. The population of the study was three thousand, seven hundred and forty-two (3742) employees made up of senior and junior staff of pharmaceutical manufacturing firms in South-East, Nigeria. The sample size of 348 was drawn using Freund and William's formula at 5 percent error margin. A survey design was adopted for the study. Instruments used for data collection were interview guide and questionnaire. A total of three hundred and forty eight (348) copies of the questionnaire were distributed to the respondents from which three hundred (300) copies were returned while forty eight copies (48) were not returned. Four hypotheses were tested using Z - test with the aid of Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 20. The study revealed that Self-awareness had significant positive relationship with the intellectual stimulation, $Z(95, n = 300)$ from $6.697 < 8.372, p < 0.05$. Relationship management had significant positive relationship with idealized employees $Z(95, n = 300)$ from $7.736 < 9.180, p < 0.05$. Social skill had significant positive relationship with employee's Individual consideration, $Z(95, n = 300)$ from $7.725 < 8.776, p < 0.05$ and Motivation had significant positive relationship with employee inspirational motivation of pharmaceutical manufacturing firms in south East, Nigeria, $Z(95, n = 300)$ from $7.679 < 8.949, p < 0.05$. The study concluded that self-awareness, relationship management, social skill and motivation had significant positive relationship with intellectual stimulation, idealized employees, and employee's individual consideration and employee inspirational motivation. The study recommended that there was need for self-awareness to communicate with clarity and intention, this would give the power to influence outcomes and help become better decision-makers and give more self-confidence.

Keywords: Emotional Intelligence, Transformational Leadership, Self-awareness, Intellectual Stimulation, Employee's Individual Consideration, Employee Inspirational Motivation, Pharmaceutical, Manufacturing Firms.

Cite: Emecheta, J. O., Okonkwo, A. O., Okechukwu, E. U. & Eze, F. O. (2026). Effect of emotional intelligence on transformational leadership of pharmaceutical Manufacturing Firms in South East, Nigeria. *International Journal of Management Foresight and Strategy*, 4 (2), 352 – 521. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20085192>

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CHAPTER ONE

INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background of the Study

The present-day employee expects a safe working environment where they can freely voice their opinions, where the role of emotionally intelligent leaders becomes crucial. Leaders play an important part in cultivating their team's emotional dynamics. When leaders model the behavior they want their teams to exhibit, they see their teams develop the same traits. Emotional intelligence was first coined in 1990 by researchers John Mayer and Peter Salovey, but was later popularized by psychologist Daniel Goleman. Emotional Intelligence is one's ability to understand and manage their emotions and others' emotions in any situation. It trains leaders to be empathetic. Even before somebody begins to lead others, leadership demands leading one emotionally, being aware, and being in command of one's own emotions. The real challenge lies within. One needs to be able to empathize with others and forge relationships that are entrenched in minds and hearts. Emotional Intelligence is the deciding factor in one's success as a leader (Singh, 2022). Irrespective of their cadre in the organization, all leaders must harness their emotional intelligence skills to empower their teams and the entire organization. It includes self-awareness, self-management, social skills, and relationship management which are the "sine qua non" of leadership.

Cooper (2019) defines emotional intelligence as "the ability to sense, understand, and effectively apply the power and acumen of emotions as a source of human energy, information, connection, and influence." While Cherry (2022) asserts that Emotional intelligence (EI) is the ability to perceive, control, and evaluate emotions. Some researchers suggest that emotional intelligence can be learned and strengthened, while others claim it's an inborn characteristic. Research shows it is a useful tool for navigating work life, relationships, education, and mental and physical well-being. The ability to express and control emotions is essential, but so is the ability to understand, interpret, and respond to the emotions of others. Imagine a world in which you could not understand when a friend was feeling sad or when a co-worker was angry (Kendra, 2023). Psychologists refer to this ability as emotional intelligence. Emotions play a significant role in decision-making, trust-

building, employee engagement, and conflict management. When it comes to laying the foundations of a human-centric workforce, the role of Emotional Intelligence is pivotal. Emotionally Intelligent Leaders are committed to improving workplace productivity, team performance, and morale. Emotional Intelligence determines how leaders interact with their teams. Those with high emotional intelligence usually do better in their interpersonal skills, thereby boosting employee morale (Landry, 2019).

Leading organizations involves interactions with individuals and a person with higher levels of EI may be better at interacting appropriately with others than a person with low levels of EI. Emotionally intelligent leaders practice self-awareness, regulate their emotions and clearly express how they're feeling to others. They can effectively gauge the needs, wants and expectations of their co-workers and team members (Jamie, 2023). EI can help a person build relationships, communicate with others, and maintain friendships. Also, EI can help a person work with and supervise other people. It can also help them cope with and be more resilient to stresses they might face. A highly emotional intelligent leader is likely to be quite self-aware. Leaders with high emotional intelligence respond in ways that their employees can relate better to, thereby improving team performance, mitigating clashes, and addressing issues when required the most. When leaders bear witness to a positive culture and supportive environment from the top-down, employees feel more heard, valued, and cared for at work; this translates to increased job satisfaction and productivity. No one wants a boss who's short-tempered, intimidating, and unfair. The modern workplace demands leaders that excel in people-centric skills. Effective people management is a necessary quality for current and aspiring leaders who aim to improve workplace communication and prepare employees for success. Examining people management skills can help you discover your strengths and identify areas for improvement (Herrity, 2023). To excel at people management, leaders need to put themselves in their employee's shoes. They need to analyze why someone in their team is behaving a certain way. This could mean listening to their concerns and respecting them enough to have authentic conversations, among other things. This is an effective way the leaders can get a read on their team members and make sound decisions accordingly.

Employees are often inclined toward compassionate and emotionally grounded leaders. They feel more comfortable voicing their thoughts and opinions at work without being put in a spot. Also, emotionally intelligent leaders are the reasons why some organizations experience less attrition than others. Employees are likely to stick with organizations that are led by emotionally adept leaders. Ramakrishnan (2021) opines that “people leave managers, not organizations. Leaders’ empathy reassures people that they are valued members of a larger unit; lack of empathy reduces relationships to transactional levels and destroys organization unity.” In support to this Mathur, (2022) maintains that “becoming aware and fine-tuned with one’s emotions allows a leader to make rational decisions, overcome negative thoughts, handle volatile situations with ease, as well as understand why others behave in a specific manner. And all these traits are the building blocks of effective leadership”.

Emotionally intelligent leaders devote extra time to forging their team camaraderie. They make sure that each team member in the team is well-versed in each other’s potential, personalities, background, working style, and goals. This eliminates doubts, resentment, and disputes down the line. The deeper people understand themselves and those around them, the better they can accomplish goals and surpass difficulties. After all, teamwork and communication can win in most scenarios. Having a culture that promotes emotional intelligence improves both internal and external customer relations. Deeper the understanding of emotional intelligence among sales/ marketing teams, better is their ability to make emotional connections and increase sales. Similarly, customers also resonate with businesses that bring out their human side. Good management is fundamental to the success of a business. When you look at an effective and efficient company, the outcomes they achieve can usually be tied back to excellent managers organizing and motivating employees while instilling a positive workplace culture (Valamis, 2023). Embracing an emotionally sensitive culture into operations and marketing can be a trailblazing way for organizations to seize profitability. As organizations continue to re-assess business practices, a great customer service experience becomes paramount. Being aware of a customer’s emotional needs plays a key role in strengthening brand loyalty, which then translates to more sales. Indeed, the success or failure of any team of organization is directly related to its level of leadership. Leaders fuel an

organization's emotional state. A good example is how a leader's poor behaviour towards others can easily trickle down the organizational ranks, resulting in toxic interactions and environment that will most likely lead to low employee engagement and high staff turnover.

Transformational leadership is defined as a leadership approach that causes change in individuals and social systems. In its ideal form, it creates valuable and positive change in the followers with the end goal of developing followers into leaders. Transactional leadership is a style of leadership in which leaders promote compliance by followers through both rewards and punishments (Lutkevich & Pratt, 2023). Enacted in its authentic form, transformational leadership enhances the motivation, morale and performance of followers through a variety of mechanisms. These include connecting the follower's sense of identity and self to the mission and the collective identity of the organization; being a role model for followers that inspires them; challenging followers to take greater ownership for their work, and understanding the strengths and weaknesses of followers, so the leader can align followers with tasks that optimize their performance. Burns, transforming leadership is a process in which "leaders and followers help each other to advance to a higher level of morale and motivation".

Transformational leaders act as mentors to their followers by encouraging learning, achievement, and individual development. They provide meaning, act as role models, provide challenges, evoke emotions, and foster a climate of trust. The five dimensions of transformational leadership are idealized influence (attributed), idealized influence (behavioral), individual consideration, inspirational motivation, and intellectual stimulation (Lutkevich & Pratt, 2023). Idealized influence (attributed) refers to the socialized charisma of the leader and whether or not he or she is perceived as being confident and committed to high-order ideals. Idealized influence (behavioral) refers to charismatic actions by the leader that are based on values, beliefs, or ideals. Individualized consideration is the extent to which a leader attends to the needs and concerns of his or her followers by providing socio-emotional support. This involves mentoring followers, maintaining frequent contact, encouraging followers to self-actualize, and empowering them. Inspirational motivation is the degree to which leaders inspire and appeal to followers by setting challenging goals and communicating optimism with regard to goal attainment.

Intellectual stimulation refers to the extent to which leaders engage in behaviors that cause followers to challenge their assumptions, think creatively, take risks, and participate intellectually. The full range of leadership introduces four elements of transformational leadership: Individualized Consideration, Intellectual Stimulation, Inspirational Motivation and Idealized Influence. Emotional intelligence, in particular, is a key leadership skill that will help leaders effectively coach team members, solve problems, and collaborate with colleagues (HRDQ, 2022). Emotional intelligence is important for a variety of reasons. Emotionally intelligent leaders are able to develop and maintain a positive, productive, and efficient workplace while constantly motivating their employees to put their best foot forward. Leaders with this important skill are able to create workplace environments in which employees feel comfortable taking risks and sharing their ideas. They are able to make difficult decisions, resolve conflict effectively, and adapt to changing business goals and circumstances. A lack of emotional intelligence inhibits a leader's ability to effectively collaborate and communicate with others (HRDQ, 2022). When a leader is not able to manage their emotions, employees may be less eager to share their ideas and are less likely to reach their full potential.

1.2 Statement of problem

Emotional intelligence is the ability to understand and manage emotions effectively. Emotional intelligence (EI) forms the juncture at which cognition and emotion meet, it facilitates our capacity for resilience, motivation, empathy, reasoning, stress management, communication, and our ability to read and navigate a plethora of social situations and conflicts. Emotional intelligence in leadership comprised empathy, social skills, self-awareness, self-regulation and motivation. These are all teachable soft skills that are the focus of leadership and management courses. A leader with high Emotional Intelligence can also help to foster a workplace culture that does not become toxic in the first place. The benefits of emotional intelligence in the workplace include being able to better understand nonverbal cues, properly adjust your behavior, make good decisions and become a respected leader.

Leaders set the tone of their organization. If they lack emotional intelligence, it could have more far-reaching consequences, resulting in lower employee engagement and a higher turnover rate.

While leaders might excel at their job technically, if they cannot effectively communicate with their team or collaborate with others, those technical skills will get disregarded. Lack of emotional intelligence inhibits a leader's ability to effectively collaborate and communicate with subordinates. The study established that the challenges of emotional intelligence arise in the organization as a result of lack of self awareness, poor relationship among the management, absence of social skill and poor motivation of employees. When a leader is not able to manage their emotions, employees might be less eager to share their ideas and are less likely to reach their full potential.

Lower emotional intelligence, on the other hand, often results in difficulties relating to other people or working through your own feelings. With the foregoing, it is worthwhile to establish strategies on how to overcome the problems of emotional intelligence as it may result to lack of intellectual stimulation, unidealized influence, lack of employees individual consideration and inspirational motivation. Hence, the study aimed to examine the effect of emotional intelligence on transformational leadership of pharmaceutical manufacturing firms in South East, Nigeria.

1.3 Objectives of Study

The broad objective of the study was to examine the effect of emotional intelligence on transformational leadership of pharmaceutical manufacturing firms in South East, Nigeria. The specific objectives were to:

- i. Ascertain the effect of self-awareness on intellectual stimulation of pharmaceutical manufacturing firms in South East, Nigeria.
- ii. Evaluate the effect of team work on idealized influence of pharmaceutical manufacturing firms in South East, Nigeria.
- iii. Examine the effect of effective communication on employee's Individual consideration of pharmaceutical manufacturing firms in South East, Nigeria.
- iv. Evaluate the effect of motivation on employee inspirational motivation of pharmaceutical manufacturing firms in South East, Nigeria.

1.4 Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study

- i. What is the effect of self-awareness on the intellectual stimulation of employees of leaders of pharmaceutical companies in South East, Nigeria?
- ii. What is the effect of team work on the idealized influence of pharmaceutical manufacturing firms in South East, Nigeria?
- iii. What is the effect of effective communication on employee's Individual consideration of pharmaceutical manufacturing firms in South East, Nigeria?
- iv. What is the effect of motivation on employee inspirational motivation of pharmaceutical manufacturing firms in South East, Nigeria?

1.5 Statement of Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses guided the study

- i. Self-awareness has no effect on the intellectual stimulation of employees of pharmaceutical manufacturing firms in South East, Nigeria.
- ii. Team work does not have a significant effect on the idealized influence of pharmaceutical manufacturing firms in South East, Nigeria.
- iii. Effective communication has no effect on employee's Individual consideration of pharmaceutical manufacturing firms in South East, Nigeria.
- iv. Motivation has no effect on employee inspirational motivation of pharmaceutical manufacturing firms in South East, Nigeria.

1.6 Scope of the Study

The study examined the effect of emotional intelligence on the transformational leadership of pharmaceutical manufacturing firms in south East, Nigeria. The dependent variables are intellectual stimulation; idealized influence; Individual consideration while the independent variables are self-awareness, effective communication, motivation, and team work with reference to employees of pharmaceutical manufacturing firms in south East, Nigeria. The geographical

scope of the study was South East, Nigeria. South East, Nigeria is made up of five States which includes Abia State, Anambra State, Ebonyi State, Enugu State and Imo State. The time scope for the study was 2021-2023

1.7 Significance of the Study

The potential of any study is dependent on the level of the outcomes of the study to close the existing research and business practice gaps. This, to a large extent, depends upon the level of a study's significance to advance knowledge and enhance practical application. The significance of the study was assessed under theoretical and practical significance.

Contribution to Business Practice

This study seeks to add to the body of knowledge by examining the effect of emotional intelligence on transformational leadership. Findings of this study when completed may lead to promoting emotional intelligence initiatives and training across diverse employee levels especially in the manufacturing industry for the purpose of enhancing employee, leadership and organizational performances. This approach could be very effective in enhancing worker's commitment and reducing turnover intention among other important benefits. To the best of my knowledge, this study would hopefully be one of the first to enlarge the concept of EI dimensions and leadership performance in a previously unexplored sector and setting. The outcomes of this study might facilitate encouragement and implementation of EI framework.

The outcomes of this study would have a strong potential for practical applications of EI dimensions for companies within the context of broader human resource practices such as employee selection, performance management, and human capital development, as well as implications in constricted contexts such as customer service and management of external relations. The findings of this study may also inform the adoption of practices that could positively influence leadership emotional intelligence, and quality of leadership of the Nigerian corporate leaders which may also lead to significant recommendations in leader development practices for current and future leaders across diverse business organizations. This study would offer a benchmark for investigating if EI practices could be systematically and deliberately integrated to leadership development program across industry.

The knowledge gained from this study is expected to enhance understanding of leadership performance and may generate the robust framework for evaluating leadership performance which is currently recognized to be a complicated issue in a number of organizations.

Implications for Social Change

This study could be significant to social implications because, business organizations across the world are experiencing constant radical change and social change is inconceivable. The findings of this study may enable leadership to improve their emotional intelligence which would conceivably boost positive social change in the area of employees' productivity, leadership performance and organizational competitiveness. No doubt, leaders influence business performance and sustainability therefore, if businesses fail, due to poor leadership coordination and inability to foster common understanding, stakeholders, particularly, investors may be averse to take the risk of opening new businesses.

1.8 Limitations of the study

The constraints encountered by the researcher included;

The refusal of some employees to complete the questionnaires or to be interviewed for fear of official reprisal, this affected the volume of information available for the study.

In the process of conducting the research, the researcher's work was impeded by the attitude of the respondents, some respondents felt indisposed to provide vital information concerning their polytechnics as a result of prejudiced opinion conceived about the study. Fundamental constraints were encountered in the course of this research, the researcher was faced with certain unforeseen shortcomings such as, materials constraints and above all power failure constraint.

However, these bottlenecks were overcome by the researchers' share determination and commitment to the completion of the work.

1.9 Operational definition of terms

Self awareness: Self-awareness is the ability of an individual to perceive and understand the qualities that makes up the individuals such as personality, actions, values, beliefs, emotions, and thoughts. Self-awareness represents the capacity of becoming the object of one's own attention.

Individual consideration: Individual consideration is the extent to which a leader is concerned about the needs and challenges of his followers and how he provides support to them. Leaders support to followers comes on the areas of training, coaching, allocating tasks and motivation.

Employee inspirational motivation: employee inspirational motivation is a component of transformational leadership. It helps followers to raise their realization and commitment to achieving the mission and target of the organization.

Intellectual stimulation: this is a leader's ability to instill innovative and creative capabilities into followers as a way of building their critical thinking and problem-solving skills. It involves arousing followers' thoughts and imagination, as well as stimulating their ability to identify and solve organizational problems.

Emotional intelligence: Emotional intelligence is the ability of an individual to perceive, use, understand, manage, and handle emotions. Emotional intelligence helps both employee and manager, followers and leaders to manage their own emotions and understand the emotions of people around them.

Transformational leadership: Transformational leaders know how to encourage, inspire and motivate employees to perform in ways that create meaningful change.

CHAPTER TWO

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

2.1 Conceptual Review

2.1.1 Emotions

Emotion is a term whose precise definition has been argued by psychologists and philosophers for more than a century. The very root of the word "emotion" implies that there is a tendency for movement and action (motion). All emotions are, in essence, urges for action, momentary plans. In fact, every emotion prepares the body for a completely different kind of reaction (Kanas & Chalkias 2020). There are many emotions in a variety of shades, the most notable emotions being anger, sadness, fear, love, shame, and more. Moods, mentality, and affective disorders are undeniable dimensions of emotion. Sociologists emphasize the value of emotions by explaining that emotions lead us to face difficult situations that are too important to be left to logic alone. When it comes to making our decisions and actions, what we feel counts exactly the same and often more than what we think or believe. Therefore, our emotions are related to our adjustment to the conditions of life and work and affect, in combination with our rationale, our professional and personal success on many levels (Kanas & Chalkias 2020). Goleman, (2005), opine that Emotion is “any agitation or disturbance of mind, feeling, passion; any vehement or excited mental state”.

The word ‘emotion’ is derived from the Latin word “Emovere”, which means to be ‘stirred up,’ or ‘to stimulate’. The English word ‘emotion’ is derived from the French word émouvoir. This is based on the Latin emovere, where e- (variant of ex-) means ‘out’ and movere means ‘move’. The related term “motivation” is also derived from movere. No aspect of our mental life is more important to the quality and meaning of our existence than emotions. Emotions literally jerk a person. Emotions are reactions that human beings experience in response to events or situations. Emotion is defined as “a complex reaction pattern, involving experiential, behavioral and physiological elements.” Emotions are how individuals deal with matters or situations they find personally significant. Emotional experiences have three components: a subjective experience, a

physiological response and a behavioral or expressive response (UWA, 2019). All emotions begin with a subjective experience, also referred to as a stimulus, while basic emotions are expressed by all individuals regardless of culture or upbringing, the experience that produces them can be highly subjective. Emotions and how we feel about certain things most often influences our thinking. Even our perception is not always determined by the outside stimulus but by our internal feelings, emotions, desires, and aversions. Thus feelings and emotions are dynamics of our behaviour, and thus are very important. Emotion is associated with mood, temperament, personality and disposition and motivation. Energy in motion is an emotion and is a way of expressing oneself in life. Emotions cannot be considered as good and bad as each emotion has a specific role to play in colouring human life. Emotions are reactions that human beings experience in response to events or situations. The type of emotion a person experiences is determined by the circumstance that triggers the emotion (Kendra, 2022).

Emotions constitute the highest form of the sensory relationship between humans and the objects and facts of reality; this relationship is characterized by relative stability, generality, and correlation between needs and values which have been developed throughout an individual's personal development. UWA, (2019) noted that emotions are often confused with feelings and moods, but the three terms are not interchangeable. According to the American Psychological Association (APA), emotion is defined as "a complex reaction pattern, involving experiential, behavioral and physiological elements." Emotions are how individuals deal with matters or situations they find personally significant. Emotional experiences have three components: a subjective experience, a physiological response and a behavioral or expressive response. The formation of stable emotional relationships is the most important presupposition of personality development. It constitutes the main aim and ultimate result of the individual's learning ability. The conscious knowledge of motives, models, and behavioral stipulations alone is not enough to guide the individual's existence within society. On the contrary, only when the individual becomes possessed of stable emotions is this knowledge shaped and formed into behavior. Every aspect of human activity is accompanied by a variety of emotions. The importance of emotional management has led to the designation and study of emotional intelligence and its abilities, especially in organizational settings. Robert, (2023) asserts that an emotion may involve conscious

experience and reflection, as when one “wallows” in it, or it may pass virtually unnoticed and unacknowledged by the subject. An emotion may be profound, in the sense that it is essential to one’s physical survival or mental health, or it may be trivial or dysfunctional. An emotion may be socially appropriate or inappropriate.

2.1.2 Intelligence

Intelligence or intelligent quotient (IQ) simply refers to the capability to have awareness of other's emotions comprising empathy, influence, collaboration and conflict management. Intelligence is a form of mental capability relating to the handling and cognitive reasoning of diverse information. It ability to apply knowledge to manipulate one's environment or to think abstractly as measured by objective criteria. According to Mayer et al. (2007), intelligence is a comprehensive notion that relates to a hierarchy of mental capabilities. Intelligence encompasses the aptitudes of abstract reasoning. Intelligence is a human intellectual capability, which consists of a set of problem-solving abilities. According to Elaine (2020), possession of a high Intelligence Quotient alone is not a guarantee for success; however, the level of success attained in life is influenced by both Emotional Intelligence and Intelligence Quotient.

Scientific studies on intelligence were systematized in the early 20th century; intelligence remains a topic of interest and debate for centuries. Four centuries ago, Descartes' definition of intelligence was the ability to discriminate directly was one of them. Wechsler, on the other hand, defines intelligence as "the ability to solve problems and define logical relationships" and also as "acting around an individual's purpose, thinking rationally and communicating effectively with their environment" (Aslan, 2009). On the subject of intelligence, especially until the 1950s, more cognitive dimension was emphasized. For example, in the 1920s, Lewis Terman defined intelligence as the ability to think abstractly. Mayer and his colleagues took a similar approach and defined intelligence as the ability to distinguish similarities and differences between objects, evaluate their relationships with each other and with the whole, and abstract reasoning. (John, Mayer, Salovey, Caruso & Sitarenios, 2001) On the other hand, Thorndike expressed intelligence as the ability to react well. Sternberg expressed intelligence as the mental abilities required for choosing, shaping, and adapting to the environment. From a general point of view, intelligence

was defined by Sternberg as the ability to adapt to the environment and learn from experiences. Piaget and Vygotsky highlighted the social impact on intelligence development. Based on this, Piaget evaluated intelligence as the ability to adapt to the environment. According to another definition, intelligence is the ability to manage itself and the environment.

Human intelligence is the intellectual power of humans, which is marked by complex cognitive feats and high levels of motivation and self-awareness (Colom, 2010). Intelligence enables humans to remember descriptions of things and use those descriptions in future behaviors. It is a cognitive process. It gives humans the cognitive abilities to learn, form concepts, understand, and reason, including the capacities to recognize patterns, innovate, plan, solve problems, and employ language to communicate. Intelligence enables humans to experience and think.

As a result of years of research on intelligence, a common view has been reached that intelligence is a mental capacity like the ability to think abstractly. It pointed out that this mental ability should be perceived as a general learning ability with a developmental feature. When all the definitions of intelligence are evaluated, the expression "ability to adapt to the environment" draws attention. Accordingly, the individual will be successful to the extent that he complies with the organization's rules, culture, and the people he works with. When this expression is considered from the point of leadership, it will mean that the leader has a high intelligence level that they adapt quickly to the organization they are in, the conditions of the time, and customer expectations. In this case, it shows the importance of intelligence, which means adaptation to the environment in leadership (Aslan, 2009).

2.1.3 Emotional Intelligence

Although emotional intelligence is a new concept, it has become a phenomenon that is discussed in every layer of society and has applications in many different fields and is researched. Today, widespread academic studies are carried out on emotional intelligence in different business sectors, especially in the field of education. Emotional intelligence refers to the ability to perceive, control, and evaluate emotions. Some researchers suggest that emotional intelligence can be learned and strengthened, while others claim it is an inborn characteristic (Jovanovski, 2020). There are many

different definitions in the literature on the concept of emotional intelligence, and each definition draws attention to a different aspect of emotional intelligence. While there are those who describe emotional intelligence as the ability to understand emotions correctly and express them effectively, there are also those who describe emotional intelligence as a different type of intelligence that affects work efficiency, leadership, and performance. According to Dr. Reuven Bar-On, Emotional Intelligence is defined as "an array of noncognitive capabilities, competencies, and skills that influence one's ability to succeed in coping with environmental demands and pressures." Emotional intelligence consists of abilities such as being aware of one's own emotions, not giving up the struggle against changing situations and pressures, being passionately attached to short and long-term goals, being aware of other people's expectations and needs, conscientiousness and honesty. It is the sum of a person's ability to be aware of their own emotions, to manage their emotions, to feel self-confidence, to activate themselves, to be aware of the emotions of others, to manage the emotions of others and to activate them. Emotional intelligence (EI or EQ for "emotional quotient") is the ability to perceive, interpret, demonstrate, control, evaluate, and use emotions to communicate with and relate to others effectively and constructively. This ability to express and control emotions is essential, but so is the ability to understand, interpret, and respond to the emotions of others (Kendra, 2023). Therefore, people with high emotional intelligence have made their private and professional lives easier for them. Being aware of those around them and their feelings increases the potential to overcome the problems encountered in daily life.

Emotional intelligence (EI) is most often defined as the ability to perceive, use, understand, manage, and handle emotions. The concept of Emotional Strength was first introduced by Abraham Maslow in the 1950s the term "emotional intelligence" seems first to have appeared in a 1964 paper by Michael Beldoch. People with high emotional intelligence can recognize their own emotions and those of others, use emotional information to guide thinking and behavior, discern between different feelings and label them appropriately, and adjust emotions to adapt to environments (Argyle, 2017). Emotional Intelligence is the "ability to monitor one's own and other people's emotions, to discriminate between different emotions and label them appropriately, and to use emotional information to guide thinking and behavior". Emotional intelligence also refers to the ability to know when and how to express emotion as well as being able to control it. Although

there is no universal definition for emotional intelligence, however, Goleman (2005) posits that emotional intelligence is a skill that anyone who owns it, tries to control his life with self-awareness and improve it with self-management, and perceives its effects through sympathy or by managing the relations he tries to improve his or others' moral. Mayer, Salovi, and Caruso, (2007) claim that emotional intelligence is the ability to cognition, evaluation, and expression of emotions, and the ability to control emotions. In yet another definition, Antonakis and Ashkanasy (2009) argue that emotional intelligence includes innate factors (self-awareness, self-control, feeling independence) and external factors (relationship, ease in sympathy, amenability). Also, Emotions are brief, organized sets of responses (including physiological changes, expressive behaviors, action tendencies, and subjective experiences) that optimize how individuals address the challenges and exploit the opportunities that arise in the events that they encounter. Charlotte (2020) noted that the four key components of emotional Intelligence are (i) self-awareness, (ii) self-management, (iii) social awareness, and (iv) relationship management.

In practical terms, being aware that emotions can drive our behavior and impact people (positively and negatively), and learning how to manage those emotions – both our own and others'. Managing emotions is especially important in situations when we are under pressure like in: Giving and receiving feedback, Meeting tight deadlines, Dealing with challenging relationships, Not having enough resources, Navigating change and Working through setbacks and failure. It is a scientific fact that emotions precede thought. When emotions run high, they change the way our brains function diminishing our cognitive abilities, decision-making powers, and even interpersonal skills. Understanding and managing our emotions (and the emotions of others) helps us to be more successful in both our personal and professional lives.

At a personal level, emotional intelligence helps us to: Have uncomfortable conversations without hurting feelings, Manage our emotions when stressed or feeling overwhelmed and Improve relationships with the people we care about. At work, emotional intelligence can help us to: Resolve conflicts, Coach and motivate others, create a culture of collaboration, Build psychological safety within teams and Applied to meet goals and targets, as well as create a happier and healthier working culture.

Academics and practitioners alike are agreed that the intelligence of human beings and its implications for the organization should be from both cognitive as well as emotional perspectives. They say that as compared to cognitive intelligence, it is emotional intelligence that has greater relevance to organizational success.

2.1.4 Models of Emotional Intelligence

Faltas (2017) highlighted three foremost models of Emotional Intelligent, namely, ability model, trait model, and mixed model to describe emotional intelligence. The major dissimilarity in these three groupings is whether the model(s) advocated by researchers perceive Emotional Intelligent as an inherent human attribute or a capability that can be developed. The three models are discussed below:

i. Ability Model

The notion behind the ability model of Emotional Intelligent is the competences openly connected to emotions which are deliberated to be part of everyday functioning (Mayer et al., 2004). Ability model centers on the capability of the individual to process emotional information and use it properly within the social context (Mayer et al., 2000). According to Humprey et al. (2007) and Mohammed (2018), ability model contends that the operationalization of ideas, intelligence, and the features of development apply to emotional intelligence domain. Mayer et al (2000) and Freudenthaler, Neubaur, Gabler, and Scherl (2008) stated that Emotional Intelligent incorporates affect associated behavioral issues and self-perceived skills that are prerequisite to job performance.

ii. Trait Model

The trait model lays emphasis on behavioral characteristics and self-perceived capabilities which focus on emotion-related tendencies. Trait emotional intelligence (trait EI) refers to a constellation of emotional self-perceptions located at the lower levels of personality hierarchies and integrates the affective aspects of personality (Siegling, Furnham & Petrides, 2015). According to Petrides and Furnham (2000), conceptual dissimilarity between ability model and trait model of emotional intelligence is based on the characteristics of people which influence management of emotions.

The trait model of Emotional Intelligent is also, the arrangement of emotional perceptions of one's personality at lower degrees of temperament.

iii. Mixed Model

In its original design, the mixed model highlighted five areas of Emotional Intelligent: identifying one's own emotions, handling emotions, inspiring people, understanding other's emotions, and managing relationships (Goleman, 1995). According to Mayer et al., (2008), the mixed model elucidates the integration of mental capabilities, characters and traits approach to describe Emotional Intelligent.

2.1.5 Emotional Intelligence and Leadership

According to Zhou and George (2013), emotional intelligence enables a person to properly determine what he or she is feeling and at the same time, be sympathetic towards the feelings of others. Because they can identify what they are truly feeling and express these emotions, they are also more receptive towards the emotions of others (Zhou & George, 2013). According to Sy, Tram, and O'Hara (2006), positive job performance is linked with highly emotionally intelligent team members. Sy et al. found that team members with high emotional intelligence are proficient in knowing what they about certain tasks and decisions, and are also more receptive of what others will feel on certain tasks and decisions. Members who can easily identify their own emotions and regulate these can lead to higher level of faith and confidence in themselves. They can make realistic actions leading to positive performance even with minimal supervision. Team members who have low levels of EI, on the other hand, cannot recognize what they are feeling and controlling their emotions; so, they need more supervisory interference in order for them to work well with others, be more creative and adapt better with their teammates (Sy et al., 2006). According to Zhou and George (2013), highly intelligent team members can also use their emotions to improve their cognition. Members with high emotional intelligence can effectively process information. They can use their emotions to gauge which options are more important, especially if the options are competing and similar. They can also use their emotions to increase

the flexibility of information processing and become involved in different types of information processing. As such, emotions can be used to ensure and enhance effective functioning.

Zhou and George (2013) also emphasized that emotions can be critical in changing situations. Highly emotionally intelligent people can be good at coordinating how they feel and share what they are doing. People with high emotional intelligence can regulate their emotions better.

They are not only perceptive of the emotions of others, but also make an effort to manage these emotions. According to Zhou and George, unmanaged emotions can affect information processing negatively. If the emotions of others can be regulated easily, highly emotionally intelligent individuals can gather insights from the emotions of others and see where interest their interests are focused on (Zhou & George, 2013). People who have high emotional intelligence, being able to manage their own and others' emotions, can join or withdraw from an emotion depending on what their situations called for. Because of this ability to control his or her immediate reactions, a person with high emotional intelligence can postpone his or her judgment on a specific situation and communicate this judgment in an informed and careful manner. Emotionally intelligent people are those who can think first before they act and communicate properly. All these capabilities allow individuals with high emotional intelligence to play a major role in improving their performance in the workplace. Goleman, Boyatzis, and McKee (2013) believed that most leaders today attained their positions because of their emotional intelligence, rather than cognitive intelligence.

2.1.6 Emotional Intelligence and Leadership Performance

Leadership is an emotion-laden issue, therefore, very fundamental to leadership practices and actions (George, 2000). Emotional Intelligent has been confirmed to expressively relate to a firm's performance in a number of industries (Jasleen & Anupam, 2019; Safaa, 2018). There is progressively growing empirical evidence that suggests that Emotional Intelligent is linked to effective leadership (Miao et al., 2018). Research has demonstrated that emotional intelligence is essential for improving performance productivity in manufacturing organizations (Chooi & Amin, 2016; Ibrahim et al., 2017). Bal Subramanian et al. (2008) carried out a study that examined the

link between Emotional Intelligent and leadership effectiveness. The findings revealed that leaders with high a level of Emotional Intelligent function effectively. Boyatzis and Ratti (2009) reported that the skill level that differentiates effective managers and leaders is emotional intelligence. Due to the growing complexity of managing contemporary business organizations, Business managers with high Emotional Intelligent may be more skillful in encouraging subordinates to generate a number of important positive work outcomes, such as employee satisfaction, commitment, high level of engagement and decline turnover intention. Lam and O'Higgins, (2012) stated that Emotional Intelligent represents a desirable set of abilities essential for competent management of the workplace. Research carried out in Sweden concerning the Emotional Intelligent of project managers by Vierimaa (2013) reported that Emotional Intelligent significantly contributed to the performance of project leaders.

Emotionally intelligent leaders are very imaginative and capable of influencing emotions and relations to foster mutual understanding (Mintz & Stoller, 2014). Parrish (2015) documented that Emotional Intelligent is highly vital and constitutes basic condition for leadership success. According to Goldring et al. (2015), EI leaders can effectively manage subordinates' emotions as well as their own to achieve better collaboration in accomplishing firm's mission. Shapira-Lishchinsky and Levy-Gazenfrantz, (2016) stated that emotionally intelligent leaders are more knowledgeable and conversant in making decisions that create win-win approaches which improve individual and firm performance. Emotional Intelligent has become a fundamental competence compared to technical and managerial competences when advancing middle or senior leadership positions, thus, Emotional Intelligent competencies are vital for improved productivity and leadership career advancements (Faltas, 2017). Previous studies have reported that Emotional Intelligent is not only a major distinctive feature of leadership effectiveness and performance, but that leader who has high levels of Emotional Intelligent can efficiently control their own emotions and correctly evaluate and understand the emotional disposition of their subordinates (Mokgata, 2018; Saqib et al., 2018). The major task of leaders is to drive the combined emotions of their subordinates in a positive direction and to lessen the possibility of forming toxic emotions. Momeni (2009) stated that Emotional Intelligent is a mental capability that has an impact on other skills of executives, most specifically their leadership abilities.

Emotional Intelligent encompasses the capability to identify and understand emotions and symbolizes a fundamental skill of leadership performance. Meta-analysis study conducted by O'Boyle et al. (2011) reported that Emotional Intelligent is connected to both employees and leadership performance. Leaders who have Emotional Intelligent talents will have high inspiration and impact coworkers positively which are essential for excellent achievement in the workplace. Possession of reasonable levels of Emotional Intelligent assists leaders to develop competencies in the workplace (Ramchunder & Martins, 2014), as well as enlarging their self-actualization (Thory, 2016). Emotional Intelligent skills are connected to the decision-making process, and such competences can improve individual and group decisions and outcomes to maintain harmonious relationship with others. Emotional Intelligent of leaders perform a vital role in the organizations as leaders who display positive moods are more effective than leaders who have negative emotions. Consequently, leaders' positive emotions can increase positive leadership practices by extension both subordinates and leadership performance. According to Antonakis and Dietz (2010), the major role of leadership is to encourage positive interface between leaders and subordinates, which accounts for why coworkers pay serious attention to leadership behavior and emotions. Leaders with high Emotional Intelligent and maturity are more likely to demonstrate supportive behaviors and treat their subordinates with psychological concerns This, in turn, inspires and impacts subordinates job satisfaction, commitment and overall performance.

Leaders who display high Emotional Intelligent are able to coordinate and energize coworkers and exhibit self-management capability which influences the followers positively (Seethapathy & Venkatesh, 2016). Researchers such as Kotze and Nel (2015) highlight some disadvantages of high Emotional Intelligent. These academics labeled Emotional Intelligent as a 'tricky management style', where leaders who are emotionally intelligent but morally weak in their leadership dealing may exploit it to their benefit. Other scholars such as Antonakis (2004), Brown et al. (2006) and Barbuto and Burbach (2006) remarked that empirical support linking Emotional Intelligent and leadership performance remains weak. As earlier noted, scholars have proposed multiplicities of emotional intelligence dimensions ranging from five, seven and up to twelve measures. Following the seven-dimensional approach adopted in this study, researchers have documented varying impacts of these dimensions on leadership performance.

For instance, innovations have become the fundamental source of competitive advantage in the contemporary business environment and as such recognized as a valuable asset that can impact leadership performance. According to Karabulut (2015), although being innovative is a risky venture, however, successful leaders must take risks that empower them to accomplish and sustain high performance. Innovative leaders should take decisions to improve organizational factors that are relevant to performance improvement (Hannah et al., 2019). In light of the innovation revolution, there is an emerging question that business leaders should seek to answer: How do I become an innovation leader in my workplace? This is a fundamental question because proactive leaders should be able to implement innovative ideas successfully to stay ahead of rivalry. Although leadership can bring enormous talent towards improving performance and that of the organization, however, innovation constitutes one of the most critical issues to enhance organizational performance (Moo, & Rashad, 2015).

A large number of previous studies suggest that self-awareness is connected with successful leadership. Self-awareness is a vital and important first step toward maximizing management competences and leaders with well-developed self-awareness is more effective intuitive decision makers. The outcome of survey carried out by organizational psychologist Tasha Eurich, reported that 95 percent of people assume they're self-aware, but roughly 10 to 15 percent really are (Lauren, 2019). Business managers who are exceedingly emotionally self-aware are better able to read their "instinctive moods" and use them to regulate their behavior and decisions. In order to inspire the subordinates, leaders need to bring out the best in themselves, this is where self-awareness comes into play and through this process, a leader will gain insights into his or her own behavior and learn how to adjust and determine how is perceived in the workplace (Lauren, 2019). High levels of self-awareness unexpectedly can result in either good or bad outcomes. Leaders' jobs revolve around decision making and intuition is particularly significant in circumstances where a decision needs to be made rapidly, without time to contemplate the diverse features of the situation (Nocker & Sena, 2019). A number of successful entrepreneurs such as Steve Jobs, Bill Gates, and Richard Branson to mention a few have attributed part of their success to a strong intuition.

From a practical viewpoint, understanding individual dissimilarities in emotion regulation seems to be vital for informing training interventions intended to improve leader emotional regulation competencies. Therefore, leaders who are not judgmental, but think before engaging or acting have the tendency to redirect employees disruptive instincts and dispositions into the constructive drive toward organizational transformation and performance improvement. In addition, EI leaders can differentiate the motives of subordinates and respond correctly by offering the required direction/guide and desired support, which will inspire them to accomplish performance improvement (Nocker & Sena, 2019). A strong predisposition and motivation on the part of leader to accomplish predetermined objectives can strengthen subordinates. Consequently, leaders with such behavioral competences have a better prospect of building a team with similar features to lead transformational change that improve individual and business performance. Leadership is one of the major influences to motivate and boost employees' efforts/energy, and continuously facilitate support for change initiatives. Thus, leadership plays a major role in a workplace by motivating employees to display desired behavior in order for the company to be able to withstand and adapt effectively to sustain performance improvement (Moo & Rashad, 2015).

People desire to support and understanding (empathy) in all facets of life workplace, family settings, and friends (Edmondson & Lei, 2014). Leaders can offer empathy and by doing so, he or she fosters a strong bond that inspires and encourages subordinates toward performance improvement. Empathy is a notion that is very fundamental to leadership and numerous leadership theories propose that the capability to have and demonstrate empathy is a fundamental aspect of leadership (Elaine, 2020; Walumbwa et al., 2008). Higher level of empathy permits leaders to better understand and react to subordinates' needs/expectations in a way that upsurges performance and several important individual and workplace outcomes. Leader empathic behavior accounted for roughly three times as much difference with employee structural behaviors. A leader lacking empathy competency would more likely fall back on routine suggestions or ones that could work well for the leader but not necessarily the subordinates and the overall organization (Ned, 2019).

2.1.7 Components of Emotional Intelligence

Goleman (1995) who popularized emotional intelligence identifies five emotional domains: This includes self-awareness, self-regulation, motivations, empathy, social skills and relationship management.

2.1.8 Components of Emotional intelligence used in the study

2.1.8.1 Self-awareness

Self-awareness is a critical tool to help individuals and organizations reach higher levels of job satisfaction, become a better leader, improve relationships with colleagues, and manage your emotions better. It's also positively correlated with higher levels of overall happiness (Forsey, 2018). Self-awareness is the ability to understand that the self is separate from others; however, to be self-aware, a person must be able to recognize and label their own feelings, thoughts, and behaviors. At its core, self-awareness showcases that a person is separate from others regarding thoughts, wants, and needs. While consciousness is being aware of one's environment, body, and lifestyle, self-awareness is the recognition of that awareness. Self-awareness can be practiced and cultivated -- it's not a fixed trait. Individuals, who practice self-awareness, can easily evaluate their values, passions, and goals as well fit into current environment and emotions and align better. It also helps to understand how other people view an self-aware individual, creating stronger, more authentic relationships with colleagues (Forsey, 2018).

Self-awareness was first defined by Shelley Duval and Robert Wicklund (1972), who proposed that, at a given moment, people can focus attention on the self or on the external environment. At its basic level, self-awareness is the ability to understand that the self is separate from others; however, to be self-aware, a person must be able to recognize and label their own feelings, thoughts, and behaviors. If a person is self-aware, they can assess their own physical, mental, and emotional states and understand there are various aspects of their internal personality that allow them to interact with the external world. At its core, self-awareness showcases that a person is separate from others regarding thoughts, wants, and needs (Carnevale and Collins, 2021). Self-awareness has been called "arguably the most fundamental issue in psychology, from both a

developmental and an evolutionary perspective." it develops systematically from birth through the life span and it is a major factor for the development of general inferential processes. Series of studies showed that self-awareness about cognitive processes participates in general intelligence on a part with processing efficiency functions, such as working memory, processing speed, and reasoning. Mindfulness allows people to become more aware of themselves in the present, while compassion allows them to do so without passing judgment on themselves. Reflection and feedback allow people to take what they have learned and improve themselves in order to achieve their goals and reach their full potential (Kendra, 2023). Emotional self-awareness is not just about understanding one's own emotions. It's also about recognising the emotional states of others and being able to respond in a way that meets their needs. For example, a leader who can read the emotional cues of their team and adapt their communication style accordingly would be said to have strong emotional awareness. Self-awareness happens through sensory data, thoughts, feelings, actions and wants.

Self-awareness is a valuable tool, as it helps you regulate your thoughts and emotions to make clear, strong decisions. Individuals become conscious of themselves through the development of self-awareness. This particular type of self-development pertains to becoming conscious of one's own body and mental state of mind including thoughts, actions, ideas, feelings and interactions with others. "Self-awareness does not occur suddenly through one particular behavior: it develops gradually through a succession of different behaviors all of which relate to the self. Jason, (2021) opine that no one is born with self-awareness. It is a skill that needs to be learned, refined, and strengthened over time. To be successful in their role and to advance their skill set and careers professionally, individuals need to actively work to improve their self-awareness. Doing so benefits individuals at all levels as the workforce will be more in-tune with their needs, more empathetic towards others, and more prepared in the case of future disruption. In order to create a culture that truly embraces and encourages self-awareness, there is need to have a clear understanding of the varying levels, types, and approaches to becoming self-aware (Jason, (2021). Self-awareness is all about creating a healthy and productive state of mind for one to focus their thoughts and attention. Highly self-aware individuals are able to turn their focus and critiques to themselves, observing their current emotional and mental state. People who are truly self-aware

separate their decision-making from their emotions; they control and manage their thoughts, rather than having their thoughts and emotions control them.

Self-awareness represents the capacity of becoming the object of one's own attention. In this state one actively identifies, processes, and stores information about the self. In the workplace, self-awareness is something all employees should strive for. Enabling individuals to have control over their own actions and emotions, a highly self-aware employee is one that takes challenges in stride and reacts in a calm, professional manner. This is a critical aspect when it comes to our current state of business, as many industries and companies continue to face unusually prolonged disruptions. Self-awareness also entails a sense of continuity as a person across time and includes a feeling of self as being distinct from the rest of the environment. Self-awareness also comes in degrees: Terms such as 'meta', 'reflective', 'iterative meta-representational', and 'extended' consciousness indicate various levels of self-awareness (Morin, 2011).

Self-awareness is often seen as a critical component in leadership and career success, and has therefore become a feature in MBAs, leadership development, and management education. High self-awareness is claimed to lead to better decision making, is linked to team performance and authentic leadership (Dierdorff & Rubin, 2015). Self-awareness can be viewed from subjective and objective angle. Subjective self-awareness, which is a state of consciousness where attention is focused on events external to the person, and second, objective self-awareness, which is focused exclusively upon the self. This two-dimensional approach also proposes that self-awareness is attained through focusing attention on oneself, which initiates a comparison against self-developed standards (Carden, Jones & Passmore, 2021).

2.1.8.2 Team work

A team is a group of people linked in a common purpose. Human teams are especially appropriate for conducting tasks that are high in complexity and have many interdependent subtasks. Teamwork occurs when a group of people work together to successfully complete a task. More broadly, it also relates to the cohesiveness of a team, their ability to create a positive working atmosphere and how they recognise the strengths and skills that each team member brings.

Teamwork is present in any context where a group of people are working together to achieve a common goal. These contexts include an industrial organization (formal work teams), athletics (sports teams), a school (classmates working on a project), and the healthcare system (operating room teams). Basic requirements for effective teamwork are an adequate team size. The context is important, and team sizes can vary depending upon the objective (Thompson, 2011).

Teamwork happens when people work together toward a common goal. That goal could be professional or personal. Teamwork has been a key factor in the progress, evolution, and survival of humanity. Teamwork is considered one of the most effective work forms. Working in teams also benefits the individual on a personal level as it fulfills needs such as social interaction and affiliation. Regardless of the profuse research validating the effectiveness teamwork brings to organizations, many management personnel still do little to build teams (Khawam, Didona and Hernandez, 2017). Teamwork is one of the most noticeable and essential work configurations of the 21st century. The 21st century has brought many changes to the structure of organizations and also to the nature of jobs. Levi, (2014) suggests that even though the use of teams in the workplace has a long history, the past decades have shown that the notion of organizational teamwork has reformed. To complete shared goals, team members have to bring together diverse viewpoints and build on them. A productive operating environment is based on effective communication and teamwork among employees. It's what allows operations to run efficiently and effectively. Teamwork leads to better outcomes and effectiveness. Multiple minds working on difficult tasks or projects will achieve better results and offer different solutions than individuals working alone.

Teamwork is as old as mankind, and a variety of organizations use the term. Teamwork in either many ways, such as in the production, marketing processes, and many others. Management team, production team or an entire organization can be referred as a team (Ooko, 2015). Teamwork emerged as one of the most important ways of organizing work. Teamwork is the process of working together among a group of people in order to accomplish a goal or a set of goals. The external factors that affect teamwork are the political, economic, social and technological whiles the internal factors of teamwork constitute leadership style, diversity (culture, talent and personalities) communication, and cohesiveness among others which affects teamwork (Stephen, 2018).

2.1.8.3 Effective communication

Effective communication skill helps teachers to motivate students to learn, build supportive relationships using encouragement and empathy, give feedback and manage the classroom, making the classroom a safe and supportive learning environment. Communication is not only verbal, but also non-verbal through signals x giving out through body language which are positive, confident, and engaging. Communication is a vital key for effective teaching and learning in the classroom and goes beyond the messages we send, it also includes how we receive messages. Communication can be described as the process where people exchange thoughts or ideas with one another. The benefits of fostering such relationships enable students to freely discuss thoughts and ideas and create an open environment in which questions can be asked without the risk of being judged or humiliated as proposed by Hanifan, (2022). Communication skills are most vital for interactions with students, as it enhances the act of teaching and helps in the role of comprehending and breaking down complex information, conveying this information clearly to students, presenting in a manner that sustains their attention, and listening to and resolving their questions or problems (Sword, 2020). Communication is a very important component of the teaching profession. Without it, it would be impossible to teach or learn.

Effective communications skill help to develop students' knowledge, skills, and judgment around human communication that and also facilitate their ability to work collaboratively with others. Effective communication is a process of exchanging ideas, thoughts, knowledge and information such that the purpose or intention is fulfilled in the best possible manner. In simple words, it is nothing but the presentation of views by the sender in a way best understood by the receiver. Just delivering a message is not enough; it must meet the purpose of the sender. Keeping this in mind, let us discuss the elements which make, (Prachi, 2018). Effective communication is the process of delivering messages to a target audience in a way that guarantees satisfactory reception and understanding. If the communication is effective, both the sender and the receiver will share the same information at the end of the process, (MyAccountingCourse.com, 2022). Communication skills involve listening, speaking, observing and empathising. It is also helpful to understand the

differences in how to communicate through face-to-face interactions, phone conversations and digital communications like email and social media, (Indeed Editorial Team, 2021).

Communication is a key variable that facilitate or break a business – without looking at its size. As the latest workplace communication statistics have observed, effective communication processes are paramount for employee output and retention, (Filipov, 2022). Effective communication is a critical component of business success. Yet, for most leaders or managers, this can be a significant blind spot that derails relationships, make goals harder to achieve, limits advancement opportunities, and impedes overall business and personal success. Effective Communication in the workplace is not just exchanging information. When done well, there is real power in internal communications to move company's forward, engaging employees in teamwork action that supports the company's mission and vision. Leaders who constantly communicate the strategy in clear language, and use it as a tool to relate the organization's initiatives and progress, help inspire and motivate employees, keeping them focused and working together toward success, (Grossman, 2022).

Communication strategies have been reported to be a factor that influences performance. Communication is an integral component of any performance improvement approach. Communication strategies play a central role in influencing performance (Arab & Muneeb, 2019). Poor communication is a breakdown that results from a discrepancy or disconnect between what is said and what is understood. This lack of mutual understanding can happen at the interpersonal level between colleagues or at an organizational level. Effective communication is critical to any organization and can help it in many ways. In fact, communication plays a role in product development, customer relations, and employee management – virtually every facet of a business' operations. Employees are a key audience because they often serve as the conduit to other audiences. If employees are informed and engaged, communications with other constituencies are likely to be strong as well,(Leigh, 2019). Communication refers to the process by which information is transmitted and understood between two or more people (Kibe, 2014). Communication is an integral part of the organizational process as the flow of communication up and down the organizational hierarchy has its effects on efficiency, decision- making and morale of organizations. Thus, effective communication is regarded as the foundation of organizations

today. Communication involves transmission of verbal and non-verbal messages. It consists of a sender, a receiver and channel of communication (Davison, 2018). In the process of transmitting messages, the clarity of the message may be interfered or distorted by what is often referred to as barriers. Communication requires full understanding of behaviors associated with the sender and receiver and the possible barriers that are likely to exist.

Communication consists of the process of transmitting, disseminating, or passing information from one person to the other or from one place to the other (Femi, 2014). Communication can also be defined as creating, transmitting and interpreting ideas, facts, opinions and feelings. It is a process that is essentially a sharing one, a mutual interchange between two or more persons. Communication refers to how information is transmitted and understood between two or more people (Markovic & Salamzadeh, 2018). Communication in the workplace occurs through different modes. Clarity in communication and timely information about changes affecting work are meaningful to labour productivity. Also, to achieve the targeted productivity level, managers should confirm clarity or understand instructions, provide enough training to employees, make sure cooperation at work exists by providing incentives and finally, develop a good communication plan for timely information delivery on changes affecting work. For an organization to be successful, it should not only keep an open line of communication between managers, employees, stakeholders, and the community, it should also have a strategy in place to ensure communication is effective, consistent, and aligned with business objectives (Guthrie, 2019). Effective communication is the building block of any organization because without effective communication, organizational performance tends to suffer. Without effective communication, organizational performance tends to suffer. All organizations rely on effective communication for their basic functioning.

2.1.8.4 Motivation

Motivation is the process that initiates, guides, and maintains goal-oriented behaviors. It is what causes you to act, whether it is getting a glass of water to reduce thirst or reading a book to gain knowledge. Motivation involves the biological, emotional, social, and cognitive forces that activate behaviour. In everyday usage, the term "motivation" is frequently used to describe why a

person does something. It is the driving force behind human actions. Motivation does not just refer to the factors that activate behaviors; it also involves the factors that direct and maintain these goal-directed actions (though such motives are rarely directly observable) (Nevid, 2013). As a result, we often have to infer the reasons why people do the things that they do based on observable behaviours (Morin, 2020). The four resulting forms of motivation are extrinsic (external source, action), identified (external source, non-action), intrinsic (internal source, action), and introjected (internal source, non-action). The understanding of these different forms of motivation is important both for the individual and for organizations seeking to promote higher performance or goal achievement (Ismael, 2020). There are many different forces that guide and direct individuals motivations (Kendra, 2020). Motivation is an important factor which encourages persons to give their best performance and help in reaching enterprise goals. A strong positive motivation will enable the increased output of employees but a negative motivation will reduce their performance. A key element in personnel management is motivation. According to Likert, "It is the core of management which shows that every human being gives him a sense of worth in face-to face groups which are most important. A supervisor should strive to treat individuals with dignity and recognition of their personal worth (Venkatesh, 2021)

Motivation is the driver of guidance, control and persistence in human behavior. Increased motivation and discipline can be pursued by the provision of incentive. To motivate the employee in working can be done by giving a fair and reasonable incentive. Motivation refers to a process of inducing and stimulating an individual to act in certain manner (Byju's, 2023). In the context of an organisation, motivation implies encouraging and urging the employees to perform to the best of their capabilities so as to achieve the desired goals of the organisation. It refers to driving the individual psychologically so as to induce his willingness to work and perform better. In an organisation motivation can take various forms such as promotion, appraisal, recognition, etc. depending on the expectations and desires of the employee. Motivation implies encouraging and urging the employees to perform to the best of their capabilities so as to achieve the desired goals of the organisation. Motivation is a force which cause people to behavior particularly and according to management point of view, the aim of creating motivation in employees is to have a behavior in which brings the highest benefits for the organization. Motivational incentive is what

drives people to perform, grow, and achieve their goals in therapy, coaching, or organizational settings. It plays a key role in determining a range of factors (Moore, 2021).

Motivation incites or induces the action of employees. Motivational system is meant to meet all the employees' needs. As soon as their satisfaction is fulfilled, the employees will tend to outline an independent relationship between their involuntary wish of performing the professional activity and their mood. Motivation is "powering people to achieve high levels of performance and overcoming barriers in order to change. Motivation is the word derived from the word 'motive' which means needs, desires, wants or drives within the individuals (Juneja, 2015). It is the process of stimulating people to actions to accomplish the goals. Motivation is the psychological process that gets employees going, keeps them going, and determines the direction and strength of the effort they apply. It's what causes them to stop and apply their energies elsewhere. Motivation and performance lead to personal outcomes for each employee. When aggregated, employee outcomes lead to organisational outcomes like turnover and profit. If there's motivation, performance is possible (Timeless, 2023). Motivation is the reason for which humans and other animals initiate, continue, or terminate a behavior at a given time. Motivational states are commonly understood as forces acting within the agent that create a disposition to engage in goal-directed behavior. It is often held that different mental states compete with each other and that only the strongest state determines behavior (Wasserman and Wasserman, 2020).

Motivation is the word derived from the word 'motive' which means needs, desires, wants or drives within the individuals. It is the process of stimulating people to actions to accomplish the goals (Juneja, 2015). Motivational incentives lead to higher rates of retention in the organization. Motivational incentives are a type of reward system where someone where somehow an individual receives some type of motivation for their performance. Incentive programs are designed to attract, engage, and retain talent. Incentives themselves are rewards and benefits used to motivate positive behaviors in your workforce. They come in many forms, like tuition reimbursement, more time off, and additional flexibility in work arrangements (Wong, 2020). The more motivated the employees are, the more empowered the team is. Every concern requires physical, financial and human resources to accomplish the goals. It is through motivation that the human resources can

be utilized by making full use of it. This can be done by building willingness in employees to work. This will help the enterprise in securing best possible utilization of resources.

2.1.9 Leadership

As mentioned above, Leadership is a critical pillar in every organization. Leadership is the process to lead followers. It creates the path of operation towards the achievement of the organizational goals by understanding the needs of the employees and motivating them. In a business, for example, executives define the vision of the business. This vision should be clearly described to employees who must understand and support this vision. Executives must help employees to understand their role in achieving business goals. A useful definition of leadership is given by Katz: "Leadership is a process where one person systematically influences others towards the execution of the tasks of the team." There are many definitions of what could be defined as leadership, however, all of them result in the common parameter of having a member (or members) within a team assume the role of coordinating the actions of the other team members in order to achieve the collective goals.

Leadership is a complex concept of social and personal behavior, which has led to a variety of definitions in an attempt to capture and clarify its content. Indicatively a definition of leadership is provided by (Hollander, 1985), "The process of leadership consists of a relationship of mutual influence between two or more persons where the relationships they develop are interdependent in order to achieve common goals under group conditions", (Katz, 1973), "Leadership is a process where one person systematically exerts more influence than others on team performance", (Zevgaridis 1981), "Leadership is the ability to direct others", (Rue & Byars, 1983), "Leadership is a process of influencing formal or informal working groups in their work related to the definition and achievement of goals and objectives. The ability to both gain and influence followers empowers the leader".

According to many researchers leadership surfaces:

- i. As a characteristic of the position one possesses
- ii. As a characteristic of the individual

- iii. As a characteristic of behavior.

Leadership may surface because of one of these factors or due to the combination of more than one of the discussed factors. The purpose of leadership is to attempt to influence and motivate the behavior and actions of a small or large group, or even of one individual, in such a way that everyone is willing to strive in order to achieve the collective goals of the group. Leadership as a function leads to a high level of motivation and commitment from the members of a team (Georgas, 1999).

Leadership styles

The fact that leadership is a complex concept, the result of personal and social characteristics and behaviors is also supported by the existence of the various styles of leadership that one can encounter, especially in their workplace environment. Different situations require that a different style is utilized, therefore no single leadership style is appropriate for every situation. Leadership styles include transformational leadership, transactional leadership, Autocratic leadership, democratic leadership, charismatic leadership, situational leadership and Laissez-faire Leadership.

2.1.10 Transformational Leadership

The transformational leadership style as mentioned above was first established by Burns (1978) and further developed in a wide range of research by Bass and his colleagues (Avolio, 1999; Avolio and Yammarino, 2002; Bass, 1997; Avolio and Bass, 1988; Avolio and Bass, and Jung, 1999). According to Bass (1985; 1998) the transformational leadership style involves establishing a leadership model that earns the trust of the employees increases their confidence and aims to move their concerns towards achievement and growth rather than existence.

Transformational leadership is a form of leadership style that enhances subordinates' commitment by directing and influencing their desires, value and self-esteem (Widayanti & Puranto, 2015). A transformational leader focuses energy and attention on how to create a vision, develops the intellectual stimulation, inspires and fosters subordinates' performance in the workplace (Hong, Qinxuan & Jiexiang, 2013; Rosete & Ciarrochi, 2005).

Transformational leaders stimulate and motivate coworkers at workplace through sharing of vision concerning what can be accomplished (Bass & Avolio, 2004; Northouse, 2016). According to Odumeru and Ogbonna (2013) and Chandra and Priyono (2016), transformational leadership implies drive to change or coordinates subordinates efforts towards desired behavior. Transformational leadership refers to leadership effort aiming at encouraging workers through shared collectivism instead of individualism approach (Given, 2008) Transformational leadership style established reciprocal relationship between the leader and the subordinates to achieve desired objectives (McCleskey, 2014). Transformational leadership focuses on group effort instead of individual.

Transformational leadership has traditionally been defined as the demonstration of the following components: Idealized influence (attributed), idealized influence (Behavioural), intellectual stimulation, inspirational motivation and individualized consideration (Bass & Avolio, 1997). It is also defined as a leadership approach that causes a change in individuals and social systems. In its ideal form, it creates valuable and positive change in the followers with the end goal of developing followers into leaders. Enacted in its authentic form, transformational leadership enhances followers' motivation, morale and performance through various mechanisms. These include connecting the follower's sense of identity and self to the mission and the collective identity of the organization; being a role model for followers that inspires them; challenging followers to take greater ownership of their work, and understanding the strengths and weaknesses of followers, so the leader can align followers with tasks that optimize their performance.

2.1.11 Emotional Intelligence and Transformational Leadership

The relationship between emotional intelligence and transformational leadership is an area of modern scientific research. Over the last decade, the majority of leadership research has been dominated by the investigation of transformational and charismatic leadership theories. Leadership behavior through these surveys is expressed through several characteristics, however the most significant characteristics which are also related to EI are the following:

- i. Personality characteristics (Hoogh, hartog, and Koopman, 2005; Houghton, Bonham, neck and Singh, 2004);
- ii. Leadership behaviours (Mackenzie, Podsakoff, and Rich, 2001).

Recent research on leadership behaviours has focused on investigating multidimensional aspects of intelligence as a suitable space for applying transformational leadership. These views of leadership assume that leadership is more effective when the leader uses emotional and inspirational techniques of influence to lead the organization and its employees (Bass, 1985). Later, Bass (2002), who correlated cognitive, social and emotional components of intelligence with transformational dimensions of leadership, concluded that cognitive, social and emotional components of intelligence are critical for the effectiveness of transformational leadership.

2.1.12 Components of transformational Leadership used in the study

2.1.12.1 Intellectual Stimulation

Intellect concerns the logical and the rational functions of the human mind, and usually is limited to facts and knowledge. As a branch of intelligence, intellect concerns the logical and the rational functions of the human mind, and usually is limited to facts and knowledge. Additional to the functions of linear logic and the patterns of formal logic the intellect also processes the non-linear functions of fuzzy logic and dialectical logic (Nithyananda, 2017). A person's intellectual understanding of reality derives from a conceptual model of reality based upon the perception and the cognition of the material world of reality. Intellectualization is a psychotherapeutic method based of intense intellectual focus in order to avoid dealing with a problem that occupies the attention of a person. Intellectual stimulation is the ability to encourage creativity, curiosity, and critical thinking among your team members. Intellectual stimulation is the process of challenging and stimulating the minds of followers, by encouraging them to question assumptions, explore new ideas, and seek innovative solutions. It is not about imposing ones views or dictating the answers, but rather creating a learning environment where everyone can contribute and grow. Intellectual stimulation is one of the four dimensions of transformational leadership, along with idealized influence, inspirational (Linked, 2023). Intellectual stimulation is important because it

helps individuals and teams cope with uncertainty and complexity in several ways. It fosters a culture of learning and adaptation, where you and your followers can embrace change and uncertainty as opportunities rather than threats. It enhances the collective intelligence and creativity of team, by tapping into the diverse perspectives and experiences of your followers. It builds trust and empowerment among team members, by showing them that you value their input and respect their autonomy and lastly, it increases the motivation and satisfaction of your followers, by providing them with intellectual challenge and feedback (Linked, 2023).

Intellectual stimulation is defined as having a leader who encourages innovation and creativity, as well as critical thinking and problem-solving. Intellectual stimulation involves arousing followers' thoughts and imagination, as well as stimulating their ability to identify and solve problems creatively. As suggested by Hackman & Johnson, providing Intellectual Stimulation involves the leader encouraging individuals in teams to be strong role models and coaches and empower others to embrace creativity and innovation (Hackman & Johnson, 2018). Nurturing the development of others by modeling transformational leadership development behaviors is on the rise in agribusiness, especially in providing Intellectual Stimulation to workers and team members. Incorporating intellectual stimulation into leadership practice can help teams cope with uncertainty and complexity. Intellectual stimulation can bring many benefits to you and your organization, especially in times of uncertainty and complexity. Such benefits include improved performance and outcomes, enhanced resilience and agility, increased engagement and retention, and stronger collaboration and diversity (Linked, 2023). Intellectual stimulation can be a powerful tool for coping with uncertainty and complexity; however, it comes with some challenges that need to be addressed. These include potential resistance and conflict from followers who are used to a more directive or conventional leadership style. Additionally, intellectual stimulation can require more time and resources than other forms of leadership. Moreover, ethical and legal issues can arise such as plagiarism, copyright, and confidentiality.

Intellectual stimulation is the degree to which the leader challenges assumptions, takes risks and solicits followers' ideas, leaders with this style stimulates and encourages creativity in their followers. They nurture and develop people who think independently. For such a leader, learning

is a value and unexpected situations are seen as opportunities to learn. The followers ask questions, think deeply about things and figure out better ways to execute their tasks. Through intellectual stimulation, transformational leaders encourage followers to question their own beliefs, assumptions, values and when appropriate, those of the leader, which may be outdated or inappropriate for solving current problems (Bass & Avolio, 2004; Elkins & Keller, 2013; Sundi, 2013) Intellectual stimulation is used by leaders to develop employee capabilities of exploring and capturing opportunities to develop performance. employees get the opportunity to think from a new perspective of an old problem, where they can consider a wide variety of opinions to make decisions. Intellectual stimulation solicits employees' perspective on problems in this way to develop more opportunities. Transformational leaders encourage employees' performance by developing critical thinking skills. The development of these skills and knowledge help employees take a challenging task at the workplace. Intellectual stimulation develops empowering conditions among individuals where the employees can get quality support to develop performance and information to create opportunities and resources to sustain their performance at the workplace (Hosna, Islam, and Hamid, 2021).

2.1.12.2 Idealized Influence

Identified motivation mediates the relationship between idealized influence behavior and organizational commitment. Idealized influence is one of the four components of transformational leadership, a style of leadership that aims to inspire and motivate followers to achieve higher levels of performance and commitment. Idealized influence refers to the leader's ability to act as a role model, embody a shared vision, and earn respect and trust from the followers (Linked, 2023). One of the first steps to use idealized influence across cultures is to understand followers' values and beliefs, and how they relate to vision and goals. Another key aspect of idealized influence is to demonstrate ethical and moral standards in leadership. This means that leaders act with integrity, honesty, and fairness, and that they uphold the principles and values that you advocate. Idealized influence can be explained within the organization in the context of knowledge creation. The term idealized influence means simply being influential over ideals. At the highest level of morality, leaders and their employees may dedicate themselves to the best ideals. Knowledge systems emanate from individuals with the capability to display knowledge using their association. These

interactions between individuals bring in social relationships when the organization deals with a bigger social collective network which needs idealized influence (Ngaithe, K'Aol, Lewa & Ndwiga, 2016).

Idealized influence refers to the behaviours of a transformational leader that evoke in followers as sense of trust, admiration, respect and the desire to emulate the leader. Regarding the influence of idealized influence on employee performance, employees were proud to be associated with the supervisors and performance requirements are designed according to the organization needs (Chebon, Aruasa and Chirchir, 2019). Idealized influence can be most expressed through a transformational leader's willingness to take risks and follow a core set of values, convictions and ethical principles in the actions he takes. It is through this concept of idealized influence that the leader builds trust with his followers and the followers, in turn, develop confidence in their leader. The leader behaves in a manner that serves as an exemplary role model for associates and impacts company values, ethical values, and worker performance. The 'idealized' aspect relates to role modeling after certain traits and characters of other people or groups. Leaders' idealized influence on coworkers can positively and significantly affect job performance

Individualized influence is the degree to which a leader is perceived as a role model who is confident and can impact employees (Gomes, 2014). It provides a role model for highly ethical behavior, instills pride, and gains respect and trust. At first idealized influence, can develop employee performance by communicating collective purposes and values, demonstrating confidence and determination, and acting as a charismatic role model (Yue et. al., 2019). In idealized influence, the leaders concerns are more on charismatic actions. These actions impact the employee's behavior. Leaders can develop beliefs about employees ability to do more in their work. Leaders influence employees by adding values and purpose to their work. Inspiring employees in a way that employees have become concerned about their work itself (Hosna, Islam &Hamid, 2021).

It is evident that leadership is a process that is applied by managers in order to achieve organizational goals. As such, it is evident that any leadership style is correlated to the manager's personal characteristics (Personality, emotions, etc). therefore, leadership as a process is a function

of the outcome of which is influenced by different parameters. One of the most important parameters which affect leadership is emotional intelligence and according to many scientific studies, efficient leaders do display high levels of emotional intelligence (Kamas & Chalkias, 2020).

2.1.12.3 Individual Consideration

The individual perspective deals with the development of followers through coaching and mentoring. Followers are treated individually to increase their level of maturity and improve effective ways to address their goals and challenges. In the individualized view (IC), transformation leaders pay particular attention to each individual employee's needs for performance and growth by acting as a coach or mentor. Followers and colleagues are developed to successively higher levels of potential. Individual consideration is practiced when creating new learning opportunities and a nurturing climate. Individual differences in terms of needs and desires are recognized. Two-way communication is encouraged and management by walking around the workspace is practiced (Ondari, Were, & Rotich, 2018).

In basic understanding, the individualized view as part of transformational leadership is crucial for decision-making, as it involves the appreciation of ideas and viewpoints held by individuals within the organization. This also includes sensitivity to individual needs, all of which are important additions to the decision-making process. Individualized viewing, therefore, improves the decision-making process and the quality of decisions by allowing leadership to obtain as much information as possible through two-way communication with subordinates (Chebon, Aruasa, & Chirchir, 2019).

Individualized consideration is the involvement of people in the transformation process of an organization. These bring with them the need to properly diagnose their wants, needs, values, and abilities. This type of activity leads to a higher level of trust in the leader. So, apart from a global picture, a transformational leader needs to know what motivates each of their team members individually. Human desires and needs are different. Some want certainty, some want excitement and change; some prefer money and some free time. A leader who is aware of the different needs and desires of people has the opportunity to use all these different demands in the right way.

Through their behavior, transformational leaders show acceptance of individual differences and distribute tasks according to their personal affinity. Based on the progress in the execution of the individual tasks, a manager receives a picture of the regularity (or irregularity) of their own actions from an individualized perspective (Ogola, Sikalieh & Linge, 2017).

Individualized consideration is the degree to which the leader attends to each followers needs, acts as a mentor or coach to the followers, and listens to the follower's concerns and needs. The leader gives empathy and support, keeps communication open, and places challenges before the followers. This also encompasses the need for respect and celebrates the individual contribution that each follower can make to the team. The followers have a will and aspirations for self-development and have intrinsic motivation for their tasks.

Individual consideration is an employee cultivation process where employees' personal needs will be in consideration. Even employees' private life including their family members is treated as a whole. The process of individualized consideration will make employees feel indebtedness and feeling of appropriateness. This will develop a strong sense of emotional bond with the organizations, hence, employees remain loyal, and performance can be sustained. Previously individual consideration's focus was on employee career development enhancing the potential of employees, developing abilities, and developing individuals based on culture and personal needs (Hosna, islam &Hamid, 2021).

2.1.12.4 Inspirational Motivation

Popa (2012) defined Inspirational Motivation as a quality of a leader which enables him in converting and communicating the vision with full enthusiasm and confidence. Inspirational motivation is a leader's ability to articulate a compelling vision of a better future for an organization so that followers move from self-interest to the collective interests of the organization (Edirisooriya, 2020). This inspires enthusiasm among the followers, willing to abhor the status quo and enthusiastically pursue the aspired better future. However, this contradicts the premise of the individualized perspective of a transformative leader, which requires the leader to focus on the interests and needs of the individual (Magasi, 2021). It can be concluded that the leader strives to meet the needs of the followers in order to enable the followers to generate more collective gains

for the organization. Eva et al. (2019) criticize it as unethical for the leader to use followers as a means to an intended end. From this perspective, the manager would be accused of not being altruistic but rather egocentric.

Inspirational motivation refers to the style which creates an attractive goal of the future and the demonstration of optimism and enthusiasm and the leader's behaviours aimed at inspiring and motivating followers to attain ambitious and challenging goals, or even apparently unattainable ones. Inspirational motivation involves a leaders' ability to inspire enthusiasm and optimism to subordinates, the outcome being the improvement of organizational performance. The inspirational motivation constructs considered in this study are visionary, optimism, confidence and stimulation (Anyiko-Awori, Namada & Linge, 2018). Inspirational motivation is used by leaders through social persuasion to inspire followers' belief that they can perform better (Bandura, 1997). When leaders inspire their employees to envision a better future and performance, it becomes a self-fulfilling prophecy and leads to them achieving their expected performance. Top, Abdullah, and Faraj (2020) find that inspirational motivation is strongly correlated with high achievement, partly because of this high expectation of achievement among highly effective followers.

Inspirational motivation comes from using both effective and communicative influence styles. This behavior expresses the importance of leaders instilling high expectations in employees, inspiring and motivating them by providing meaning and challenges for employees to develop a shared vision in organizations. Inspirational managers align individual and organizational goals, making achieving organizational goals an attractive means of achieving personal goals. The manager offers meaning and challenge that motivates and inspires the work of the employees. In this regard, the leader fosters team spirit, enthusiasm, and optimism in their followers by engaging them in a positive vision of the future and communicating high expectations that followers want to achieve (Ngaithe, K'Aol, Lewa & Ndwiga, 2016).

Inspirational motivation refers to the way leaders motivate and inspire their followers to reach ambitious goals and view the future with optimism. Inspirational motivation is an aspect seen in leaders when they act in ways that cause employees to perform better by instilling a sense of

meaning in their work (Anyiko-Awori, Namada & Linge, 2018). It is widely used by leaders to develop a collective vision of the organization among employees. In this way, leaders create collective goals to be achieved for employees. Frequent interaction between employees goes a long way toward achieving the goal. Transformational leaders inspire employees by teaching them the meaning of work. This leads to employees developing a willingness to perform. Leaders inspire employees to work as a team and achieve the set goal through good performance (Afsar et al., 2019). Inspirational motivation is used to define organizational motives and vision for employees. Through inspirational motivation, employee performance is driven towards achieving the company's vision by inspiring and engaging employees. Managers inspire employees to motivate speeches, words by speaking to them individually. Leaders also use symbolic and imagery processes to motivate employees to perform (Hosna, Islam & Hamid, 2021).

Inspirational motivation is also the degree to which the leader articulates a vision that is appealing and inspiring to followers. Leaders with inspirational motivation challenge followers with high standards communicate optimism about future goals and provide meaning for the task at hand. The visionary aspects of leadership are supported by communication skills that make the vision understandable, precise, powerful and engaging.

2.1.13 Conceptual Framework

Fig 2.1. Conceptual framework of Emotional Intelligence and transformational leadership

In line with the purposes of the study, the diagram shows that the independent variable is emotional intelligence, and the dependent variable is transformational leadership behavior. The relationship

between the sub-dimensions of these two variables will be examined in the study. Figure 2.1 shows the dimensions of emotional intelligence and transformational leadership behavior and the relationship between them. The diagram also shows that the components of independent variable which includes self awareness, team work, effective communication and motivation relates with the components of dependent variables which includes intellectual stimulation, idealized influence, individual consideration and inspirational motivation.

2.2 Theoretical Framework

The Following Theories were used in the Study

- i. Triarchic Theory of Intelligence
- ii. The Leader-Member-Exchange (LMX) theory
- iii. Transformational Leadership Theory
- iv. Traits Theory in Leadership
- v. Behavioral Leadership Theories
- vi. Situational Theories in Leadership

2.2.1 Triarchic Theory of Intelligence

Triarchic Theory of Intelligence was proposed by Robert Sternberg in 1985. The theory is based on the definition of intelligence as the ability to achieve success based on one's personal standards and one's socio-cultural context. According to the triarchic theory, intelligence has three aspects: analytical, creative, and practical (Sternberg, 1985).

Analytical intelligence also referred to as componential intelligence, refers to intelligence that is applied to analyze or evaluate problems and arrive at solutions.

Creative intelligence is the ability to go beyond what is given to create novel and interesting ideas. This type of intelligence involves imagination, innovation, and problem-solving.

Practical intelligence is the ability that individuals use to solve problems faced in daily life, when a person finds the best fit between themselves and the demands of the environment. Adapting to

the demands environment involves either utilizing knowledge gained from experience to purposefully change oneself to suit the environment (adaptation), changing the environment to suit oneself (shaping), or finding a new environment in which to work (selection).

Emotional intelligence has turned out to be progressively mainstream as a measure for distinguishing individuals who are successful in life, and as an instrument for reaching this success. The idea of emotional intelligence clarifies why two individuals of a similar IQ can achieve inconceivably extraordinarily different levels of accomplishment in life (Goleman, 1998) as individuals are in some cases successful not due to their knowledge, but rather because of their capacity to interact with individuals socially and emotionally by utilizing charming temperament in their exchanges (St.Clair, 2004).

2.2.2 The Leader-Member-Exchange (LMX) theory

The Leader-Member-Exchange (LMX) theory challenges the assumption that leaders treat followers in a collective way, as a group. The theory explains that the relationship between managers and their subordinates develops over time as a result of rule-making processes and social exchange between them. A study by Krishnan (2005), on Leader-Member Exchange, Transformational Leadership, and Value Systems found that LMX is positively related to transformational leadership, which in turn is positively related to terminal value system congruence.

Krishnan (2005), a study that made use of a sample of 100 pairs of managers and subordinates from a non-profit organization in the United States studied the four outcomes which are; perceived effectiveness of leader and work unit, follower satisfaction with leader, follower's motivation to put in extra effort, and follower's intention to quit the organization. Results of regression analysis using the forward option show that transformational leadership is a stronger predictor of effectiveness, satisfaction, and extra effort than LMX and terminal value system congruence. Due to its rule-making processes between a leader and follower, this theory is closely linked to individual consideration where coaching and mentorship are key ingredients, the follower is treated individually and learning opportunities are created.

2.2.3 Transformational Leadership Theory

Transformational leadership theory, formulated by Burns in 1978 in the political context for leaders to influence their followers and extended to the organizational context by Bass in 1985, postulates that a leader can motivate followers to change their belief system, values, and attitudes in order to perform better than they thought possible (Mwesigwa et al. 2020). Furthermore, the charisma possessed by idealized influence leaders builds trust between themselves and their followers (Le & Le, 2021), creating an enabling environment through which the followers willingly carry out their assigned responsibilities without coercion. Among other researchers, Mugizi et al. (2019) utilized this theory in investigating the relationship between leadership style and teachers' retention, observing that transformational leaders can achieve positive outcomes such as employee retention. In addition, this study used the theory to explain how idealized influence and inspirational motivation contribute to desired organizational outcomes such as performance, talented staff retention, organizational commitment, and self-efficacy among other emerging phenomena.

2.2.4 Traits Theory in Leadership

The understanding of "leaders are born not made" regarding the "theory of traits" in the oldest sources of the Ancient Greek and Roman periods has revealed the assumption that leaders are born with superior characteristics. Traits Theory aims to discover the characteristics that make leaders effective and to train future leaders in this direction. According to this theory, the various personal or psychological characteristics of the individual make the individual a leader. This theory argues that leadership comes from birth, the individual has innate leadership abilities, and that these individuals will manifest themselves as leaders under all conditions. As a result of the researches about the theory of traits, 5% of leadership studies used common descriptive statements in 4 or 5 studies. These features; intelligence, self confidence, broad-mindedness, being healthy, being born in high socio-economic society (Aslan, 2009). However, "As a result of the research conducted on three hundred leaders such as Clara Barton and Winston Churchill, it has been determined that these leaders do not have ideal lives or superior features. For example, it has been demonstrated that 25% have severe physical disabilities, and 50% were abused as children or grew up in poverty"

(Altılar, 2005). According to this research, leaders do not have the characteristic of being born in a high socio-economic society, which is one of the conditions in the theory of characteristics. Traits Theory lost its effect in the 1950s, and behaviors of the leader began to be examined instead of characteristics. However, today it is claimed that certain personality traits are important in the emergence of the leader or the influence of the person (Demir, Chevirgen, & Yılmaz, 2010). As a result of the trait theory being inadequate to explain leadership, social psychologists have turned to studies to test the functions and structures of groups. As a result, they developed a behavioral approach that considers the leader as "the person who performs the behaviors that will help the group to reach certain results for the group of which it is a member" (Shimshek, 2006).

2.2.5 Behavioral Leadership Theories

Behavioral leadership theories suggest that behavioral characteristics, not personal characteristics, determine the effectiveness of the leader, and leadership behaviors can also be gained through education. The leader must achieve the goals set by the group; such as the type of communication with the audience, the group commitment, the way of motivation, the contribution of group members to the decision-making process, the way they manage the meetings, the way of giving orders, and making the resources within the group. Various applied and theoretical studies by management scientists have contributed to the development of behavioral leadership theory. The main ones are Ohio State University Leadership Studies, Michigan State University studies, the Managerial Diagram Model of Blake and Mouton, and McGregor's X and Y Theories study (Demir, Cevirgen & Yılmaz, 2010). There are two pioneering schools among these studies carried out from the 1950-the 1960s until today. "These are The Ohio State Leadership Studies, which treat leadership as a person indexed" leader figure "and try to measure the leadership effect on subordinates' perceptions and motivations (The Michigan Leadership Studies)." The Ohio State University Leadership Research was conducted by the Bureau of Business Research in 1945 to investigate the effect of leadership behavior on military air force personnel on group performance and job satisfaction (Aslan, 2009). While Ohio State Leadership Studies tried to classify leadership behaviors and develop scales and questionnaires that define behavior, they considered the behaviors of managers in two independent and distinct dimensions initiating structure leadership

and consideration leadership behavior. The leadership gives importance, acts in a leader, supportive and friendly manner, deals with subordinates, listens to their problems, consults them on important matters, and does not ignore their advice.

In the context of structural leadership behavior, the leader formally sets and defines his or her subordinates' roles, assigns subordinates to roles, sets clear performance standards and expects subordinates to comply with these standards and procedures, criticize or punish those who do not comply, coordinate the activities of a large number of subordinates. (Yukl, 2002). In the context of the main results of the Ohio University Research, it was found that increasing the behavior of the leader taking into account the understanding decreases turnover and absenteeism; It has been concluded that an increase in the behavior of the leader that activates the structure increases the performance of the group members (Kochel, 2003). Another study focusing on the behavior of the leader is Douglas McGregor's Theory of X and Y. According to the theory, one of the most important factors determining the behavior of managers is their assumptions about human behavior. The basic assumptions of McGregor's X and Y theories are shown in the table.

Table 3.3 McGregor X and Y theories

X Theory	Y Theory
A mediocre person prefers to be led.	Work is as natural for a person as play and rest.
The average person does not want to take responsibility, is not very willing, and prefers assurance to everything.	A person is not naturally lazy; it is his experiences that make him like that. A person works by self-control in line with the goal he sets.
For these, the manager must force people to work, control them closely, and evaluate them for achieving goals.	Therefore, what a leader needs to do is to create a suitable environment and to ensure that the person improves themselves.
Human beings do not like to work by nature and avoid work as much as possible.	Every person has potential. Under the appropriate circumstances, one develops them and learns to assume more responsibility.

In this theory, a leader who chooses X theory will show authoritarian behavior, and a leader who adopts Y theory is more democratic and participatory, consults his subordinates, and encourages them to participate in decisions. McGregor preferred the Y theory. On the other hand, the X and Y theory seeks to classify people. However, it is extremely difficult to classify human behavior in

a simple way. In the words of Tyler, "each person is a group of personalities that can be different people at different times, and people are at least as variable as chameleons."

2.2.6 Situational Theories in Leadership

Previous traits theory and behavioral theories claim that there is only one ideal leadership style, situational leadership theories debated that the most appropriate leadership behavior can change according to circumstances and situations. Instead of the view that situational leadership theories, previous traits theory, and behavioral theories claim that there is only one ideal leadership style, he argued that the most appropriate leadership behavior could vary according to the conditions and situation (Tengilimoglu, 2005). According to researchers like Hersey and Blanchard, leadership depends on situational factors rather than inherited and personal characteristics. This theory is leadership that changes situation-specific. For example, in some cases, a more autocratic approach is required, while in others, a more participatory approach may be required. Besides, there may be differences at different levels of the same organization in terms of the required leadership style (Demir, Chevirgen, & Yılmaz, 2010). In other words, leaders may need to adopt different approaches in management, depending on the different situations that may arise (Giderler, 2005). According to this theory, which tries to explain leadership by taking the conditions into account, the factor that determines the effectiveness of a leader in the conditions they are in (Demir, Chevirgen, & Yılmaz, 2010). In other words, the leadership process is a complex process that consists of the relations between the leader, the audience, and their conditions (Tengilimoglu, 2005). Contingency theories are as follows (Aslan, 2009).

- i. Fred Fiedler's Effective Leadership Theory
- ii. House and Evans' Path-Goal Theory of Leadership
- iii. Vroom-Yetton Leadership Theory
- iv. Reddin's Three-Dimensional Leadership Theory
- v. Hersey-Blanchard's Situational Leadership Theory

The best-known theory among Situational Theories is Fiedler's 'Contingency Theory', which was developed by Fred Fiedler and his friends in 1964. This theory has been examined in two

dimensions as the "Relationship Oriented Approach" and "Business-Oriented Approach" similar to the previous Ohio and Michigan University studies. In addition to these two leadership approaches, Fiedler proposed three important situational variables in assessing whether a situation is suitable for leadership. These variables are "Leader-Member Relationships," "Task Structure," and "Leader's Legal Power" (Aslan, 2009). Leader member relations express the nature of the relations between the leader and the working group. If these relationships are considered good, the environment for leadership is positive. If the opposite is the case, the negative environment is mentioned. The task structure is concerned with the existence of a predetermined way and method of doing the job. Planned work creates a positive environment for leadership, while unplanned work creates a negative environment. The leader's legal power is the leader's legal power through his managerial position. This legal power may be too much or too little. If it is too much, it is a positive environment for leadership, and if it is less, a negative environment is mentioned (Kochel, 1993). The basic assumption of Fiedler Theory; Leadership behavior will not change from situation to situation (Aslan, 2009). According to Fiedler, with leadership training, leaders cannot be changed; only with education, they can understand their leadership approach. However, situations can be changed according to the abilities of the leaders, or the leader can learn to change the situations in order to be successful (Ceylan and Begeç, 2000).

The road-goal theory developed by Robert House and Martin Evans in 1970 is based on the expectation theory from motivation theories (Baysal and Tekarslan, 2004; Eren, 2003). Path-Purpose theory suggests that the leader will behave differently in different situations (Hollander & Offerman, 1990). In this respect, it differs from Fiedler's theory. According to the Path-Purpose theory, there are two dimensions that affect human behavior; - Expectations of individuals that certain results will be achieved with certain behaviors. - The value is given by individuals to these results. In this case, it is stated that the leader has two important duties within the organization. The first is the case of setting organizational goals and thus telling the audience what behavior will be rewarded. The second is to increase the rewards by supporting the audience in the expected behaviors and reaching the goal (Eren, 2008). Path-Goal theory tried to explain how leadership behaviors affect the satisfaction of subordinates with two situational factors. These are the personal characteristics of subordinates and the characteristics of the environment.

The personal characteristics of subordinates are also determined as self-control and perceived ability. Its environmental characteristics constitute the structure, formal authority systems, and business groups. The Path-Goal theory has four leadership behaviors (Hoffman & Morgeson, 2003). These; Autocratic leadership, one of the traditional leadership behavior styles, is defined as an autocratic leadership style, in which the decisions within the organization are taken only by the manager by using the authority arising from its position. Democratic leadership style emerges as a leadership behavior style that is popular in the period when management tends to and attaches importance to human relations. A good relationship of trust between such a leader and his audience, that is, the leader's trust in his audience, encourages their subordinates in determining organizational goals, plans and policies, organizing, division of labor, and participation in decision-making processes. Participatory leadership is defined as a decision-making power shared with employees or a form of joint decision-making. Leadership oriented toward success sets high and important goals. His subordinates have full confidence that they will accomplish these tasks in the best way. Another of the situational leadership theories is the Vroom-Yetton leadership theory, put forward by Victor Vroom and Philip Yetton in 1973. Later, this theory was developed by Victor Vroom and Arthur G. Jago in 1988 (Lunenburg, 2010). This theory focused on the leader's decision-making process. Therefore, it is also expressed as a decision tree model. The leader follows the decision tree until the result is reached. At the end of the branches, what the leader will do is determined.

According to this theory,

- i. Autocratic-1 (A1): The leader solves the problem on his own in the light of current information.
- ii. Autocratic-2 (A2): The leader asks for additional information from his subordinates and solves the problem himself.
- iii. Consultant-1 (C1): The leader takes the individual thoughts and offers of his subordinates before making a decision, and then makes the decision himself.
- iv. Consultant-2 (C2): The leader takes the thoughts and proposals of his subordinates as a group before making a decision and then makes his decision himself.
- v. Group-1 (G1): The leader discusses the problem with his subordinates individually, and a joint decision is made.
- vi. Group-2 (G2): The leader gathers all his subordinates together as a group and ensures that decisions are taken in a democratic way without imposing his own opinion.
- vii. Delegate (D1): The leader gives the information about the solution of the problem and the responsibility of solving the problem to the subordinate and asks the subordinate to inform the subordinate how a solution has been reached.

According to this theory, the leader should use different decision methods to solve different problems to increase the efficiency and productivity of the employees. No decision-making process can be described as the best in all conditions (Zel, 2001)

The Vroom-Yetton theory is a more complex theory than the old models. But, the increase in the number of opportunities and situations can be easily solved with the software program. As a result, this theory has been supported by other studies in the literature. Yet, its weaknesses and inconsistencies were observed in the search for effective leadership. Emotional intelligence research in leadership today indicates that behaviors have a learnable side. In this sense, it can be stated that Vroom and Yetton's Theory is similar to this view.

Paul Hersey and Kenneth Blanchard's "Life Cycle Approach" is a theory developed by making use of Ohio University studies, Blake and Mouton's Management Style Matrix, and Reddin's

Three-Dimensional Leadership Behavior. In the first step of the models, there are "Task Behavior" and "Relationship Behavior" dimensions (Aslan, 2009).

In theory, the subject that emphasized is the situational variables related to the maturity levels of subordinates. Maturity means "job maturity" (having technical and general knowledge about the job) and "psychological maturity" (self-confidence, fully skilled, etc.). If subordinates have low task maturity, that is, they are less skilled or have low education level, and low self-confidence, the more mature skills they desire to see from their leaders, are different from the behaviors that subordinate with high education and self-confidence and desire to work demand from their leaders.

Figure 3.3. Hersey-Blanchard's Situational Leadership Theory (Luthans, 1995)

Figure 3.3. Shows that there are four categories related to maturity levels. These;

M1; people have neither the expertise nor the enthusiasm to do anything.

M2; people have no capabilities but a willingness to do the task.

M3; people have talents but don't want to do what leaders want

M4; people have both abilities and a desire to do what they want (Luthans, 1995).

It can be seen from Figure 3.3. That as the audience reaches a high level of maturity, the leader's control and attitudes towards the person decrease. While in M1, the viewers need a clear and specific direction, in M2, there is a need for a high task, high person behavior. M3 shows that low relationship and low task can also be a problem of motivation, which requires a participatory, supportive leadership style. In M4, on the other hand, the leader does not need to do much because the audience also has the ability and the desire to take responsibility. Another theory among Contingency Theories is Reddin's "Three-Dimensional Leadership

Theory." Based on the "Task-Oriented" and "Person-Oriented" dimensions of Ohio University Theory and Management Style Matrix, Reddin added the "Effectiveness" dimension to these two dimensions, four of which are effective, four of which are ineffective. He determined his leadership style.

Figure 3.4. Reddin's Three-Dimensional Activity Theory

In Reddin's Leadership Activity Theory, what a manager reveals as a result is more important than what he does. The manager must act effectively in different situations, and the manager should have as much style width as possible. This kind of width enables to prevent or to deal with different situations and thus to have high efficiency.

Based on Ohio University Research, Reddin determines four basic approaches using the variables of whether the leader has more or less authority, whether the leader-subordinate relations are good or bad, and whether the structure of the task is determined.

Figure 3.5. Reddin's leading behavior model

Separated Leader; Engaged in small task sizes and low human relationships, this manager is often helpful in rules and procedures and constantly demonstrates a style of interaction aimed at correcting mistakes. The manager usually gives instructions in writing as his social relations are weak. It considers the organization separately from the individuals that made it up. While evaluating subordinates according to whether they obey the rules or not, they value their superiors according to their work, intelligence, and mind. Managers who adopt this kind of management approach try to avoid possible conflicts that may arise between employees.

Related Leader; This type of managers, who are in high human relations and low task dimensions, accept people as they are and get to know them. They try to establish mutual communication with their subordinates. They see the organization as a system and exhibit a consensual and guiding management style regarding differences of opinion.

Dedicated Leader; Managers, who adopt a managerial style with low human relations and high task dimensions, tend to dominate and dominate the employees. Employees often give verbal orders. He goes to punish error and suppress disagreements.

Integrated Leader; These managers, who have high human relations and high task dimensions, want to be a part of the events and exhibit a participatory management style.

The common point of situational leadership theories described so far; It can be stated that a relationship or task-oriented leadership style will not be valid in all situations and conditions, a task-centered leadership style may cause effects in some cases, and a relationship-centered leadership style can be efficient and effective in some cases (W. J. Reddin, 2002).

2.3 Empirical Review

2.3.1 Self awareness on Intellectual Stimulation

Bratton, Dodd & Brown (2011), conducted a study that aimed to follow a line of research that examines the impact of elements of emotional intelligence (EI), particularly those related to self-awareness, on self-other agreement and performance. Design/methodology/approach This is a quantitative study that employs the same methodology as Sosik and Megerian to analyze survey data gathered from a matched sample of 146 managers and 1,314 subordinates at a large international technology company based in North America. Findings The analysis revealed that the relationship between EI and leader performance is strongest for managers who underestimate their leader abilities. Under estimators earn higher follower ratings of leader performance than all other agreement categories (In agreement/ good, in agreement/ poor, and Over estimators). The analysis also suggests that there appears to be a negative relationship between EI and leader performance for managers who overestimate their leader abilities. Research limitations/ implications of the counterintuitive findings for under estimators as well as the imperative for further study utilizing alternative measures of EI are discussed. Originality/value Previous empirical work in this area used an ad hoc measure of EI. This study extends this work by utilizing a larger, business sample and employing a widely-used and validated measure of EI, the Emotional Quotient Inventory. Results further illuminate the nature of the relationship between EI and self-other agreement and provide a potential selection and development tool for the improvement of leadership performance.

Fauji and Mira (2013) examined the relationship between intellectual stimulation, knowledge sharing, innovation and firm performance. The model tested on the 56 owners of small and medium enterprises (SMEs) in Tegal, Indonesia. This study aimed to determine whether the intellectual stimulation can influence innovation which is mediated by knowledge sharing, and whether innovation can improve a firm's performance. Software analysis techniques PLS (Partial Least Square) are used in this research. The final results indicate that there are positive effects on intellectual stimulation, experiential sharing and explicit knowledge sharing; explicit knowledge sharing has a positive effect on product innovation and product innovation has a positive effect on business performance. While experiential sharing has a positive effect on product innovation, it is not significant, so the hypothesis is rejected.

Yasin, Nawab, Bhatti and Nazir (2014) investigated the relationship of Intellectual Stimulation, Innovations and SMEs Performance. For this purpose, data was collected from the 50 SMEs in Hattar (Haripur) industrial area of Pakistan. Out of 500 questionnaires 350 were returned and 348 were valid for analysis, response rate was 70%. Pearson correlation and regression analysis was used for investigation of this relationship. This study found that intellectual stimulation may be used as tool for the development of innovations and higher SMEs performance and this study also found a strong positive relationship of innovations to the SMEs performance.

Anjali and Anand (2015) analyzed the relationship between the perceived levels of job commitment and intellectually stimulating factors. A cross-sectional study was conducted on a sample size of 150 IT professionals across six companies in Bangalore and Mysore regions, Karnataka. The perceived levels of job commitment in the presence and absence of intellectually stimulating factors were tested using parametric approach. The outcome of the study revealed that in the presence of intellectually stimulating factors, employees are more content with their jobs and their commitment to the job is stronger.

Peng, Lin, Chaubroeck, McDonough, Hu and Zhang (2015) examined the influence of CEOs' intellectually stimulating behavior, namely, encouraging followers to bring up new perspectives and innovative approaches at work, on employees' perceptions of the meaningfulness of their work. Specifically, we examined the moderating roles of firm performance and industry

dynamism. We surveyed the 174 CEOs and employees from 43 firms in innovation-driven industries in the Northern region of China. A 7-point Likert-type scale was used. Descriptive statistics and zero-order correlations were used for statistical analysis. Results showed lower firm performance or rapid and unpredictable changes in the industry are associated with a stronger positive relationship between CEO intellectual stimulation and employee work meaningfulness.

Subhasree and Vishvakarma (2015) examined the impact of self-awareness on eight states of personality. A cognitive assessment survey was made for measuring the time duration of past, present and future thinking of participants within India for 15 hours per day in order to inculcate self-awareness. A sample of (N=40) female participants were taken by using purposive sampling, out of which 20 were residential college students of age 18-25 and 20 were housewives of age 30-45. Eight state questionnaire (8SQ) was administered (pre-test) on them, then exposed to continuous self-awareness for a week and again post-test was taken. The data was analyzed by using t-test. It was observed that there were some states of personality which found to be significant at 0.01 and 0.05, like anxiety, repression, fatigue and arousal.

K'Aol, Ngaithe, Lewa and Ndwiga (2016) examined effect of Intellectual Stimulation and Individualized Consideration on performance of staff in State Owned Enterprises in Kenya. Positivism research philosophy and descriptive research design were used in this study. Stratified random sampling technique was used to select a sample of 163 senior managers from the target population of 275 senior managers. A structured questionnaire was used to collect data from the selected members of top management team in SOEs. The study used factor analysis to reduce data, correlation analysis to establish the relationship between staff performance and intellectual stimulation and individualized consideration, chi square test, Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) and multiple linear regression model to test the hypotheses. The study found that intellectual stimulation was positively and significantly related with staff performance, $r(139) = .73$, $p < .00$ and significantly predicted staff performance, $\beta = .78$, $t(145) = 3.38$, $p < .001$. Individualized consideration was strongly correlated with staff performance $r(138) = .75$, $p < .00$ and significantly predicted staff performance, $\beta = 1.07$, $t(145) = 4.57$, $p < .00$.

Leonard, George, Peter, and Michael (2016), research on Effect of Intellectual Stimulation and Individualized Consideration on Staff Performance in State Owned Enterprises in Kenya. The study used factor analysis to reduce data, correlation analysis to establish the relationship between staff performance and intellectual stimulation and individualized consideration, chi-square test, Analysis of Variance (ANOVA), and a multiple linear regression model to test the hypotheses. The study found that intellectual stimulation was positively and significantly related with staff performance. Individualized consideration was strongly correlated with staff performance and significantly predicted staff performance.

Mary, Damary, and Teresia (2017), research on the Influence of Intellectual Stimulation Leadership Behaviour on Employee Performance in SMEs in Kenya. A correlational research design was employed to investigate the relationship between the independent variable and the dependent variable. Pearson's correlation, multiple regression, and chi-square techniques were used to analyze the data. The results showed that intellectual stimulation leadership behavior and Employee Performance in SMEs in Kenya had a strong positive and significant correlation.

Israel, Marisa, and Susana (2017), research on Leadership Intellectual Stimulation and Team Learning: the Mediating Role of Team Positive effect. Using a cross-sectional sample of 562 employees, nested within 130 teams from 44 small- and medium-sized organizations, we implemented a Structural Equation Model analysis at the team level. Results provide evidence of the strong relationship that intellectual stimulation has on team learning and team positive affect, as well as the potential of positive affect for stimulating team learning. Team positive effect serves as a partial mediator between intellectual stimulation and team learning, contributing to explaining significant additional variance. Leadership intellectual stimulation is a relevant team social resource that provides support for team learning. Also, positive affect contributes significantly to improving learning among teams.

Agyemang, Boateng and Dzandu (2017) explored whether Intellectual stimulation, Idealised Influence and individualized consideration affect knowledge sharing among employees in Ghana. A cross-sectional survey design was employed. The study employed a convenience sampling technique to select a sample size of 500. However, out of the 500 questionnaires

distributed, 283 were used in the final analysis; thus, those that were correctly filled. Data was analyzed using multiple regression. The study found that there is a significant positive relationship between idealised influence and knowledge sharing. However, the relationship between intellectual stimulation and individualized consideration and knowledge sharing was found to be insignificant.

Sancher-Cardona, Salanova and Llorens-Gumbau (2018) investigated how leadership intellectual stimulation relates to team positive affect and team learning. We explore the role of positive affect as mediator between leadership intellectual stimulation and team learning. Using a cross-sectional sample of 562 employees, nested within 130 teams from 44 Spanish small- and medium-size organizations Structural Equation Model analysis was implemented at the team level. Results provide evidence of the strong relationship that intellectual stimulation has on team learning and team positive affect, as well as the potential of positive affect for stimulating team learning. Team positive affect serves as a partial mediator between intellectual stimulation and team learning, contributing to explain significant additional variance. Leadership intellectual stimulation is a relevant team social resource that provides support for team learning.

Chebon, Aruasa and Chirchir (2019) conducted a study that sought to determine the influence of transformational leadership on employee performance drawing evidence from the Moi Teaching and Referral Hospital (MTRH) in Kenya. The target population of the study comprised 3,739 employees (18 staff from top management; 110 employees from middle level management and 3611 employees from the operational level). The sampling frame used in the study was the staff establishment dashboard for MTRH. Stratified random sampling method was employed and simple random sampling used in each of the stratum to recruit respondents to participate in the study. The sample size is 463 respondents (17 from top management; 86 from middle management and 360 operational staff). On the influence of individualized consideration on employee performance, the study found out that there is recognition of employees to better productivity, teaching and coaching of staff. Furthermore, supervisors respect and celebrate individual contribution and provide opportunities for the identification of needs and capabilities of others. Regarding the influence of intellectual stimulation on employee performance, the study revealed

that supervisors encourages high productivity through creativity and innovation and encourages staff to rethink ideas that had never been questioned.

Rahman,S., Ferdausy,S.,& Uddin, A. (2019) conducted a study on the purpose of identifying the relationships between emotional intelligence and the components of transformational leadership behavior of the supervisors. Data for this study were collected from 166 subordinates (who rated their supervisors' emotional intelligence and the components of transformational leadership behavior) working at different organizations around the UK with the help of a structured questionnaire. Results indicated that emotional intelligence positively correlated with all the components of transformational leadership behaviour. Implications, limitations, and future research directions are also discussed.

Khan, Khan, Rehan and Khan (2020) conducted a study on the impacts of intellectual stimulation on Employees' innovative behaviors: the Mediating role of contingent rewards. The survey and questionnaire approach were used to obtain data. A population of 1148 employees of four universities of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, Pakistan with 296 sample size was selected using statistical formula. A 7-point Likert scale was used to measure the variables. Correlation procedure and hierarchical regression was used for statistical analysis. There is significant association among research variables meaning that both intellectual stimulation and contingent rewards are vital for improving the employees' innovative behavior.

Sahota, Goeres, Kelly, Tang, Hofmeister and Alberti (2020) conducted a study that sought to elicit student views on intellectual stimulation in family medicine, and their understanding of academic family medicine. It was a qualitative focus group study of volunteer students from the University of Calgary, Canada, and Newcastle University, UK. Six focus groups were conducted with 51 participants. The data were analysed thematically. Students associated intellectual stimulation in family medicine with clinical practice. Intellectual stimulation was related to problem solving and the challenge of having to know a little about everything, along with clinical uncertainty and the need to be vigilant to avoid missing diagnoses. Student awareness of academic family medicine was limited, and students identified it with teaching rather than research.

Sulistiawana, Ekowati and Putri (2020) conducted a research with the purpose of examining how regulatory focus and employee creativity and how the interaction effect between two contextual factors, intellectual stimulation and individual participation will strengthen the effect of promotion focus to individual creativity. The research used employees in radio station as respondents with total 142 respondents. The authors tested the hypothesis by using hierarchical regression analysis and moderated regression analysis in order to test the moderating effect of intellectual stimulation and individual participation. The results of this study showed that promotion focus is positively related to creativity, whilst prevention focus is negatively related to creativity. Our interesting finding was only intellectual stimulation has a moderation effect between promotion focus and creativity.

Thuan (2020) examined the role of follower creative ability and job autonomy as mediating mechanisms linking leader intellectual stimulation with follower creativity. A time-lagged study was undertaken to gather data from employees working in the information technology sector in Vietnam (N = 415). This study used structural equation modeling (SEM) to analyze the gathered data. This study found a positive direct relationship between leader intellectual stimulation and follower creative performance. Moreover, the follower's proactive personality moderated this direct relationship. Furthermore, the results illustrated that follower creative ability and job autonomy partially mediated the positive effect of leader intellectual stimulation on follower creativity.

Chella, Pipitone, Morrin, & Racy (2020) The experience of inner speech is a common one. Such a dialogue accompanies the introspection of mental life and fulfills essential roles in human behavior, such as self-restructuring, self-regulation, and re-focusing on attentional resources. Although the underpinning of inner speech is mostly investigated in psychological and philosophical fields, the research in robotics generally does not address such a form of self-aware behavior. Existing models of inner speech inspire computational tools to provide a robot with this form of self-awareness. Here, the widespread psychological models of inner speech are reviewed, and a cognitive architecture for a robot implementing such a capability is outlined in a simplified setup

Garden, Jones, Passmore (2021) conducted a study on the Self-awareness is often seen as a critical component in leadership and career success, and has therefore become a feature in MBAs, leadership development, and management education. It has become a popular “buzzword” in management literature, yet when reviewing this literature, there appears to be no consistent definition of the construct. This article reports a systematic literature review, covering how the construct of self-awareness is defined and how it differs from self-consciousness and self-knowledge within the context of management education. After screening, 31 articles were included in the review, analysis of which identified there is an overlap with how self-awareness, self-consciousness, and self-knowledge are defined. Other themes from our analysis include the identification of the components of self-awareness, how to be self-aware, and the purpose of self-awareness. The contribution of our article is the provision of clarity on the construct of self-awareness and a working definition, which can be used in the fields of leadership and management development by practitioners in education and organizations, and for future research within the context of adult development and the workplace.

Khan, Amin and Saif (2022) examined the relationship between individualized consideration, idealized influence of transformational leadership and inspirational motivation and intellectual stimulation. The study applied a cross-sectional approach to examine the relationships between predictor (individualized consideration) and criterion variable, idealized influence (Role Model), mediated by inspirational motivation and intellectual stimulation in organisations across Pakistan. The results showed that the predictor (individualized consideration), mediator 1 (inspirational motivation) and mediator 2 (intellectual stimulation) are significantly associated with the dependent variable of idealized influence (R -values = .560, .737, & .815), respectively. The mediation statistics is also significantly upholding the assumptions of mediation. The inspirational motivation reduces Beta of ‘c’ from .602 to 0.223 of ‘ \hat{c} ’, while intellectual stimulation decreases Beta of ‘c’ from .602 to 0.160 of ‘ \hat{c} ’, thereby showing greater role of intellectual stimulation than inspirational motivation.

Bratton, Dodd & Brown (2011), conducted a study that aimed to follow a line of research that examines the impact of elements of emotional intelligence (EI), particularly those related to self-

awareness, on self-other agreement and performance. Design/methodology/approach This is a quantitative study that employs the same methodology as Sosik and Megerian to analyze survey data gathered from a matched sample of 146 managers and 1,314 subordinates at a large international technology company based in North America. Findings The analysis revealed that the relationship between EI and leader performance is strongest for managers who underestimate their leader abilities. Underestimators earn higher follower ratings of leader performance than all other agreement categories (In agreement/good, In agreement/poor, and Overestimators). The analysis also suggests that there appears to be a negative relationship between EI and leader performance for managers who overestimate their leader abilities. Research limitations/implications of the counterintuitive findings for underestimators as well as the imperative for further study utilizing alternative measures of EI are discussed. Originality/value Previous empirical work in this area used an ad hoc measure of EI. This study extends this work by utilizing a larger, business sample and employing a widely-used and validated measure of EI, the Emotional Quotient Inventory. Results further illuminate the nature of the relationship between EI and self-other agreement and provide a potential selection and development tool for the improvement of leadership performance

London, Sessa, & Shelley,(2023) conducted a study on the Self-awareness—how we see ourselves and the effects we have on our environment—influences our behavior and the type of person we want to become. This article examines recent research and areas of practice that address the meaning of self-awareness and how it develops over time. We build on extant comprehensive reviews of the literature to define self-awareness and its accuracy, measurement, and effects, including the dark side of being overly introspective. We offer a framework to integrate theory-based processes. We present the results of a literature search of educational interventions aimed at increasing mindfulness through reflection, feedback, and coaching. We conclude with calls for research and implications for practice in areas of measurement, tracking changes, interventions, and self in relation to others in areas of societal impact, self-presentation on digital media, and promoting self-awareness in relation to organization and team membership.

2.3.2 Team work on Idealized Influence

Adeoye and Torubelli (2011) conducted a study to explain the interactive and relative effects of emotional intelligence and human relationship management on the organizational commitment of Nigerian civil servants. Simple random sampling technique was used in selecting 300 participants from the Ministries of Education, Local government affairs, Civil service commission, Agriculture and Governors office of Bayelsa and Oyo States. Of the sample selected, 160 were males and 140 were females. Their ages range between 28 and 55 years with a mean age of 36.7 and a standard deviation of 6.9. Three instruments: Emotional intelligence scales (EIS), Human relationship management scale (HRMS) and Organizational commitment questionnaire (OCQ) were used to collect data from the participants. Data analysis involved the use of Pearson Product Moment Correlation and multiple regressions. The results indicated that the two independent variables, when taken together, were effective in predicting organizational commitment. Each of the variables contributed significantly to the prediction of organizational commitment with emotional intelligence making a higher contribution to the prediction of Organizational commitment. Based on the outcome of the study, Emotional intelligence intervention and Human relationship management programmes were advocated in order to enhance the organizational commitment of the civil servants.

Rana and Ajmal (2012) researched the Transformational Leadership Style as Predictor of Decision Making Styles: Moderating Role of Emotional Intelligence in Pakistan. Regression analysis is utilized to study the relationship between transformational leadership style and decision-making styles and step-wise regression analysis is used to study moderating effect of emotional intelligence. The study found that transformational leadership style strongly predicts rational and dependent decision-making styles and weakly predicts intuitive and spontaneous decision-making styles while no association was found with avoidant decision-making styles. The research also found that emotional intelligence moderates the relationship between transformational leadership styles and decision-making styles.

Sobhi-Gharamaleki (2012) conducted a research to understand the relationship of emotional intelligence and its dimensions (self-awareness, self-management, social awareness and

relationship management) to achievement motivation. The statistical population included all female first grade high school students studying in Karaj city. A sample of 60 students was selected by multi-stage random cluster sampling procedure. All participants completed the Achievement Motivation-Denver Youth Survey and Bradberry-Greaves Emotional Intelligence test. Results showed a significant positive relationship between achievement motivation and emotional intelligence. Global emotional intelligence as well as its components, self-awareness, self-management and relationship management correlated positively with achievement motivation. But social awareness was not found to be associated with achievement motivation. The results showed that adolescents with high emotional intelligence hold more realistic perceptions in interpersonal relationships and this ability probably helps them develop achievement motivation. Higher achievement motivation may help enhance feelings of self-efficacy as well as academic motivation.

Shahram (2014) researched the Relationship between Emotional Intelligence and Transformational Leadership in Sports Managers in Iran. The method of the study was a correlation. The data were analyzed using both descriptive and inferential statistics including mean, standard deviation, minimum and maximum scores, Pearson correlation formula, independent t-test, and multiple regression analysis. The results revealed significant positive correlations, both simple and multiple, between emotional intelligence and transformational leadership style in the sports managers in Alborz province.

Yunus and Aduros (2015) researched on the impact of transformational leadership style which consists of four dimensions (4I's), namely, Idealized Influence (II), Inspirational Motivation (IM), Intellectual Stimulation (IS), and Individual Consideration (IC) toward the job performance among employees. It also determines the moderating effect of the trust of employees to their leaders or managers with the relationship between two constructs, as well as trust in transformational leadership style and employees' job performance. A set of 220 questionnaires were distributed to employees at several food manufacturing companies in Shah Alam which are Silver Bird Group Berhad (High 5) and Gardenia Bakeries Sdn. Bhd. There are other types of leadership styles however for this study Transformational Leadership styles were used. The findings were analyzed

using descriptive and statistical statistics. The result of the study indicated that there was a positive and significant relationship between transformational leadership styles and employee's job performance.

Juma and Ndisya (2016) investigated the Influence of Transformational Leadership on Employee Performance using a case study of Safaricom Limited. The influence of intellectual stimulation on employee performance was examined using five measures namely: Employee's opportunity to work in a way they think best; consent to determine their own pace for change; consent to make a judgment in unraveling a problem; employee's receipt of assistance to reconsider ideas that had never been looked into; and employees' challenge to deliberate on old problems in new ways.

Sahibzada, Kakakhel and Khan (2016) examined the impact of idealized influence and inspirational motivation of leaders on employees' job satisfaction. Data was collected through a well-established questionnaire from 330 employees of 10 different private sector universities located in KPK. The results using descriptive statistics confirmed a non-zero relationship of the two dimensions of leadership with employees' job satisfaction. Idealized Influence showed significant association with employee's job satisfaction. The study brought out important findings to bring about behavioral improvements in leadership style of education sector that will eventually enhance levels of Job Satisfaction of employees.

Liberty and Kida (2017) examined the effect of emotional intelligence on employees' performance with the aim of understanding the influence of emotional intelligence of employees on their performance in the organization. The variables studied were emotional intelligence on organizational employee performance. Six organizations from mixed industries in operation in Maiduguri Borno State were studied. Questionnaires were administered on the 121 samples which were determined purposely. A Chi-Square (X^2) was used to test the hypotheses formulated. It was found that the use of emotional intelligence was a more potent drive to any accomplishment than monetary rewards.

Ogola, Sikalieh and Linge (2017) investigated the influence of Idealized Influence leadership behavior on employee performance in Small and Medium Enterprise in Kenya. This study targeted

the KPMG top 100 SMEs of 2014 in Kenya. A correlational research design was employed to establish the relationship between Idealized Influence leadership behavior and employee performance in Small and Medium Enterprises in Kenya. The study found that Idealized Influence leadership behavior and Employee Performance in SMEs in Kenya had a strong positive and significant correlation $r(194) = .829, p < .000$ and a positive and significant relationship ($\beta = .829, t(194) = 20.503, p < .000$). Results show that if a leader inculcates trust in employees, practices high ethical values, acts as a role model to the employees and encourages employees to take risks; these will positively affect employees work and hence high performance levels.

Nyokabi, K'Aol and Njenga (2017) conducted a study to determine the effect of idealized influence and inspirational motivation of the Chief Executive Officer (CEO) on the performance of senior managers in the private sector in Kenya. The study adopted the positivism research philosophy and descriptive correlational research design. The target population consisted of 984 senior managers reporting to the CEOs of 183 private sector companies under the umbrella of the Kenya Private Sector Alliance (KEPSA). A sample size of 284 was drawn using stratified random sampling, and data was collected using structured questionnaires. A response rate of 92% was realized. Data was analyzed using descriptive statistics namely frequencies, means, and standard deviation. Inferential statistics were also used in the analysis which included Pearson's correlation, Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) and multiple linear regression. Results of the multiple linear regression showed that the CEO's idealized influence significantly predicted performance of senior managers $R^2 = .505, F(1, 260) = 264.042, p < .05; \beta = .711, t(260) = 16.249, p < .05$. Testing the influence of goal orientation as a moderating variable showed that goal orientation significantly predicted the relationship between idealized influence and inspirational motivation of the CEO and performance of senior managers $R^2 = .839, F(2, 5) = 265.099, p < .05, \beta = .111, t = 3.900, p < .05$.

Njiraini, K'Aol and Linge (2018) determined the extent to which idealized influence and inspirational motivation influence job satisfaction among employees in commercial banks in Kenya. The study adopted a positivist research philosophy and a descriptive correlation research design. The target population consisted of 10,310 managerial employees in commercial banks in

Kenya. A sample of 424 employees was obtained from the population using a stratified random sampling technique. Data were collected using structured questionnaires. A response rate of 82% was obtained. Data was analyzed using descriptive statistics and inferential statistics. Inferential statistical methods used to analyze the data were Chi-square, Pearson's correlation, ANOVA, and multiple linear regressions. The Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) tool version 22 was used to analyze the data. Correlation analysis found that idealized influence, inspirational motivation and job security were positively and significantly correlated to job satisfaction $r(346) = .496, p < .05$, $r(347) = .587, p < .05$, $r(347) = .697, p < .05$ respectively. Multiple linear regression results showed that idealized influence significantly influenced job satisfaction of the employees ($R^2 = .246, F(1, 97.750) = 112.421, p < .05$). Similarly, multiple linear regression results showed that inspirational motivation significantly influenced job satisfaction of the employees ($R^2 = .344, F(1, 126.302) = 180.980, p < .05$). Job security was found to significantly moderate the relationships between idealized influence, inspirational motivation and job satisfaction ($R^2 = .431, F(3, 44.688) = 86.330, p < .05$).

Change, Linge and Sikalieh (2019) investigated the influence of idealized influence on employee engagement in parastatals in the energy sector in Kenya. Also, the study sought to determine the moderating influence of employee motivation on the relationship between idealized influence and employee engagement. This study targeted the 10 parastatals within the energy sector in Kenya with a population of 315 middle-level managers. The study adopted a positivist research philosophy to examine how idealized influence influences employee engagement and data were collected using structured questionnaires. A correlational research design was conducted with the purpose of determining the strength of the relationship between parameters of idealized influence and employee engagement in parastatals in the energy sector in Kenya. The findings showed that employee engagement has a statistical significant relationship with charisma, $r(166) = 0.590, p < 0.01$; ethical leadership, $r(165) = 0.553, p < 0.01$; teamwork, $r(166) = 0.531, p < 0.01$. Multiple linear regression analysis revealed that employee motivation positively and significantly moderates the relationship between idealized influence and employee engagement, $R^2 = 0.405, F(2, 159) = 54.100, p < 0.05, \eta^2 = 0.225, p < 0.05$.

Langat, Linge and Sikalieh (2019) conducted a research to examine the influence of idealized influence on employee job performance in the insurance industry in Kenya. This study adopted the positivism research philosophy and correlation research design. The target population of the study was 676 lower-level managers from 52 insurance companies operating in Kenya as of 2017. A sample size of 245 was drawn using a stratified random sampling technique and systematic sampling. 245 questionnaires were distributed out of which 211 were completed and returned representing a response rate of 86% which was deemed as adequate for a correlation research design. The analysis of variance was used to test the hypothesis. Results showed that idealized influence significantly predicted employee job performance. In addition, the study inferred that employee work value congruence had a significant moderating effect on the relationship between transformational leadership and employee job performance among lower-level managers in the Insurance sector in Kenya.

Hunegnaw and Shavina (2019) conducted a research to analyze the relationship between transformational leadership and employee job performance in the public sector of Amhara National Regional State Bureaus. Correlational and descriptive survey designs were applied. Quantitative data was collected from 373 sample respondents through the application of stratified and simple random sampling techniques but out of these, five questionnaires were not valid and the analysis was made for 368 respondents. Reliability and validity of the measurements were checked through the use of factor analysis and pilot test. Pearson correlation and linear regression analysis were applied. The researcher found that transformational leadership and its dimensions (idealized influence, inspirational motivation, intellectual stimulation and individualized consideration) have positive and significant correlation with employee performance. On the other hand, from the uni- and multi-dimensional regression analysis, it was found that transformational leadership and two of its dimensions (and inspirational motivation and individualized consideration) were significant predictor of job performance respectively while the remaining two dimensions of transformational leadership (idealized influence and intellectual stimulation) were not significant.

Otienoa, Teresia, and Damary (2019), studied the influence of idealized influence on employee engagement in parastatals in the energy sector in Kenya. The objective of the study was to investigate the influence of idealized influence on employee engagement in parastatals in the energy sector in Kenya. A correlational research design was conducted with the purpose of determining the strength of the relationship between parameters of idealized influence and employee engagement in parastatals in the energy sector in Kenya. The findings showed that employee engagement has a statistical significant relationship with charisma, ethical leadership, and teamwork. Multiple linear regression analysis revealed that employee motivation positively and significantly moderates the relationship between idealized influence and employee engagement.

Escortell, Baquero, Delgado and Wright (2020) investigated the relationship between leadership and job satisfaction, as well as any differences between internal employees and outsourced workers. A novel method was adopted using fuzzy-set qualitative comparative analysis (fsQCA). A questionnaire-based survey was conducted to collect responses from 60 members of staff at four- and five-star hotels in Spain. Across the sample, a high level of leadership in three of the four dimensions of transformational leadership was observed to be sufficient to increase job satisfaction. The three optimal combinations of dimensions are: individualized consideration, intellectual stimulation, and idealized influence; individualized consideration, inspirational motivation, and idealized influence; and intellectual stimulation, inspirational motivation, and idealized influence. The findings suggest that there are differences between outsourced workers and internal employees. Outsourced workers need all four dimensions to achieve high job satisfaction, whereas internal employees can achieve high job satisfaction without individualized consideration.

MbitheMusyoki, Okoth, Kalai and Okumbe (2021) investigated the influence of principals' transformational leadership practices on student academic performance in Kenya Certificate Secondary Examination (K.C.S.E) in Makueni County, Kenya. The objective that guided the study was to: determine the influence of principals' idealized influence on student performance at KCSE in Makueni. The hypothesis was: there is no relationship between principals' idealized influence,

and inspirational motivation with students' mean scores at Kenya Certificate of Secondary Education Makueni County. The sample comprised of 111 principals, 729 teachers and 12 Ministry of Education officials. Questionnaires and interview guide were used to collect data. Reliability was computed using Cronbach's alpha method. The coefficient value was 0.85 at $\alpha = 0.05$. H01 indicate a negative and strong significant coefficient between the indicators of principals idealize and students means score at K.C.S.E which included ($r = -.213$, $p\text{-value} < 0.05$); ($r = 267$, $p\text{-value} < 0.01$) respectively. The null hypothesis there is no significant relationship between Idealized influence and students' mean score at Kenya Certificate of Secondary Education would be accepted if $p < 0.05$. The null hypothesis was rejected.

Afshari (2022) investigated the relationships between the idealized influence component of transformational leadership (TL) and employee organizational commitment in two different cultural contexts. Data were collected from the members of two manufacturing organizations, one in Australia and one in Iran. Questionnaires were distributed to all levels of the two organizations. In total, 189 completed questionnaires were returned from the two countries, representing a response rate of 56.7%. Structural equation modeling (SEM) was employed to test the hypotheses. The results demonstrated statistically significant relationships between two forms of idealized influence – attributed and behavior – and the employees' organizational commitment in the Iranian sample. However, in the Australian sample, only idealized influence behavior showed a significant impact on employee commitment. Furthermore, the findings showed that identified motivation mediates the relationship between idealized influence behavior and organizational commitment.

ALmahasneh, Rahman, Omar and Zulkifli (2022) conducted a study that applied transformational leadership and perspective theory to ascertain the impacts of idealized influence and inspirational motivation on organizational culture. Data were gathered from information technology firm managers in Jordan, utilizing a quantitative approach – there were three levels of managers involved. Structural equation modeling with partial least squares (PLS-SEM) was used for data analysis. The results show positive impacts of idealized influence and inspirational motivation on organizational culture. The positive impact of idealized influence and inspirational motivation on organizational performance implies that organizational culture mediates the relation between

idealized influence, inspirational motivation, and organizational performance. Several interesting findings were highlighted for the Information Technology sector in Jordan. Relevant companies worldwide could peruse the findings of this study to improve their organizational culture and performance. The current study adds to the epistemology new framework covering the transformational leadership theory perception to address the factors that influence organizational performance, including the transformational leadership styles to achieve superior performance through the activation of organizational culture.

Budur and Demir (2022) investigated the relationship of transformational leadership with employee performance and citizenship behaviors. Further, it examined the correlation between the sub-dimensions of transformational leadership (TL) and organizational citizenship behaviors (OCB). To achieve this, 399 participants were selected through convenience sampling method, and data was collected from them using a survey questionnaire. According to the findings, inspirational motivation had significant and positive effects on employee performance (EP). Furthermore, OCB affected EP partially, while courtesy and conscientiousness had significant positive impacts on EP. Concerning the relationship between TL and OCB, individual consideration was found to have significant and positive effects on courtesy and civic virtue, but not on sportsmanship and conscientiousness, while idealized influence was not found to have any significant relationship with OCB dimensions. Finally, in terms of the OCB's mediation, individual consideration was shown to have an indirect effect on EP via conscientiousness.

2.3.3 Effective communication on Individualized consideration

Adeoye and Torubelli (2011) conducted a study to explain the interactive and relative effects of emotional intelligence and human relationship management on the organizational commitment of Nigerian civil servants. A simple random sampling technique was used in selecting 300 participants from the Ministries of Education, Local government affairs, Civil service commission, Agriculture and Governors office of Bayelsa and Oyo States. Of the sample selected, 160 were males and 140 were females. Their ages range between 28 and 55 years with a mean age of 36.7 and a standard deviation of 6.9. Three instruments: Emotional intelligence scales (EIS), Human relationship management scale (HRMS) and Organizational commitment questionnaire (OCQ)

were used to collect data from the participants. Data analysis involved the use of Pearson Product Moment Correlation and multiple regressions. The results indicated that the two independent variables, when taken together, were effective in predicting organizational commitment. Each of the variables contributed significantly to the prediction of organizational commitment with emotional intelligence making a higher contribution to the prediction of Organizational commitment. Based on the outcome of the study, Emotional intelligence intervention and Human relationship management programs were advocated in order to enhance the organizational commitment of civil servants.

Rana and Ajmal (2012) researched the Transformational Leadership Style as Predictor of Decision Making Styles: Moderating Role of Emotional Intelligence in Pakistan. Regression analysis is utilized to study the relationship between transformational leadership style and decision-making styles and step-wise regression analysis is used to study moderating effect of emotional intelligence. The study found that transformational leadership style strongly predicts rational and dependent decision-making styles and weakly predicts intuitive and spontaneous decision-making styles while no association was found with avoidant decision-making styles. The research also found that emotional intelligence moderates the relationship between transformational leadership styles and decision-making styles.

Sobhi-Gharamaleki (2012) conducted a research to understand the relationship of emotional intelligence and its dimensions (self-awareness, self-management, social awareness and relationship management) to achievement motivation. The statistical population included all female first grade high school students studying in Karaj city. A sample of 60 students was selected by multi-stage random cluster sampling procedure. All participants completed the Achievement Motivation-Denver Youth Survey and Bradberry-Greaves Emotional Intelligence test. Results showed a significant positive relationship between achievement motivation and emotional intelligence. Global emotional intelligence as well as its components, self-awareness, self-management and relationship management correlated positively with achievement motivation. But social awareness was not found to be associated with achievement motivation. The results showed that adolescents with high emotional intelligence hold more realistic perceptions in interpersonal

relationships and this ability probably helps them develop achievement motivation. Higher achievement motivation may help enhance feelings of self-efficacy as well as academic motivation.

Shahram (2014) researched the Relationship between Emotional Intelligence and Transformational Leadership in Sports Managers in Iran. The method of the study was a correlation. The data were analyzed using both descriptive and inferential statistics including mean, standard deviation, minimum and maximum scores, Pearson correlation formula, independent t-test, and multiple regression analysis. The results revealed significant positive correlations, both simple and multiple, between emotional intelligence and transformational leadership style in the sports managers in Alborz province.

Yunus and Aduros (2015) researched on the impact of transformational leadership style which consists of four dimensions (4I's), namely, Idealized Influence (II), Inspirational Motivation (IM), Intellectual Stimulation (IS), and Individual Consideration (IC) toward the job performance among employees. It also determines the moderating effect of trust of employees to their leaders or managers with the relationship between two constructs, as well as trust in transformational leadership style and employees job performance. A set of 220 questionnaires were distributed to employees at several food manufacturing companies in Shah Alam which are Silver Bird Group Berhad (High 5) and Gardenia Bakeries Sdn. Bhd. There are other types of leadership styles however for this study Transformational Leadership styles were used. The findings were analyzed using descriptive and statistical statistics. The result of the study indicated that there was a positive and significant relationship between transformational leadership styles and employee's job performance.

Juma and Ndisya (2016) investigated the Influence of Transformational Leadership on Employee Performance using a case study of Safaricom Limited. The influence of intellectual stimulation on employee performance was examined using five measures namely: Employee's opportunity to work in a way they think best; consent to determine their own pace for change; consent to make a judgment in unraveling a problem; employee's receipt of assistance to reconsider ideas that had never been looked into; and employees' challenge to deliberate on old problems in new ways.

Sahibzada, Kakakhel and Khan (2016) examined the impact of idealized influence and inspirational motivation of leaders on employees' job satisfaction. Data was collected through a well-established questionnaire from 330 employees of 10 different private sector universities located in KPK. The results using descriptive statistics confirmed a non-zero relationship of the two dimensions of leadership with employees' job satisfaction. Idealized Influence showed significant association with employee's job satisfaction. The study brought out important findings to bring about behavioral improvements in leadership style of education sector that will eventually enhance levels of Job Satisfaction of employees.

Liberty and Kida (2017) examined the effect of emotional intelligence on employees' performance with the aim of understanding the influence of emotional intelligence of employees on their performance in the organization. The variables studied were emotional intelligence on organizational employee performance. Six organizations from mixed industries in operation in Maiduguri Borno State were studied. Questionnaires were administered on the 121 samples which were determined purposely. A Chi-Square (X^2) was used to test the hypotheses formulated. It was found that the use of emotional intelligence was a more potent drive to any accomplishment than monetary rewards.

Ogola, Sikalieh and Linge (2017) investigated the influence of Idealized Influence leadership behavior on employee performance in Small and Medium Enterprise in Kenya. This study targeted the KPMG top 100 SMEs of 2014 in Kenya. A correlational research design was employed to establish the relationship between Idealized Influence leadership behavior and employee performance in Small and Medium Enterprises in Kenya. The study found that Idealized Influence leadership behavior and Employee Performance in SMEs in Kenya had a strong positive and significant correlation $r(194) = .829, p < .000$ and a positive and significant relationship ($\beta = .829, t(194) = 20.503, p < .000$). Results show that if a leader inculcates trust in employees, practices high ethical values, acts as a role model to the employees and encourages employees to take risks; these will positively affect employees work and hence high-performance levels.

Nyokabi, K'Aol and Njenga (2017) conducted a study to determine the effect of idealized influence and inspirational motivation of the Chief Executive Officer (CEO) on the performance

of senior managers in the private sector in Kenya. The study adopted the positivism research philosophy and descriptive correlational research design. The target population consisted of 984 senior managers reporting to the CEOs of 183 private sector companies under the umbrella of the Kenya Private Sector Alliance (KEPSA). A sample size of 284 was drawn using stratified random sampling, and data was collected using structured questionnaires. A response rate of 92% was realized. Data was analyzed using descriptive statistics namely frequencies, means, and standard deviation. Inferential statistics were also used in the analysis which included Pearson's correlation, Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) and multiple linear regression. Results of the multiple linear regression showed that the CEO's idealized influence significantly predicted the performance of senior managers $R^2 = .505$, $F(1, 260) = 264.042$, $p < .05$; $\beta = .711$, $t(260) = 16.249$, $p < .05$. Testing the influence of goal orientation as a moderating variable showed that goal orientation significantly predicted the relationship between idealized influence and inspirational motivation of the CEO and performance of senior managers $R^2 = .839$, $F(2, 5) = 265.099$, $p < .05$, $\beta = .111$, $t = 3.900$, $p < .05$.

Njiraini, K'Aol and Linge (2018) determined the extent to which idealized influence and inspirational motivation influence job satisfaction among employees in commercial banks in Kenya. The study adopted a positivist research philosophy and a descriptive correlation research design. The target population consisted of 10,310 managerial employees in commercial banks in Kenya. A sample of 424 employees was obtained from the population using a stratified random sampling technique. Data were collected using structured questionnaires. A response rate of 82% was obtained. Data was analyzed using descriptive statistics and inferential statistics. Inferential statistical methods used to analyze the data were Chi-square, Pearson's correlation, ANOVA, and multiple linear regressions. The Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) tool version 22 was used to analyze the data. Correlation analysis found that idealized influence, inspirational motivation and job security were positively and significantly correlated to job satisfaction $r(346) = .496$, $p < .05$, $r(347) = .587$, $p < .05$, $r(347) = .697$, $p < .05$ respectively. Multiple linear regression results showed that idealized influence significantly influenced job satisfaction of the employees ($R^2 = .246$, $F(1, 97.750) = 112.421$, $p < .05$). Similarly, multiple linear regression results showed that inspirational motivation significantly influenced job satisfaction of the employees ($R^2 = .344$,

$F(1, 126.302) = 180.980, p < .05$). Job security was found to significantly moderate the relationships between idealized influence, inspirational motivation and job satisfaction ($R^2 = .431, F(3, 44.688) = 86.330, p < .05$).

Change, Linge and Sikalieh (2019) investigated the influence of idealized influence on employee engagement in parastatals in the energy sector in Kenya. Also, the study sought to determine the moderating influence of employee motivation on the relationship between idealized influence and employee engagement. This study targeted the 10 parastatals within the energy sector in Kenya with a population of 315 middle-level managers. The study adopted a positivist research philosophy to examine how idealized influence influences employee engagement and data were collected using structured questionnaires. A correlational research design was conducted with the purpose of determining the strength of the relationship between parameters of idealized influence and employee engagement in parastatals in the energy sector in Kenya. The findings showed that employee engagement has a statistical significant relationship with charisma, $r(166) = 0.590, p < 0.01$; ethical leadership, $r(165) = 0.553, p < 0.01$; teamwork, $r(166) = 0.531, p < 0.01$. Multiple linear regression analysis revealed that employee motivation positively and significantly moderates the relationship between idealized influence and employee engagement, $R^2 = 0.405, F(2, 159) = 54.100, p < 0.05, \eta^2 = 0.225, p < 0.05$.

Langat, Linge and Sikalieh (2019) conducted a research to examine the influence of idealized influence on employee job performance in the insurance industry in Kenya. This study adopted the positivism research philosophy and correlation research design. The target population of the study was 676 lower-level managers from 52 insurance companies operating in Kenya as of 2017. A sample size of 245 was drawn using a stratified random sampling technique and systematic sampling. 245 questionnaires were distributed out of which 211 were completed and returned representing a response rate of 86% which was deemed as adequate for a correlation research design. The analysis of variance was used to test the hypothesis. Results showed that idealized influence significantly predicted employee job performance. In addition, the study inferred that employee work value congruence had a significant moderating effect on the relationship between

transformational leadership and employee job performance among lower-level managers in the Insurance sector in Kenya.

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Otienoa, Teresia, and Damary (2019), studied the influence of idealized influence on employee engagement in parastatals in the energy sector in Kenya. The objective of the study was to investigate the influence of idealized influence on employee engagement in parastatals in the energy sector in Kenya. A correlational research design was conducted with the purpose of determining the strength of the relationship between parameters of idealized influence and employee engagement in parastatals in the energy sector in Kenya. The findings showed that employee engagement has a statistical significant relationship with charisma, ethical leadership, and teamwork. Multiple linear regression analysis revealed that employee motivation positively and significantly moderates the relationship between idealized influence and employee engagement.

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Afshari (2022) investigated the relationships between the idealized influence component of transformational leadership (TL) and employee organizational commitment in two different cultural contexts. Data were collected from the members of two manufacturing organizations, one in Australia and one in Iran. Questionnaires were distributed to all levels of the two organizations. In total, 189 completed questionnaires were returned from the two countries, representing a response rate of 56.7%. Structural equation modeling (SEM) was employed to test the hypotheses. The results demonstrated statistically significant relationships between two forms of idealized influence –attributed and behavior – and the employees' organizational commitment in the Iranian sample. However, in the Australian sample, only idealized influence behavior showed a significant impact on employee commitment. Furthermore, the findings showed that identified motivation mediates the relationship between idealized influence behavior and organizational commitment.

ALmahasneh, Rahman, Omar and Zulkifflli (2022) conducted a study that applied transformational leadership and perspective theory to ascertain the impacts of idealized influence and inspirational motivation on organizational culture. Data were gathered from information technology firm managers in Jordan, utilizing a quantitative approach – there were three levels of managers involved. Structural equation modeling with partial least squares (PLS-SEM) was used for data analysis. The results show positive impacts of idealized influence and inspirational motivation on organizational culture. The positive impact of idealized influence and inspirational motivation on organizational performance implies that organizational culture mediates the relation between idealized influence, inspirational motivation, and organizational performance. Several interesting findings were highlighted for the Information Technology sector in Jordan. Relevant companies worldwide could peruse the findings of this study to improve their organizational culture and performance. The current study adds to the epistemology new framework covering the transformational leadership theory perception to address the factors that influence organizational performance, including the transformational leadership styles to achieve superior performance through the activation of organizational culture.

Budur and Demir (2022) investigated the relationship of transformational leadership with employee performance and citizenship behaviors. Further, it examined the correlation between the

sub-dimensions of transformational leadership (TL) and organizational citizenship behaviors (OCB). To achieve this, 399 participants were selected through convenience sampling method, and data was collected from them using a survey questionnaire. According to the findings, inspirational motivation had significant and positive effects on employee performance (EP). Furthermore, OCB affected EP partially, while courtesy and conscientiousness had significant positive impacts on EP. Concerning the relationship between TL and OCB, individual consideration was found to have significant and positive effects on courtesy and civic virtue, but not on sportsmanship and conscientiousness, while idealized influence was not found to have any significant relationship with OCB dimensions. Finally, in terms of the OCB's mediation, individual consideration was shown to have an indirect effect on EP via conscientiousness.

2.3.4 Motivation on Employee Inspirational Motivation

Wan Omar and Hussin (2013) conducted a study that empirically investigated the relationships between transformational leadership style proxied by charismatic or inspirational motivation, intellectual stimulation, and individualized consideration with job satisfaction. 100 respondents from an academic institution in Malaysia had voluntarily participated in the study. The data was analyzed by means of confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) using SPSS Amos software. The revised structural equation modeling (SEM) for relationship between transformational leadership style and job satisfaction passed goodness-of-fit (GOF) tests with near perfect results for absolute and incremental fit measured (chi square to degree of freedom 1.004; p-value 0.469; RMSEA 0.006; and comparative fit index (CFI) 1.000). However, only two out of the three dimensions of leadership were having significant relationships with job satisfaction. Positive relationship existed between intellectual stimulation and job satisfaction, while individual consideration was negatively related. The result also revealed that leadership was an insignificant mediator in the relationships between inspirational motivation, intellectual stimulation and individualized consideration with job satisfaction.

Ahmad, Abbas, Latif and Rasheed (2014) conducted a study to find the effect of Transformational Leadership on Employee Motivation in Telecommunication Sector in Punjab. It is also found the relationship of dimensions of Transformational Leadership to Motivation. The study employed a

descriptive method using simple random sampling technique. For this purpose 400 questionnaires were distributed but 300 were returned back with 75% response rate because the remaining responses were not according to requirement. Descriptive analysis, correlation and regression were used to analyse data. Results showed that there is a positive and significant relationship between transformational leadership and employee motivation.

Ha and Nguyen (2014) carried out a study to analyze the influence of transformational, transactional and passive/avoidant leadership behaviors on individual job performance in the context of software companies in Vietnam. The study used a sample of 304 individuals interviewed directly by questionnaire and applied the method of testing difference, EFA, multiple regression for data processing. The results showed that passive/avoidant leadership behavior is the most important factor influences on individual job performance; however, this is the negative influence. Among those behaviors which are found to influence significantly and positively on individual job performance, individualized consideration is the most important; it's then followed by idealized influence, intellectual stimulation, management by exception – active and contingent reward. However, inspirational motivation is found not to be significantly influenced on individual job performance.

Long, Yusof, Kowang and Heng (2014) conducted a study that examined the relationship between transformational leadership style and employee job satisfaction. Four transformational leadership characteristics which are idealized influence, inspiration motivation, intellectual stimulation and individualized consideration were considered. An empirical study was conducted in a Government Linked Company in Malaysia. 378 employees from 6 different departments are invited to be the respondents of this research. The number of completed surveys which were returned to the researcher was 255. This represents a return rate of 67.46%. The MLQ was used to measure transformational leadership style while MSQ was used for job satisfaction. Pearson's correlation was used to analyse the data. The findings showed that inspirational motivation was found to have no significant relationship with job satisfaction.

Naile and Selesho (2014) established the role of leadership style in motivating the teaching staff to be committed to their work. From 13 high schools in a province in South Africa, 184 teaching

staff were selected to participate. It should be noted that these ‘high schools were not performing above the provincial benchmark. In order to obtain a holistic view of the overall leadership style present in the school system, a Multifactor Leadership Questionnaire (MLQ) was used. The researchers administered the questionnaires with the assistance of schools’ administrative clerks and the completed questionnaires were collected by the research support group. Data were analysed by descriptive statistics, such as percentages, frequency and the Cronbach-alpha coefficient to test among other things, the reliability of describing the impact and the leadership style in these schools. The study reveals that there strong relationship between transformational leadership behaviours and commitment (affective commitment; continuance commitment; and normative commitment).

Shahzadi, Javed, Pirzada, Nasreen and Khanam (2014) analysed the impact of employee motivation on employee performance. Data was collected from 160 teachers of Government and private schools in Pakistan by using self-administered questionnaire. Regression analysis was applied to find the effect of employee motivation on employee’s performance involving four variables employee motivation, employee performance, intrinsic rewards and employee perceived training effectiveness. The results showed that there is significant and positive relationship exists between employee motivation and employee performance.

Aljaf and Sadq (2015) examined the impact of employee motivation in order to improve the organisational performance in Hayat University in Kurdistan Region/Iraq. In this study a survey questionnaires are distributed to a sample of teaching staff members who were teaching in various scientific departments in Hayat University for Science and Technology. The data collected from the questionnaires analysed quantitatively using SPSS program. The findings show that motivation plays a significant role in affecting academic staff’s performance and ultimately organizational performance in Hayat University.

Sahibzada, Kakakhel and Khan (2016) examined the impact of idealized influence and inspirational motivation of leaders on employees’ job satisfaction. Data was collected through a well-established questionnaire from 330 employees of 10 different private sector universities located in KPK, Pakistan. The results confirmed a non-zero relationship of the two dimensions of

leadership with employees' job satisfaction. Inspirational motivation showed significant association with employee's job satisfaction. The study brought out important findings to bring about behavioral improvements in leadership style of education sector that will eventually enhance levels of Job Satisfaction of employees.

Ngaithe, K'Aol, Lewa and Ndwiga (2016) examined the influence of Idealized Influence and Inspirational Motivation on performance of staff in State Owned Enterprises in Kenya. Stratified random sampling technique was used to select a sample of 163 senior managers from the target population of 275 senior managers. A structured questionnaire was used to collect data from the selected members of top management team in SOEs. The study used factor analysis to reduce data, correlation analysis to establish the relationship between staff performance and transformational leadership, chi square test, Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) and multiple linear regression model to test the hypotheses. The study found that inspirational motivation was positively and significantly related with staff performance, $r(140) = .73$, $p < .00$ and significantly predicted staff performance, $\beta = 1.1$, $t(145) = 4.54$, $p < .00$. The study explained that Inspirational Motivation positively and significantly increased performance of staff in SOEs in Kenya.

Tetteh and Brenyah (2016) investigated the impact different styles of leadership have on employees' satisfaction with their jobs. The research was a cross-sectional study of employees in the mobile telecommunications sector of Ghana. A total of 400 usable questionnaires were obtained. The multiple regression technique was the main statistical tool employed to test the formulated hypotheses. It is identified that three dimensions of transformational leadership style - individualized consideration, inspirational motivation and intellectual stimulation have positive effect and correlation with extrinsic satisfaction. Also three dimensions of transformational leadership style - inspirational motivation, intellectual stimulation and idealized influence show positive and significant relationship with intrinsic satisfaction.

Nyokabi, K'Aol and Njenga (2017) conducted a study to determine the effect of idealized influence and inspirational motivation of the Chief Executive Officer (CEO) on the performance of senior managers in the private sector in Kenya. The study adopted the positivism research philosophy and descriptive correlational research design. The target population consisted of 984

senior managers reporting to the CEOs of 183 private sector companies under the umbrella of the Kenya Private Sector Alliance (KEPSA). A sample size of 284 was drawn using stratified random sampling, and data was collected using structured questionnaires. A response rate of 92% was realized. Data was analyzed using descriptive statistics namely frequencies, means, and standard deviation. Inferential statistics were also used in the analysis which included Pearson's correlation, Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) and multiple linear regression. Results of the multiple linear regression showed that inspirational motivation of the CEO significantly predicted the performance of senior managers, $R^2 = .564$, $F(1, 260) = 335.141$, $p < .05$, $\beta = .751$, $t(260) = 18.307$, $p < .05$. Testing the influence of goal orientation as a moderating variable showed that goal orientation significantly predicted the relationship between idealized influence and inspirational motivation of the CEO and performance of senior managers $R^2 = .839$, $F(2, 5) = 265.099$, $p < .05$, $\beta = .111$, $t = 3.900$, $p < .05$. The study provides a unique contribution to the theory and practice of transformational leadership in a new context in terms how transformational leadership behavior associated with the dimensions of idealized influence and inspirational motivation, affect performance of senior managers in private sector organizations.

Jiang, Gao and Yang (2018) used implicit voice theory to examine the influence of employees' critical thinking and leaders' inspirational motivation on employees' voice behavior via voice efficacy. The results of a pretest of 302 employees using critical thinking questionnaires and a field study of 273 dyads of supervisors and their subordinates revealed that both employees' critical thinking and leaders' inspirational motivation had a positive effect on employees' voice and that voice efficacy mediates the relationships among employees' critical thinking, leaders' inspirational motivation, and employees' voice. Implications for research and practice are discussed.

Haleem, Jehangir and Khalil-Ur-Rahman (2018) conducted a study to find out the impact of transformational leadership on employees' job satisfaction. The study was conducted in the public sectors universities of KPK, Pakistan. A sample size of 130 employees was selected using convenient sampling techniques. The data was collected from grade 16 and upper level of employees in the universities. Initially, 130 questionnaires were sent out to the target population for their participation in the survey; out of which 100 filled questionnaires were received forming

percentage of 76.92%. These 100 properly filled questionnaires were used for statistical analysis. Both descriptive and advanced multivariate statistical, correlation and regression analysis, were conducted to get a feel for the data and to test the postulated hypothesis respectively. The findings of the study revealed that there was a non-significant influence of transformational leadership in terms of idealized influence, individualized consideration, and inspirational motivation on employees' job satisfaction in the public sectors universities of KPK, Pakistan.

Anyiko-Awori, Namada and Linge (2018) carried out a study to find the effect of intellectual stimulation on the employee performance of regulatory state corporations in Kenya. A descriptive correlation design was employed to establish the relationship between inspirational motivation leadership behaviour and employee performance in regulatory state corporations in Kenya. Proportionate stratified random sampling method was used to select a sample size of 130 out of the target population of 195 senior level managers who reported directly to Chief Executive Officers. Pearson's correlation and regression techniques were used to analyse the data. The study revealed a positive and significant correlation between inspirational motivation and employ performance ($r = 0.894$, $p = 0.000$ ($p < 0.05$)). Inspirational motivation significantly predicted employ performance ($\beta = .894$, $t = 21.063$, $p < .05$).

Moodley, Hove and Karodia (2018) conducted a study that examined the factors affecting employee motivation and its impact on organizational performance at an engineering supplies company in Durban, Kwa-Zulu Natal. The data was gathered using quantitative research methods and the research instruments utilized was a questionnaire. Both extrinsic and intrinsic sources were identified as factors affecting employee motivation, and the findings also showed that employees at the organization were motivated by financial and non-financial aspects. The employees of the company were found to have low to average motivation levels, which is manifested in disciplinary issues and high labour turnover.

Rita, Payangan, Rante, Tuhumena, and Erari, (2018) carried out a study to examine the relationship between transformational leadership, organizational commitment, motivation, organizational citizenship behavior (OCB) and employee performance. The research was located in the province of Papua, and more specifically at the District Secretariat Papua Province. The study was

conducted in the months from April to June 2016. This study tested the effect of transformational leadership, organizational commitment, work motivation, OCB and performance Officer Regional Secretariat Papua Province, then the variable research is transformational leadership, organizational commitment, work motivation, OCB and performance officer. Structural equation modeling (SEM) calculation tool is commonly used is the program analysis of moment structures. The results of the studies showed that moderating OCB does not significantly affect the relationship between organizational commitment, transformational leadership, work motivation and the performance of employees at the District Secretariat in Papua Province.

Langat, Linge and Sikalieh (2019) conducted a study on the influence of inspirational motivation on employee job performance in insurance industry in Kenya. This study adopted the positivism research philosophy and correlation research design. The target population of the study was 676 lower-level managers from 52 insurance companies operating in Kenya as of 2017. A sample size of 245 was drawn using a stratified random sampling technique and systematic sampling. 245 questionnaires were distributed out of which 211 were completed and returned representing a response rate of 86% which was deemed as adequate for a correlation research design. The analysis of variance was used to test the hypothesis. The result showed that inspirational motivation significantly predicted employee job performance. In addition, it was deduced that employee work value congruence had a significant moderating effect on the relationship between transformational leadership and employee job performance among lower-level managers in the insurance sector in Kenya.

Ohunakin, Adeniji, Oludayo, Osibanjo and Oduyoye (2019) carried out a study that examined the interaction among the transformational style of leadership and job satisfaction, life satisfaction and turnover intention of employees. A total of 324 questionnaires were administered to the employees of six functioning universities' guesthouses in South-West, Nigeria. Structural Equation Modeling was used for assessing the fit of the model. Findings indicated that idealized influence, inspirational motivation, intellectual stimulation, and individualized consideration improved job satisfaction, and inversely affected turnover intention. In addition, life satisfaction was enhanced by idealized influence and individualized consideration, while inspirational motivation and

intellectual stimulation had no positive effect on life satisfaction. Life satisfaction was positively associated with job satisfaction, and negatively associated with turnover intention.

Forson, Dwamena, Opoku and Adjavon (2021) examined the relationship between job motivation factors and performance among teachers of basic schools in Ghana. The study employed a quantitative approach on a sample of 254 teachers from a population of 678 in the Effutu Municipality of Ghana, of which 159 questionnaires were duly answered and returned (representing 62.6% return rate). Using multiple regression and ANOVA, the study found compensation package, job design and environment and performance management system as significant factors in determining teacher's motivation in the municipality. Thus, these motivation factors were significant predictors on performance when regressed at a decomposed and aggregated levels. These findings supported the self-determination theory, more specifically on the explanations advanced under the controlled and autonomous motivation factors. Significant differences were also observed in teachers' performance among one of the age cohorts. The study urged the municipal directorate of education to make more room for young teacher trainees and interns who are at the formative stage of their careers to be engaged to augment the experienced staff strength.

Muthimi, Kilika and Kinyua (2021) explored the role of inspirational motivation on the academic performance of selected universities in Kenya. The study was anchored on transformational leadership theory. Positivism research philosophy was adopted where explanatory and descriptive research designs were used for guiding the collection and analysis of data. Primary data was collected from deans of schools and chairmen of departments in the selected universities using multi-stage sampling technique. Multiple regression analysis was used to test the generated hypothesis. The study established a significant positive effect of inspirational motivation on the academic performance of universities at $p < 0.05$; $t = 8.057$ and hence concluded that inspirational motivation positively affects the university academic performance of selected universities in Kenya.

Table 2.3 Summary of Empirical Review

S/N	Author (s)	Year	Area of study	Title	Methodology	Findings
1.	Anton and Jacoba	2005	South Africa	Leader emotional intelligence, transformational leadership, trust, and team commitment:	Multi-factor leadership questionnaire (MLQ),	The finding that transformational leadership and leader emotional intelligence are positively related to team commitment
2.	Ismail, Halim, Abdullah, Shminan, Muda, Samsudin, and Girardi	2009	Sarawak, Malaysia	Effect of transformational leadership characteristics and empowerment on service quality	stepwise regression analysis	There is relationship between empowerment and selected transformational leadership characteristics such as intellectual stimulation and individualized consideration is positively and significantly correlated with service quality.
3.	Hamidifar	2010	Iran	A Study of the Relationship between Leadership Styles and Employee Job Satisfaction at IAU in Tehran, Iran.	Random sampling method	Results showed that individualized consideration and laissez-faire are strong predictors of all the job satisfaction factors
4.	Adeoye and Torubelli	2011	Nigeria	Emotional intelligence and human relationship management as predictors of organizational commitment.	Pearson product moment correlation and multiple regressions.	The results indicated that the two independent variables, when taken together, were effective in predicting organizational commitment.
5.	Rana and Ajmal	2012	Pakistan.	Transformational Leadership Style as Predictor of Decision-Making Styles	Regression analysis.	The research also found that emotional intelligence moderates the relationship between transformational leadership styles and decision-making styles.

6.	Sobhi-Gharamaleki	2012	Karaj city	The prediction of achievement motivation from students' emotional intelligence.	Multi-stage random cluster sampling	Results showed a significant positive relationship between achievement motivation and emotional intelligence (self-awareness) correlated positively with achievement motivation.
7.	Fauji and Mira	2013	Indonesia	How Intellectual Stimulation Effects Knowledge Sharing Innovation and Firm Performance.	Software analysis technique PLS	The final results indicate that there are positive effects on intellectual stimulation, and explicit knowledge sharing, which has a positive effect on product innovation and product innovation has a positive effect on business performance.
8.	Ebrahimpoor and Elyasi	2013	Ardabil province	The Study of Relationship between Social Intelligence and Organizational Performance (Case Study: Ardabil Regional Water Companys Managers)	Descriptive study method using Pearson correlation test	Results indicated that social skills had the most important part in social information processing, and social awareness and social skills played a secondary role in improving performance.
9.	Wan Omar and Hussin	2013	Malaysia	Transformational leadership style and job satisfaction relationship: A study of Structural Equation Modeling (SEM).	Analysis was done by means of confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) using SPSS Amos software	Result revealed that leadership was an insignificant mediator in the relationships between inspirational motivation with job satisfaction
10.	Ahmad, Abbas, Latif and Rasheed	2014	Punjab	Impact of Transformational Leadership on Employee Motivation in Telecommunication Sector.	Correlation and regression was used for the research.	Results showed that there is a positive and significant relationship between transformational leadership and employee motivation.

11.	Ha and Nguyen	2014	Vietnam	The Influence of Leadership behaviors on Employee Performance in the Context of Software Companies in Vietnam.	The method of testing difference, EFA, multiple regression for data processing.	Inspirational motivation was found not to be significantly influenced on individual job performance
12.	Long, Yusof, Kowang and Heng	2014	Malaysia	The Impact of Transformational Leadership Style on Job Satisfaction.	Empirical study approach using MLQ and MSQ with Pearson's coefficient for analysis.	The findings showed that inspirational motivation was found to have no significant relationship with job satisfaction.
13.	Naile and Selesho	2014	South Africa	The Role of Leadership in Employee Motivation.	Multifactor Leadership Questionnaire (MLQ)	The study reveals that there strong relationship between transformational leadership behaviours and commitment.
14.	Shahzadi, Javed, Pirzada, Nasreen and Khanam	2014	Pakistan	Impact of Employee Motivation on Employee Performance.	Regression analysis	The results showed that there is significant and positive relationship exists between employee motivation and employee performance
15.	Zacher, Pearce, Rooney and McKenna	2014	Australia	Leaders' Personal Wisdom and Leader-Member Exchange Quality: The Role of Individualized Consideration	ANOVA	Results showed that leaders' personal wisdom had a positive indirect effect on follower ratings of LMX quality through individualized consideration
16.	Yasin, Nawab, Bhatti and Nazir	2014	Pakistan	Relationship of Intellectual Stimulation, Innovations and Smes Performance: Transformational Leadership a Source of Competitive Advantage in Smes.	Pearson Correlation	This study found that intellectual stimulation may be used as tool for the development of innovations and higher SMEs performance

17.	Shahram	2014	Iran.	Relationship Between Emotional Intelligence and Transformational Leadership in Sports Managers in Iran.	Pearson correlation formula and multiple regression analysis.	The results revealed significant positive correlations, both simple and multiple, between emotional intelligence and transformational leadership style in the sports managers in Alborz province.
18.	Yunus and Aduros	2015	Shah Alam	The Impact of Transformational Leadership Styles towards Employees Job Performance: The Moderating Effect of Trust	Descriptive and statistical analysis	The result of the study indicated that there was a positive and significant relationship between transformational leadership styles and employee's job performance.
19.	Anjali and Anand	2015	Karnataka	Intellectual Stimulation and Job Commitment: A Study of IT Professionals.	Parametric approach	The outcome of the study revealed that in the presence of intellectually stimulating factors, employees are more content with their jobs and their commitment to the job is stronger.
20.	Peng, Lin, Chaubroeck, McDonough, Hu and Zhang	2015	Northern Region of China	CEO Intellectual Stimulation and Employee Work Meaningfulness.	Descriptive statistics and zero-order correlations	Results showed lower firm performance or rapid and unpredictable changes in the industry are associated with a stronger positive relationship between CEO intellectual stimulation and employee work meaningfulness
21.	Subhasree and Vishvakarma	2015	India	Impact of Self-awareness on Eight States of Personality: An explorative study.	T-test	It was observed that there were some states of personality which found to be significant at 0.01 and 0.05, like anxiety, repression, fatigue and arousal.
22.	Akinlolu and Zubair	2015	Malaysia	The effects of Transformational Leadership on Job Satisfaction: A study on four and five Star	Multiple regression analysis using SPSS version 21.0	Result found that all of the Transformational leadership components like

				Hotels in Kuala Lumpur.		Individual consideration, positively and significantly influence employee job satisfaction
23.	Zatkova and Polacek	2015	Slovak Republic	Social Skills as an Important Pillar of Managerial Success	Software STATISTICA-Riggio's Social Skills Inventory (SSI)	The findings imply that social skills influence the success in the managerial position and in the career growth of the manager
24.	Aljaf and Sadq	2015	Iraq	The Impact of Employee Motivation on Organisational Performance. An Empirical Study at Hayat University-Erbil/Iraq.	Survey questionnaire method with quantitative analysis	The findings showed that motivation plays a significant role in affecting academic staff's performance and ultimately organizational performance in Hayat University
25.	Sahibzada, Kakakhel and Khan	2016	Pakistan	Role of Leaders' Idealized Influence and Inspirational Motivation on Employees' Job Satisfaction	Descriptive statistics	The results confirmed a non-zero relationship of the two dimensions of leadership with employees' job satisfaction.
26.	Ngaithe, K'Aol, Lewa and Ndwiga	2016	Kenya	Effect of Idealized Influence and Inspirational Motivation on Staff Performance in State Owned Enterprises in Kenya.	Stratified random sampling technique with correlation analysis, chi square, ANOVA and multiple linear regression model.	The study found that inspirational motivation was positively and significantly related with staff performance.
27.	Tetteh and Brenyah	2016	Ghana	Organizational Leadership Styles and their Impact in Employees' Job Satisfaction: Evidence from the Mobile Telecommunications Sector of Ghana.	Multiple regression technique was the main statistical tool	It is identified that three dimensions of transformational leadership style - individualized consideration, inspirational motivation and intellectual stimulation have positive effect and correlation with extrinsic satisfaction
28.	Alahmad	2016	US	Understanding the Relationship between Idealized Influence, Intellectual Stimulation,	Online survey using structural equation modeling	The findings indicate that each component of transformational leadership impacts

				Inspirational Motivation, Individualized Consideration and Product Innovation among Manufacturing and Services Firms: The Role of Open System.		product innovation differently
29.	Orabi	2016	Jordan	The Impact of Transformational Leadership Style on Organizational Performance: Evidence from Jordan.	Multiple linear regression	Result showed that idealized influence was not a significant factor contributing to this outcome.
30.	Ndwiga and Ngaithe	2016	Kenya	The Effect of Individualized Consideration and Intellectual Stimulation on Organizational Performance of Commercial State Owned Enterprises in Kenya.	Self-administered questionnaire and ordinary linear regression	The results showed that individualized consideration had a significant and negative effect on organization performance implying that discouraging individual consideration in a commercially owned enterprise would improve organization performance.
31.	K'Aol, Ngaithe, Lewa and Ndwiga	2016	Kenya	Effect of Intellectual Stimulation and Individualised Consideration on Staff Performance in State Owned Enterprises in Kenya.	Chi square test, ANOVA and multiple linear regression	The study found that intellectual stimulation was positively and significantly related with staff performance.
32.	Leonard, George, Peter, and Michael	2016	Kenya.	Effect of Intellectual Stimulation and Individualized Consideration on Staff Performance in State Owned Enterprises in Kenya.	Analysis of Variance (ANOVA), and a multiple linear regression model	The study found that intellectual stimulation was positively and significantly related with staff performance, and significantly predicted staff performance.

						Individualized consideration was strongly correlated with staff performance and significantly predicted staff performance
33.	Juma and Ndisya	2016	Kenya	Influence of Transformational Leadership on Employee Performance. A Case Study of Safaricom Limited. Strategic.	SPSS was used for the data analysis.	The study found a positive influence between intellectual stimulation and employee performance.
34.	Sahibzada, Kakakhel and Khan	2016	Pakistan	Role of Leaders' Idealized Influence and Inspirational Motivation on Employees' Job Satisfaction.	Descriptive statistics	The results confirmed a non-zero relationship of the two dimensions of leadership with employees' job satisfaction. Idealized Influence showed significant association with employee's job satisfaction
35.	Liberty and Kida	2017	Nigeria	Effect of emotional intelligence on employees' performance	Chi-Square (X2) was used to test the hypotheses formulated	It was found that the use of emotional intelligence was a more potent drive to any accomplishment than monetary rewards.
36.	Ogola, Sikalieh and Linge	2017	Kenya	The Influence of Idealized Influence Leadership Behavior on Employee Performance in Small and Medium Enterprises in Kenya.	Correlational research design	Results show that if a leader inculcates trust in employees, practices high ethical values, acts as a role model to the employees and encourages employees to take risks; these will positively affect employees work and

						hence high performance levels.
37.	Nyokabi, K'Aol and Njenga	2017	Kenya	Effect of Idealized Influence and Inspirational Motivation of the CEO on performance in the Private Sector in Kenya.	Descripticorrelational research design approach, using Inferential statistics for analysis	Results of the multiple linear regression showed that the CEO's idealized influence significantly predicted performance of senior managers.
38.	Mary, Damary, and Teresia	2017	Kenya.	The Influence of Intellectual Stimulation Leadership Behaviour on Employee Performance in SMEs in Kenya	Pearson's correlation, multiple regression, and chi-square techniques	Intellectual stimulation leadership behavior and Employee had a strong positive and significant correlation and a positive and significant relationship
39.	Israel, Marisa, and Susana	2017	Kenya.	Leadership Intellectual Stimulation and Team Learning: the Mediating Role of Team Positive effect.	Structural Equation Model analysis at the team level.	The findings showed strong relationship that intellectual stimulation has on team learning and team positive affect, as well as the potential of positive affect for stimulating team learning.
40.	Agyemang, Boateng and Dzandu	2017	Ghana	Examining intellectual stimulation, idealised influence and individualised consideration as an antecedent to knowledge sharing: Evidence from Ghana.	Convenience sampling technique and multiple regression	The study found that there is a significant positive relationship between idealised influence and knowledge sharing.
41.	Al-mehsin	2017	Saudi Arabia	Self-Efficacy and Its Relationship with Social Skills and the Quality of Decision-Making among the Students of Prince Sattam Bin Abdul-Aziz University.	Questionnaire method	The study results indicated that the self-efficacy of the study sample was moderate and that the relationship between self-efficiency and social skills and the quality of decision-making was a positive.

42.	Ogola, Sikalieh and Linge	2017	Kenya	The Influence of Idealized Influence Leadership Behavior on Employee Performance in Small and Medium Enterprises in Kenya.	Stratified proportionate random sampling techniques with Pearson's correlation, multiple regression and chi-square techniques.	The results showed that Individualized Consideration leadership behaviour and Employee Performance in SMEs in Kenya had a strong positive and significant and a positive and significant relationship
43.	Khalil and Sahibzadah	2017	Pakistan	Leaders' Individualized Consideration and Employees' Job Satisfaction.	Quantitative approach using convenience sampling method with mean scores, frequency distributions, Pearson's correlations and linear regression for analysis.	The results indicated a strong positive correlation between Individualized Consideration and Employees' Job Satisfaction.
44.	Kimeto, K'Aol and Njenga	2017	Kenya	Transformational Leadership Style and its influence on Organizational Commitment in Commercial Banks in Kenya.	Descriptive correlational design using stratified random sampling technique. Inferential statistics for analysis.	Results of the regression indicated that individualized consideration significantly predicted organizational commitment.
45.	Nyokabi, K'Aol and Njenga	2017	Kenya	Effect of Idealized Influence and Inspirational Motivation of the CEO on performance in the Private Sector in Kenya.	Positivism research philosophy and descriptive correlational research design alongside descriptive statistics was used for the study.	Results of the multiple linear regression showed that inspirational motivation of the CEO significantly predicted the performance of senior managers
46.	Jiang, Gao and Yang	2018	China	Employees' critical thinking, leaders' inspirational motivation, and voice behavior: The mediating role of voice efficacy.	Field study approach applying pretest using critical thinking questionnaire and confirmatory factor analysis.	Result revealed that both employees' critical thinking and leaders' inspirational motivation had a positive effect on employees' voice.
47.	Haleem, Jehangir and Khalil-Ur-Rahman	2018	Pakistan	Job Satisfaction from leadership perspective.	Convenient sampling techniques with descriptive and advance multivariate statistical, correlation	Result revealed that there was non-significant influence of transformational leadership in terms of idealized

					and regression analysis were used.	influence, individualized consideration, and inspirational motivation on employees' job satisfaction
48.	Anyiko-Awori, Namada and Linge	2018	Kenya	Effect of Inspirational Motivation on Employee Performance in Regulatory State Corporations in Kenya.	Descriptive correlation design, Proportionate stratified random sampling method and Pearson's correlation and regression techniques	The study revealed a positive and significant correlation between inspirational motivation and employee performance.
49.	Moodley, Hove and Karodia	2018	Kwa-Zulu Natal	The Factors affecting Employee Motivation and its impact on organizational performance at an Engineering Supplies company in Durban, Kwa-Zulu Natal.	Quantitative research method	and the findings also showed that employees at the organization were motivated by financial and non-financial aspects.
50.	Rita, Payangan, Rante, Tuhumena, and Erari	2018	Papua	Moderating effect of organizational citizenship behavior on the effect of organizational commitment, transformational leadership and work motivation on employee performance	Structural equation modeling (SEM) calculation tool was used.	The results of the studies showed that moderating OCB does not significantly affect the relationship between organizational commitment, transformational leadership, work motivation and the performance of employees
51.	Njiinu, K'Aol and Linge	2018	Kenya	Effect of Individualized Consideration and Intellectual Stimulation on Job Satisfaction among Employees in Commercial Banks in Kenya.	Descriptive research design was used with stratified random sampling technique and correlation analysis and multiple linear regression.	Correlation analysis found that individualized consideration, intellectual stimulation and job security were positively and significantly correlated to job satisfaction
52.	Kimeto and K'Aol	2018	Kenya	Transformational Leadership Style and its influence on Organizational	The positivist research philosophy and descriptive correlational design was used for the	Results indicated that all the four independent variables (idealized

				Commitment in Commercial Banks in Kenya.	study with stratified random sampling technique and inferential statistics for analysis.	influence, inspirational motivation, intellectual stimulation, and individualized consideration) significantly predicted organizational commitment.
53.	Njiinu	2018	Kenya	Influence of Transformational Leadership Style on Job Satisfaction among Employees in Commercial Banks in Kenya.	Sampling was done using stratified random sampling technique and inferential and descriptive statistics for analysis.	there is no significant influence of individualized consideration on job satisfaction
54.	Sancher-Cardona, Salanova and Llorens-Gumbau	2018	Spain	Leadership intellectual stimulation and team learning: The mediating role of team positive affect.	Structural Equation Model analysis	Results provide evidence of the strong relationship that intellectual stimulation has on team learning and team positive affect, as well as the potential of positive affect for stimulating team learning.
55.	Njiraini, K'Aol and Linge	2018	Kenya	Effect of Idealized Influence and Inspirational Motivation on Job Satisfaction among employees in commercial banks in Kenya.	Stratified random sampling technique for descriptive and inferential statistics for statistical analysis.	Result show that idealized influence significantly influences job satisfaction of employee.
56.	Change, Linge and Sikalieh	2019	Kenya	Influence of idealized influence on employee engagement in parastatals in the energy sector in Kenya.	Positivist research philosophy approach and correlational research design.	Results revealed that employee motivation positively and significantly moderates the relationship between idealized influence and employee engagement
57.	Langat, Linge and Sikalieh	2019	Kenya	Influence of inspirational motivation on employee job performance in the	Positivism research philosophy and correlation research design	Results showed that idealized influence significantly predicted employee job performance

				insurance industry in Kenya.		
58.	Hunegnaw and Shavina	2019	Ethiopia	The relationship between transformational leadership and job performance in Amhara national regional state bureaus, Ethiopia.	Correlational and descriptive survey designs were applied with Pearson correlation and linear regression analysis.	Result showed that transformational leadership and its dimensions (idealized influence, inspirational motivation, intellectual stimulation and individualized consideration) have positive and significant correlation with employee performance.
59.	Otienoa, Teresia, and Damary	2019	Kenya.	Influence of idealized influence on employee engagement in parastatals in the energy sector in Kenya.	A correlational research design; Multiple linear regression analysis	Employee engagement has a statistical significant relationship with charisma, ethical leadership, and teamwork. Multiple linear regression analysis revealed that employee motivation positively and significantly moderates the relationship between idealized influence
60.	Chebon, Aruasa and Chirchir	2019	Kenya	Influence of Individualized Consideration and Intellectual Stimulation on Employee Performance: Lessons from Moi Teaching and Referral Hospital, Eldoret, Kenya.	Stratified random sampling, simple random sampling methods.	On the influence of individualized consideration on employee performance, the study found out that there is recognition of employees to better productivity, teaching and coaching of staff.
61.	Chebon, Aruasa and Chirchir	2019	Kenya	Influence of Individualized Consideration and Intellectual Stimulation on Employee Performance: Lessons from Moi	Descriptive correlational design was used for the study with stratified and simple random sampling technique and inferential statistics for analysis.	Supervisors respect and celebrate individual contribution and provide opportunities for identification of needs and

				Teaching and Referral Hospital, Eldoret, Kenya		capabilities of others.
62.	Rahman,S., Ferdausy,S.,& Uddin	2019	U. K	Purpose of identifying the relationships between emotional intelligence and the components of transformational leadership behavior of the supervisors.	Structured questionnaire	Results indicated that emotional intelligence positively correlated with all the components of transformational leadership behaviour.
63.	Langat, Linge and Sikalieh	2019	Kenya	Influence of inspirational motivation on employee job performance in the insurance industry in Kenya.	Positivism research philosophy and correlation research design using a stratified random sampling technique and systematic sampling alongside correlation research design were used.	The result showed that inspirational motivation significantly predicted employee job performance.
64.	Ohunakin, Adeniji, Oludayo, Osibanjo and Oduyoye	2019	Nigeria	Employees' retention in Nigeria's hospitality industry: The role of transformational leadership style and job satisfaction.	Structural Equation Modeling was used.	Findings indicated that idealized influence, inspirational motivation, intellectual stimulation, and individualized consideration improved job satisfaction, and inversely affected turnover intention.
65.	Cahyono, Novitasari, Sihotang, Aman, Fahlevi, Nadeak, Siahaan, Asbari and Purwanto	2020	Tanherang	The Effect of Transformational Leadership Dimensions on Job Satisfaction and Organizational Commitment: Case Studies in Private University Lecturers.	Simple random sampling technique with SEM method with SmartPLS 3.0 software.	first, the dimensions of transformational leadership: idealized effect, intellectual stimulation and individualized consideration have a positive and significant effect on job satisfaction.
66.	Cheruse, Ngeno and Kaptingei	2020	Kenya	Relationship between the Head Teacher's Individualized Consideration and Learners Academic Performance in Primary Schools in	Convergent parallel mixed methods design with Simple random and stratified sampling alongside descriptive and inferential statistics	The study suggested that head teacher's individual consideration does not have a statistically significant relationship with learners' academic

				Kericho County, Kenya.		performance in primary schools
67.	Khan, Khan, Rehan and Khan	2020	Pakistan	Impacts of Intellectual Stimulation on Employees' Innovative Behaviors: The Mediating Role of Contingent Rewards.	Survey and questionnaire approach, correlation procedure and hierarchical regression.	There is significant association among research variables meaning that both intellectual stimulation and contingent rewards are vital for improving the employees' innovative behavior.
68.	Sahota, Goeres, Kelly, Tang, Hofmeister and Alberti	2020	Canada and UK	Intellectual stimulation in family medicine: an international qualitative study of student perceptions.	Qualitative approach and thematic analysis	Intellectual stimulation was related to problem solving and the challenge of having to know a little about everything, along with clinical uncertainty and the need to be vigilant to avoid missing diagnoses.
69.	Sulistiawana, Ekowati and Putri	2020	Surabaya	Regulatory Focus and Employee Creativity: The Role of Individual Participation and Intellectual Stimulation.	Hierarchical and moderated regression analysis	The results of this study showed that promotion focus is positively related to creativity, whilst prevention focus is negatively related to creativity
70.	Thuan	2020	Vietnam	Motivating follower creativity by offering intellectual stimulation.	Structural equation modeling	This study found a positive direct relationship between leader intellectual stimulation and follower creative performance.
71.	Escortell, Baquero, Delgado and Wright	2020	Spain	The impact of transformational leadership on the job satisfaction of internal employees and outsourced workers.	Fuzzy-set qualitative comparative analysis	Outsourced workers need all four dimensions to achieve high job satisfaction, whereas internal employees can achieve high job satisfaction without individualized consideration.
72.	Chella, Pipitone, Morrin, & Racy	2020	Nigeria	Inner speech is a common one. Such a dialogue	Descriptive	Existing models of inner speech inspire computational tools

				accompanies the introspection of mental life and fulfills essential roles in human behavior, such as self-restructuring, self-regulation, and re-focusing on attentional resources.		to provide a robot with this form of self-awareness.
73.	Garden, Jones, Passmore	2021	Nigeria	Self-awareness is often seen as a critical component in leadership and career success, and has therefore become a feature in MBAs, leadership development, and management education.	Descriptive Survey	The contribution of our article is the provision of clarity on the construct of self-awareness and a working definition, which can be used in the fields of leadership and management development by practitioners in education and organizations, and for future research within the context of adult development and the workplace.
74.	Nyakomitta	2021	Kenya	Influence of Transformational Leadership on the performance of Commercial Banks in Kenya.	Stratified random sampling with descriptive and inferential analyses was used.	The study findings revealed that individual consideration and performance of commercial banks are positively and significantly related
75.	Forson, Dwamena, Opoku and Adjavon	2021	Ghana	Employee motivation and job performance: a study of basic school teachers in Ghana.	Quantitative approach using multiple regression and ANOVA.	Result found that motivation factors were significant predictors on performance when regressed at a decomposed and aggregated levels.
76.	Muthimi, Kilika and Kinyua	2021	Kenya	Exploring the role of inspirational motivation to institutions of higher learning: Empirical	Positivism research philosophy and descriptive research designs using multi-stage sampling	The study established a significant positive effect of inspirational

				evidence from selected universities in Kenya	technique. Multiple regression analysis were used.	motivation on academic performance of universities
77.	MbitheMusyoki, Okoth, Kalai and Okumbe	2021	Kenya	Influence of Principals' Idealized Influence on Students' Performance at Kenya Certificate of Secondary Education in Public Secondary Schools, Kenya.	Questionnaires and interview guide.	there is no significant relationship between Idealized influence and students' mean score at Kenya Certificate of Secondary Education
78.	Khan, Amin and Saif	2022	Pakistan	Individualized Consideration and Idealized influence of transformational Leadership: Mediating Role of Inspirational Motivation and Intellectual stimulation.	Cross-sectional approach	The results showed that the individualized consideration, inspirational motivation and intellectual stimulation are significantly associated with the dependent variable of idealized influence respectively.
79.	Afshari	2022	Australian and Iran	Idealized influence and commitment: a granular approach in understanding leadership.	Structural equation modeling	The results demonstrated statistically significant relationships between two forms of idealized influence –attributed and behavior – and the employees' organizational commitment in the Iranian sample
80.	ALmahasneh, Rahman, Omar and Zulkifli	2022	Jordan	The Mediating Role of Organizational Culture in the Relationship between Intellectual Stimulation, Individualized Consideration and	Quantitative approach using structural equation modeling with partial least squares	The results show positive impacts of idealized influence and inspirational motivation on organizational culture.

				Organizational Performances.		
81.	Budur and Demir	2022	Kurdistan region of Iraq	The Relationship Between Transformational Leadership and Employee Performance: Mediating effects of Organizational Citizenship Behaviors.	Convenience sampling method	Inspirational motivation had significant and positive effects on employee performance (EP).
82.	Almahasneh, Rahman, Omar and Zulkifli	2022	Jordan	The Mediating Role of Organizational Culture in the Relationship between Intellectual Stimulation, Individualized Consideration and Organizational Performances.	Partial least squares structural equation modeling (PLS-SEM) was used for analysis.	Intellectual stimulation and individualized consideration were found to impact both organizational culture and organizational performances positively.
83.	London, Sessa, & Shelley	2023	Nigeria	Self-awareness—how we see ourselves and the effects we have on our environment— influences our behavior and the type of person we want to become.	Descriptive Survey	We present the results of a literature search of educational interventions aimed at increasing mindfulness through reflection, feedback, and coaching.

Source: Author’s Compilation, 2023.

2.4 Gap in Empirical Review

The studies were carried outside effect of emotional intelligence on transformational leadership in pharmaceutical manufacturing firms in South East, Nigeria and did not focus to best of my knowledge on the self-awareness and intellectual stimulation of employees; management and idealized influence; social skill and employee’s Individual consideration; motivation and employee inspirational motivation in South East, Nigeria. Most of the studies reviewed analysed their data through A purposeful sampling technique, Descriptive statistics and appropriate inferential statistics, Purposive Sampling technique, Pearson Moment Correlation Coefficient, Multiple sampling technique, Partial Least Square Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM), Multiple Regression Analysis (MRA) method, Simple linear regression and Pearson correlation

coefficient (r) while the present study made use of Z test to test the hypotheses. Therefore, the study aimed at filling this research gap by evaluating the emotional intelligence on transformational leadership in South East, Nigeria.

CHAPTER THREE

METHODOLOGY

3.1 Research Design

A research design is the framework or plan for the study which is used as a guide in collecting and analyzing the data. The survey research method was adopted for the study. Tull and Album (1975) define survey research as the systematic gathering of information from respondents for the purpose of understanding and/or predicting some aspects of the behaviour of the population of interest. The study adopted survey research design given the fact that it involved the assessment of phenomenon without any attempt to maneuver the study variables and is characterized by the selection of random samples from population to obtain empirical knowledge of contemporary nature.

3.2 Sources of Data

Sources of data collection included primary and secondary sources.

3.2.1 Primary Sources

Primary data refer to original data collected basically for the purpose of the study. In collecting primary data for these studies two devices were adopted thus: oral interview and the use of questionnaire.

3.2.2 Secondary Sources

Secondary data were obtained from facts already documented by others which are considered valid for the study. The secondary source of data for this study includes textbooks, internet, journals, articles and unpublished works.

3.3 Area of the Study

The study was carried out in the selected pharmaceutical manufacturing firms in South-East, Nigeria. The South Eastern region is part of the six (6) geopolitical zones in Nigeria mostly dominated by the Igbo speaking states. This area is divided by the Niger River into two unequal sections – the eastern region (which is the largest) and the Midwestern region. The river, however, has not acted as a barrier to cultural unity; rather it has provided an easy means of communication in an area where many settlements claim different origins. The Igbos are also surrounded on all sides by other tribes. The Igbo language is divided into numerous regional dialects, and somewhat mutually intelligible with the larger "Igboid" cluster. The Igbo homeland straddles the lower Niger River, east and south of the Edoid and Idomoid groups, and west of the Ibiboid (Cross River)

cluster. Igbo tribe is the biggest ethnic group in southeastern and south-central Nigeria. The language of this ethnic group is consists of many dialects. During the old history of Nigeria, the people of this tribe were known as farmers, craftsmen, and traders (*Fardon, Richard, Furniss, Graham, 1994*). The region consists of the following states; Abia, Anambra, Ebonyi, Enugu, and Imo which houses the selected higher institutions in the study. Enugu spreads south wards to the borders with Abia and north wards to Kogi state. Imo spreads its boundary to Rivers, and Cross-Rivers. Anambra spreads to Delta states and Benue States. Ebonyi spreads to Cross River and Bayelsa States, while Abia also with Rivers and Cross-Rivers states (Enugu Centenary Committee, 2009). The area of the study included: Abia - Maobison Inter Link Ass., Old Aba-Owerri Road Osioma Industrial Layout Aba; Petsow Laboratories Limited, Plot 8-10 Eziana Industrial Estate, Eziana Aba, Abia State. Anambra – Alben Healthcare Industries Limited, KM 15, Old Onitsha Awka Road, Ogidi,; Barker Alfanzo Pharmaceutical Industries (Nig) Limited, Km 3 offObosi Road, Odume Lay Out, Obosi. Enugu- Braunx Pharm Ltd, Plot B260, New Abakaliki Road Layout,Emene; Bulger Pharm Ltd; Imo - Campharm Products Limited, Ubaha-Ihioma Road, Ubaha-Ihioma, A & J Pharmaceutical Nig. Limited, 3, Egbu Uratta Ring Road, By FRSC Junction, Egbu, Owerri

3.4 Population of the Study

The population for the study included eight (8) selected management staff of the pharmaceutical manufacturing firms in the South-East, Nigeria which was among the list of Inspected Local Pharmaceutical Manufacturing Facilities in Nigeria (2018-2019) Using Who Key Elements by National Agency for Food and Drug Administration and Control (NAFDAC). The total population for the study was three thousand, seven hundred and forty-two (3742). The selected manufacturing organizations were : Maobison Inter Link Ass., Petsow Laboratories Limited, Alben Healthcare Industries Limited, Barker Alfanzo Pharmaceutical Industries (Nig) Limited, Braunx Pharm Ltd, Bulger Pharm Ltd, Campharm Products Limited, and A & J Pharmaceutical Nig. Limited, Therefore, the study limited population to all management, senior and junior staff of each of these organizations understudy.

Table 3.1 Population Distribution

	Firms	Staff Categories				
		Mgt	Senior	Junior	Total	%
	Abia					
1.	Maobison Inter Link Ass.	22	218	307	547	15
2.	Petsow Laboratories Limited	14	211	247	472	13
	Anambra State					
3.	Alben Healthcare Industries	23	114	231	368	10
4.	Barker Alfanxo Pharmaceutic	34	152	215	401	11
	Enugu					
5.	Bulger Pharm Ltd	25	181	276	482	13
6.	Braunx Pharm Ltd.	27	231	281	539	14
	Imo					
7.	A & J Pharmaceutical Nig. Ltd	42	251	224	517	14
8.	Campharm Products Limited	32	149	235	416	10
	Total	219	1,507	2016	3742	100

Source: Administrative desk office, 2023.

Table 3.1 study shows that eight firms which were selected from in South East which the researcher deemed to be representative of the pharmaceutical manufacturing firms.

3.5. Sample Size Determination

The actual population was three thousand seven hundred and forty- two (3742) employees. The study was drawn from the three levels of employees in these organizations under study using a stratified sampling method. To determine the adequate sample size, the study used Freund and William's statistical formula as quoted by (Uzoagulu, 2011).

$$n = \frac{Z^2 N(pq)}{N(e)^e + Z^2(pq)}$$

Where n = Sample Size

N = The population

p = Probability of success/proportion

q = Probability of failure/proportion

Z = Standard (error of mean) normal deviate

e = Limit of tolerable error (or level of significance)

N = 3742

p = .5

q = (1 - .5) = .5

$$\begin{aligned}
 Z &= 95 \text{ percent} = 1.96 \\
 e &= 0.05 \text{ percent} \\
 &= \frac{(1.96)^2 \times 3742 \times .5 \times 5}{3742(0.05)^2 + (1.96)^2 \times .5 \times 5} \\
 &= \frac{3.8416 \times 3742 \times .25}{9.355 + 3.8416 \times .25} \\
 &= \frac{3,593.82}{9.355 + .9604} = \frac{3,593.82}{10.315} = 348.407 \quad \underline{\sim 348}
 \end{aligned}$$

A sample is a subset of a population selected to participate in the study; it is a fraction of the whole, designed to participate in the research project. The study sample size was three hundred and forty eight (348) respondents. The sample size was justified because the population was huge and such a sample would be sufficient to address the research problem.

Bowley’s (1976) proportional allocation formula for stratified sampling was used to allocate the samples:

$$nh = \frac{n(Nh)}{N}$$

Where:

Nh = Group population from each stratum

n = overall sample size

N = the overall population

nh = sample size from each stratum, in this case each state.

Table 3.2 Computation/Allocation of Sample Size

	Organisations	Population	Calculation	Sample	Percent
1.	Maobison Inter Link Ass.	547	$\frac{547 \times 348}{3742} =$	51	15
2.	Petsow Laboratories Limited	472	$\frac{472 \times 348}{3742} =$	44	13

3.	Alben Healthcare Industries	368	$\frac{368 \times 348}{3742} =$	34	10
4.	Barker Alfanzo Pharmaceutical	401	$\frac{401 \times 348}{3742} =$	37	11
5.	Bulger Pharm Ltd	482	$\frac{482 \times 348}{3742} =$	45	13
6.	Braunx Pharm Ltd.	539	$\frac{539 \times 348}{3742} =$	50	14
7.	A & J Pharmaceutical Nig. Ltd	517	$\frac{517 \times 348}{3742} =$	48	14
8.	Campharm Products Limited	416	$\frac{416 \times 348}{3742} =$	39	11
Total		3742		348	100

Source: Field Survey, 2023

3.6 Sampling Techniques

A stratified random sampling procedure was used for selecting the participants in this study. This technique was employed to ensure a fairly equal representation of the variables for the study. The stratification was based on the pharmaceutical manufacturing firms in south east, Nigeria. Within each section, selection of staff was by simple random sampling. This was achieved by writing out the names of the staff in piece of paper which was folded and put in a basket. After thorough reshuffling, the researcher selects an element, records it and puts it back in the basket until the required number is obtained. That is, researcher applied sampling with replacement.

3.7 Instrument for Data Collection

The instruments for data collection issued in this research include the structured questionnaire, and interview.

1. **Questionnaire:** The main data collection instruments employed in this study were questionnaire. The questionnaire was divided into two parts (A and B). Part A provides general information about the respondents while part B focuses on the research questions. One type of questionnaire (structured) was designed and used for this study. The basic questions in the questionnaire centered on the main issues raised in the objectives as derived from problem statement and reflected in the research hypotheses. The questionnaire was structured in a five point Likert scale. The likert scale grading follows:

Strongly Agreed	-----	5
Agreed	-----	4
Neutral	-----	3
Disagree	-----	2
Disagree	-----	1

2. **Oral interview:** Some respondents were interviewed personally using interview schedule to get more details about the study especially those not covered by the questionnaire.

3.8. Validity of the Instrument

To ascertain the validity of the research instrument, the researcher subjected the instrument to face validation by giving it to a panel of judges comprising of three internal assessors, and five management experts that examined the items, and agreed that they were in line with the objectives of the study. The structure and language of the instrument was modified in the light of their corrections. In addition, a proper structuring of the questionnaire and conduct of a pre-test of every question contained in the questionnaire was carried out to ensure that they are valid. Finally, the design of the questionnaire was made easy for the respondents to pick their preferred choice from the options provided.

3.9 Reliability of the Research Instrument

A test-retest method was used to test the reliability of the instrument. This was done by administering 25 copies of the prepared questionnaire to the sample of the study, Cronbah’s Alpha was used in determining the extent of consistency of the reliability. A Cronbach’s alpha value (∞) of greater 0.76 indicated very strong reliability.

Scale: ALL VARIABLES

Case Processing Summary

		N	%
	Valid	25	100.0

Cases	Excluded ^a	0	.0
	Total	25	100.0

a. Listwise deletion based on all variables in the procedure.

Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	No. of Items
0.74	20

Scale reliabilities were calculated using Cronbach's Alpha; the result obtained was 0.740. This shows that the internal consistency of the scale is good for the purpose of this study, because it is greater than 0.74 which is the standard. Cronbach's Alpha is considered the most appropriate statistics test for reliability. Given the nature of responses used to construct the scale.

3.10. Methods of Data Analyses

The questionnaire responses were cleaned, grouped into various categories and entered in the SPSS software to facilitate analysis using descriptive statistics. Frequency distribution tables were used to summarize the data from the respondents. The analyzed data were presented in frequency distribution tables for ease of understanding and analysis. Data from the questionnaire were collected and analyzed using simple percentages, mean and standard deviation, Z-test statistics was used to test the hypotheses.

CHAPTER FOUR

DATA ANALYSIS AND PRESENTATION

The chapter presents and analyzes the data collected for the study. The presentation and interpretation of data were based on the responses of the respondents of Pharmaceutical

manufacturing firms in South East Nigeria. Questionnaire was administrated to the staff of the organizations under study

4.1 Distribution and returned Questionnaire

Table 4.1 Distribution and Return of the Questionnaire

Firms	Distributed	No Returned	percent	No not Returned	Percent
1. Maobison Inter Link Ass.	51	44	8	7	2
2. Petsow Laboratories Limited	44	37	8	7	2
3. Alben Healthcare Industries	34	30	7	4	1
4. Barker Alfanxo Pharmaceutic	37	31	5	6	2
5. Bulger Pharm Ltd	45	40	5	5	2
6. Braunx Pharm Ltd.	50	43	5	7	2
7. A & J Pharmaceutical Nig.	48	40	3	8	2
8. Campharm Products Limited	39	35	6	4	1
Total	348	300	86.0	48	14

Source: Field Survey, 2023

The table 4.1 shows that Three hundred and forty eight (348) copies of the questionnaire were distributed and three hundred (300) copies of the questionnaire were returned representing eighty six percent (86%) while forty eight (46) copies of the questionnaire were not returned representing fourteen (14) percent. This shows a high rate of the respondents.

4.2 Bio-Data

The bio-data comprises of the gender, marital status, educational qualifications, years of experience and age of the respondents understudy.

Table 4.2.1 presents the gender of the respondents

Table 4.2.1: Gender of the Respondents

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent
Male	130	43.3	43.3
Female	170	56.7	56.7
Total	300	100.0	100.0

Source: Field Survey, 2023

Table 4.2.1, it was observed that 130 respondents out of 300 representing 43.3 percent were males whereas 170 respondents representing 56.7 percent were females. This indicated that female were more than the males.

Table 4.2.2 presents the various age ranges of the respondents

Table 4.2.2: Age of the Respondents

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent
Below 30 years	63	21.0	21.0
30-39 years	77	25.7	25.7
40-49 years	96	32.0	32.0
50-59 years	39	13.0	13.0
60 years and above	25	8.3	8.3
Total	300	100.0	100.0

Source: Field Survey, 2023

Table 4.2.2, indicates that 63 respondents out of 300 representing 21.0 percent were below 30years, 77 respondents with 25.7 percent were within the age bracket of 30-39, 96 respondents representing 32.0 percent were within the age bracket of 40-49, 39 respondents representing 13.0 percent were within the age bracket of 50-59, while 25 respondents representing 8.3 percent were within the age bracket of 60 years and above. This implies that greater proportion of the respondents fall within the ages of 40-49 years.

Table 4.2.3 presents the marital status of the respondents

Table 4.2.3 Marital Status of the Respondents

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent
Single	86	28.7	28.7
Married	168	56.0	56.0
Divorced	19	6.3	6.3
Widowed	20	6.6	6.6
Separated	7	2.4	2.4
Total	300	100.0	100.0

Source: Field Survey, 2023

Table 4.2.3, reveals that 86 respondents out of 300 representing 28.7 percent were single, 168 respondents representing 56.0 percent were married. 19 respondents representing 6.3 percent were divorced, 20 respondents representing 6.6 percent were widowed and 7 respondents representing 2.4 percent were widowed.

Table 4.2.4 presents the educational qualification of the respondents

Table 4.2.4: Educational Qualification of the Respondents

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent
SSCE/NECO/NABTEB	55	18.3	18.3
NCE/OND	107	35.7	35.7
HND and BSC	77	25.7	25.7
Masters degree	42	14.0	14.0
Ph.D	19	6.3	6.3
Total	300	100.0	100.0

Source: Field Survey, 2023

Table 4.2.4, reveals that 55 respondents out of 300 representing 18.3 percent were holders of SSCE/NECO/NABTEB, 107 respondents representing 35.7 percent were holders of NCE/OND, 77 respondents representing 25.7 percent were holders of HND and BSC, 42 respondents representing 14.0 percent were holders of Masters degree and 19 respondents representing 6.3 percent were holders of Ph.D.

4.3 Data Relating to Research Question

4.3.1 The effect of self-awareness on intellectual stimulation of employees of pharmaceutical manufacturing firms in south east, Nigeria

Table 4.3.1.1 Response on the statement that the power to influence outcomes was due competent leader to continuously encourage team members to think

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Mean(χ)	Std.
Strongly Agree	122	40.7	40.7	4.5934	.63085
Agree	92	30.7	30.7	3.8761	.31075
Neutral	16	5.3	5.3	2.8000	.61968
Disagree	29	9.7	9.7	2.2966	.47696
Strongly disagree	41	13.7	13.7	1.8195	.93788
Total	300	100.0	100.0	3.6767	1.18434

Source: Field Survey, 2023

Table 4.3.1.1, indicates that 122 respondents out of 300 representing 40.7 percent with mean score of (4.5934) and standard deviation of (.63085) strongly agree that the power to influence outcomes was due competent leader to continuously encourage team members to think. 92 respondents representing 30.7 percent with mean score of (3.8761) and standard deviation of (.31075) Agree, 16 were neutral respondents representing 5.3 percent with mean score of (2.8000) and standard deviation of (.61968) that power to influence outcomes was due competent leader to continuously encourage team members to think. 29 respondents representing 9.7 percent with mean score of (2.2966) and standard deviation of (.47696) disagree. 41 respondents representing 13.7 percent with mean score of (1.8195) and standard deviation of (.93788) strongly disagree that the power to influence outcomes was due competent leader to continuously encourage team members to think. Total mean score of (3.6767) and standard deviation of (1.18434).

Table 4.3.1.2 Response on the statement that the better decision makers enhanced the new ways we perform in the organization plus problem-solving

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Mean(\bar{x})	Std.
Strongly Agree	99	33.0	33.0	4.8303	.27160
Agree	92	30.7	30.7	3.8761	.31075
Neutral	25	8.3	8.3	2.5440	.43019
Disagree	18	6.0	6.0	2.4444	.74061
Strongly disagree	66	22.0	22.0	2.4333	1.19465
Total	300	100.0	100.0	3.6767	1.18434

Source: Field Survey, 2023

Table 4.3.1.2, indicates that 99 respondents out of 300 representing 33.0 percent with mean score of (4.8303) and standard deviation of (.27160) strongly agree that the better decision makers enhanced the new ways we perform in the organization plus problem-solving. 92 respondents representing 30.7 percent with mean score of (3.8761) and standard deviation of (.31075) Agree, 25 were neutral respondents representing 8.3 percent with mean score of (2.5440) and standard deviation of (.43061) that the better decision makers enhanced the new ways we perform in the organization plus problem-solving. 18 respondents representing 6.0 percent with mean score of (2.4444) and standard deviation of (.74061) disagree. 66 respondents representing 22.0 percent with mean score of (2.4333) and standard deviation of (1.19465) strongly disagree that the better decision makers enhanced the new ways we perform in the organization plus problem-solving. Total mean score of (3.6767) and standard deviation of (1.18434).

Table 4.3.1.3 Response on the statement that the more self confidence of the employees supports new and innovative ways of actions in the organizations

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Mean(\bar{x})	Std.
Strongly Agree	100	33.3	33.3	4.5900	.72995
Agree	114	38.0	38.0	4.0456	.28289
Neutral	26	8.7	8.7	2.7769	.39730
Disagree	20	6.7	6.7	2.2900	.70030
Strongly disagree	40	13.3	13.3	1.6200	.65445
Total	300	100.0	100.0	3.6767	1.18434

Source: Field Survey, 2023

Table 4.3.1.3, indicates that 100 respondents out of 300 representing 33.3 percent with mean score of (4.5900) and standard deviation of (.72995) strongly agree that the more self confidence of the employees supports new and innovative ways of actions in the organizations. 114 respondents representing 38.0 percent with mean score of (4.0456) and standard deviation of (.28289) Agree, 26 were neutral respondents representing 8.7 percent with mean score of (2.7769) and standard deviation of (.39730) that the more self confidence of the employees supports new and innovative ways of actions in the organizations. 20 respondents representing 6.7 percent with mean score of (2.2900) and standard deviation of (.70030) disagree. 40 respondents representing 13.3 percent with mean score of (1.6200) and standard deviation of (.65445) strongly disagree that the more self confidence of the employees supports new and innovative ways of actions in the organizations. Total mean score of (3.6767) and standard deviation of (1.18434).

Table 4.3.1.4 Response on the statement that the communicatively with clarity and intention creates an active and engaged team

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Mean(\bar{x})	Std.
Strongly Agree	114	38.0	38.0	4.3667	.92552
Agree	106	35.3	35.3	4.1057	.17719
Neutral	7	2.3	2.3	3.0571	.32071
Disagree	42	14.0	14.0	2.2952	.63590
Strongly disagree	31	10.3	10.3	1.6839	.86375
Total	300	100.0	100.0	3.6767	1.18434

Source: Field Survey, 2023

Table 4.3.1.4, indicates that 114 respondents out of 300 representing 38.0 percent with mean score of (4.3667) and standard deviation of (.92552) strongly agree that the Communicatively with clarity and intention creates an active and engaged team. 106 respondents representing 35.3 percent with mean score of (4.1057) and standard deviation of (.17719) Agree, 7 were neutral respondents representing 2.3 percent with mean score of (3.0571) and standard deviation of (.32071) that the Communicatively with clarity and intention creates an active and engaged team. 42 respondents representing 14.0 percent with mean score of (2.2952) and standard deviation of (.63590) disagree. 31 respondents representing 10.3 percent with mean score of (1.6839) and standard deviation of (.86375) strongly disagree that the communicatively with clarity and intention creates an active and engaged team. Total mean score of (3.6767) and standard deviation of (1.18434).

Table 4.3.1.5 Response on the statement that the assumptions and biases are freed and healthy tem that grows together is ensured in the organization

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Mean(\bar{x})	Std.
Strongly Agree	108	36.0	36.0	4.5019	.76781
Agree	106	35.3	35.3	4.1057	.17719
Neutral	18	6.0	6.0	3.0222	.35572
Disagree	20	6.7	6.7	1.6200	.39947
Strongly disagree	48	16.0	16.0	1.9750	.70696
Total	300	100.0	100.0	3.6767	1.18434

Source: Field Survey, 2023

Table 4.3.1.5, indicates that 108 respondents out of 300 representing 36.0 percent with mean score of (4.5019) and standard deviation of (.76781) strongly agree that assumptions and biases are freed and healthy tem that grows together is ensured in the organization. 106 respondents representing 35.3 percent with mean score of (4.1057) and standard deviation of (.17719) Agree, 18 were neutral respondents representing 6.0 percent with mean score of (3.0222) and standard deviation of (.35572) that the assumptions and biases are freed and healthy tem that grows together is ensured in the organization. 20 respondents representing 6.7 percent with mean score of (1.6200) and standard deviation of (.39947) disagree. 48 respondents representing 16.0 percent with mean score of (1.9750) and standard deviation of (.70696) strongly disagree that the assumptions and biases are freed and healthy tem that grows together is ensured in the organization. Total mean score of (3.6767) and standard deviation of (1.18434).

4.3.2 The effect of team work on idealized influence of employees of pharmaceutical manufacturing firms in south east, Nigeria

Table 4.3.2.1 Response on the statement that the efficient planning helps leaders to becomes to become a role model for those around them in the organization

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Mean(\bar{x})	Std.
Strongly Agree	103	34.3	34.3	4.4408	.83284
Agree	131	43.7	43.7	4.0611	.16987
Neutral	7	2.3	2.3	2.8000	.20000
Disagree	44	14.7	14.7	1.8455	.29841
Strongly disagree	15	5.0	5.0	1.5867	.45019
Total	300	100.0	100.0	3.7133	1.12578

Source: Field Survey, 2023

Table 4.3.2.1, indicates that 103 respondents out of 300 representing 34.3 percent with mean score of (4.4408) and standard deviation of (.83284) strongly agree that the efficient planning helps leaders to becomes to become a role model for those around them in the organization. 131 respondents representing 43.7 percent with mean score of (4.0611) and standard deviation of (.16987) Agree, 7 were neutral respondents representing 2.3 percent with mean score of (2.8000) and standard deviation of (.20000) that the efficient planning helps leaders to becomes to become a role model for those around them in the organization. 44 respondents representing 14.7 percent with mean score of (1.8455) and standard deviation of (.29841) disagree. 15 respondents representing 5.0 percent with mean score of (1.5867) and standard deviation of (.45019) strongly disagree that the efficient planning helps leaders to become to become a role model for those around them in the organization. Total mean score of (3.7133) and standard deviation of (1.12578).

Table 4.3.2.2 Response on the statement that the proper organizing in the company gives direction to the individual efforts and promotes work ethics

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Mean(\bar{x})	Std.
Strongly Agree	84	28.0	28.0	4.7405	.51370
Agree	131	43.7	43.7	4.0611	.16987
Neutral	1	.3	.3	3.2000	.00000
Disagree	38	12.7	12.7	2.0474	.43230
Strongly disagree	46	15.3	15.3	2.2348	.88975
Total	300	100.0	100.0	3.7133	1.12578

Source: Field Survey, 2023

Table 4.3.2.2, indicates that 84 respondents out of 300 representing 28.0 percent with mean score of (4.7405) and standard deviation of (.51370) strongly agree that the proper organizing in the company gives direction to the individual efforts and promotes work ethics. 131 respondents representing 43.7 percent with mean score of (4.0611) and standard deviation of (.16987) Agree, 1 were neutral respondents representing .3 percent with mean score of (3.2000) and standard deviation of (.00000) that the proper organizing in the company gives direction to the individual efforts and promotes work ethics. 38 respondents representing 12.7 percent with mean score of (2.0474) and standard deviation of (.43230) disagree. 46 respondents representing 15.3 percent with mean score of (2.2348) and standard deviation of (.88975) strongly disagree that proper organizing in the company gives direction to the individual efforts and promotes work ethics. Total mean score of (3.7133) and standard deviation of (1.12578).

Table 4.3.2.3 Response on the statement that the fulfillment of organizational goals were achieved through controlling and promotion of values

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Mean(\bar{x})	Std.
Strongly Agree	92	30.7	30.7	4.5826	.75456
Agree	133	44.3	44.3	4.0602	.19538
Neutral	6	2.0	2.0	2.7333	.10328
Disagree	40	13.3	13.3	1.9700	.35533
Strongly disagree	29	9.7	9.7	1.9724	.76480
Total	300	100.0	100.0	3.7133	1.12578

Source: Field Survey, 2023

Table 4.3.2.3, indicates that 92 respondents out of 300 representing 30.7 percent with mean score of (4.5826) and standard deviation of (.75456) strongly agree that the fulfillment of organizational goals were achieved through controlling and promotion of values. 133 respondents representing 44.3 percent with mean score of (4.0602) and standard deviation of (.19538) Agree, 6 were neutral respondents representing 2.0 percent with mean score of (2.7333) and standard deviation of (.10328) that the fulfillment of organizational goals were achieved through controlling and promotion of values. 40 respondents representing 13.3 percent with mean score of (1.9700) and standard deviation of (.35533) disagree. 29 respondents representing 9.7 percent with mean score of (1.9724) and standard deviation of (.76480) strongly disagree that fulfillment of organizational goals were achieved through controlling and promotion of values. Total mean score of (3.7133) and standard deviation of (1.12578).

Table 4.3.2.4 Response on the statement that the effective directing integrates the resources in proper manner creating a dynamic environment

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Mean(\bar{x})	Std.
Strongly Agree	100	33.3	33.3	4.6400	.59561
Agree	109	36.3	36.3	4.0073	.08132
Neutral	23	7.7	7.7	2.5043	.45475
Disagree	6	2.0	2.0	1.8000	.00000
Strongly disagree	62	20.7	20.7	2.3355	1.07110
Total	300	100.0	100.0	3.7133	1.12578

Source: Field Survey, 2023

Table 4.3.2.4, indicates that 100 respondents out of 300 representing 33.3 percent with mean score of (4.6400) and standard deviation of (.59561) strongly agree that the effective directing integrates the resources in proper manner creating a dynamic environment. 109 respondents representing 36.3 percent with mean score of (4.0073) and standard deviation of (.08132) Agree, 23 were neutral respondents representing 7.7 percent with mean score of (2.5043) and standard deviation of (.45475) that the effective directing integrates the resources in proper manner creating a dynamic environment. 6 respondents representing 2.0 percent with mean score of (1.8000) and standard deviation of (.00000) disagree. 62 respondents representing 20.7 percent with mean score of (2.3355) and standard deviation of (1.07110) strongly disagree that effective directing integrates the resources in proper manner creating a dynamic environment. Total mean score of (3.7133) and standard deviation of (1.12578).

Table 4.3.2.5 Response on the statement that the developing the organization and society maximizes efficiency through management.

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Mean($\bar{\chi}$)	Std.
Strongly Agree	124	41.3	41.3	4.4516	.79383
Agree	91	30.3	30.3	4.0000	.00000
Neutral	14	4.7	4.7	3.4429	.45186
Disagree	43	14.3	14.3	1.9116	.31563
Strongly disagree	28	9.3	9.3	2.4143	1.08311
Total	300	100.0	100.0	3.7133	1.12578

Source: Field Survey, 2023

Table 4.3.2.5, indicates that 124 respondents out of 300 representing 41.3 percent with mean score of (4.4516) and standard deviation of (.79383) strongly agree that the developing the organization and society maximizes efficiency through management. 91 respondents representing 30.3 percent with mean score of (4.0000) and standard deviation of (.00000) Agree, 14 were neutral respondents representing 4.7 percent with mean score of (3.4429) and standard deviation of (.45186) that the developing the organization and society maximizes efficiency through management. 43 respondents representing 14.3 percent with mean score of (1.9116) and standard deviation of (.31563) disagree. 28 respondents representing 9.3 percent with mean score of (2.4143) and standard deviation of (1.08311) strongly disagree developing the organization and society maximizes efficiency through management. Total mean score of (3.7133) and standard deviation of (1.12578).

4.3.3 The effect of effective communication on employee’s individual consideration of pharmaceutical manufacturing firms in south east, Nigeria

Table 4.3.3.1 Response on the statement that the social skills have assisted the provision of services to the customers

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Mean(\bar{x})	Std.
Strongly Agree	96	32.0	32.0	4.8146	.32991
Agree	105	35.0	35.0	4.0457	.20240
Neutral	12	4.0	4.0	2.9000	.30151
Disagree	30	10.0	10.0	1.7333	.27957
Strongly disagree	57	19.0	19.0	2.5544	.92815
Total	300	100.0	100.0	3.7313	1.15104

Source: Field Survey, 2023

Table 4.3.3.1, indicates that 96 respondents out of 300 representing 32.0 percent with mean score of (4.8146) and standard deviation of (.32991) strongly agree that the social skills have assisted the provision of services to the customers. 105 respondents representing 35.0 percent with mean score of (4.0457) and standard deviation of (.20240) Agree, 12 were neutral respondents representing 4.0 percent with mean score of (2.9000) and standard deviation of (.30151) that the social skills have assisted the provision of services to the customers. 30 respondents representing 10.0 percent with mean score of (1.7333) and standard deviation of (.27957) disagree. 57 respondents representing 19.0 percent with mean score of (2.5544) and standard deviation of (.92815) strongly disagree that the social skills have assisted the provision of services to the customers. Total mean score of (3.7313) and standard deviation of (1.15104).

Table 4.3.3.2 Response on the statement that the collaboration with colleagues in the organization was possible through these social skills

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Mean(\bar{x})	Std.
Strongly Agree	124	41.3	41.3	4.4565	.82030
Agree	97	32.3	32.3	4.0701	.15286
Neutral	14	4.7	4.7	2.6286	.38316
Disagree	13	4.3	4.3	3.1231	.65084
Strongly disagree	52	17.3	17.3	1.8192	.55767
Total	300	100.0	100.0	3.7313	1.15104

Source: Field Survey, 2023

Table 4.3.3.2, indicates that 124 respondents out of 300 representing 41.3 percent with mean score of (4.4565) and standard deviation of (.82030) strongly agree that the collaboration with colleagues in the organization was possible through these social skills. 97 respondents representing 32.3 percent with mean score of (4.0701) and standard deviation of (.15286) Agree, 14 were neutral respondents representing 4.7 percent with mean score of (2.6286) and standard deviation of (.38316) that the collaboration with colleagues in the organization was possible through these social skills. 13 respondents representing 4.3 percent with mean score of (3.1231) and standard deviation of (.65084) disagree. 52 respondents representing 17.3 percent with mean score of (1.8192) and standard deviation of (.55767) strongly disagree that the collaboration with colleagues in the organization was possible through these social skills. Total mean score of (3.7313) and standard deviation of (1.15104).

Table 4.3.3.3 Response on the statement that the experiencing job satisfaction was achieved through listening skills

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Mean(\bar{x})	Std.
Strongly Agree	111	37.0	37.0	4.4108	.88783
Agree	116	38.7	38.7	4.0914	.29886
Neutral	8	2.7	2.7	2.9250	.14880
Disagree	29	9.7	9.7	1.8828	.28039
Strongly disagree	36	12.0	12.0	2.1444	1.00809
Total	300	100.0	100.0	3.7313	1.15104

Source: Field Survey, 2023

Table 4.3.3.3, indicates that 111 respondents out of 300 representing 37.0 percent with mean score of (4.4108) and standard deviation of (.88783) strongly agree that the experiencing job satisfaction was achieved through listening skills. 116 respondents representing 38.7 percent with mean score of (4.0914) and standard deviation of (.29886) Agree, 8 were neutral respondents representing 2.7 percent with mean score of (2.9250) and standard deviation of (.14880) that the experiencing job satisfaction was achieved through listening skills. 29 respondents representing 9.7 percent with mean score of (1.8828) and standard deviation of (.28039) disagree. 36 respondents representing 12.0 percent with mean score of (2.1444) and standard deviation of (1.00809) strongly disagree that the experiencing job satisfaction was achieved through listening skills. Total mean score of (3.7313) and standard deviation of (1.15104).

Table 4.3.3.4 Response on the statement that the proper planning and collaboration was building skills realized

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Mean(\bar{x})	Std.
Strongly Agree	130	43.3	43.3	4.5754	.62258
Agree	89	29.7	29.7	3.9528	.14778
Neutral	7	2.3	2.3	2.9714	.07559
Disagree	43	14.3	14.3	1.8651	.31988
Strongly disagree	31	10.3	10.3	2.3161	.94907
Total	300	100.0	100.0	3.7313	1.15104

Source: Field Survey, 2023

Table 4.3.3.4, indicates that 130 respondents out of 300 representing 43.3 percent with mean score of (4.5754) and standard deviation of (.62258) strongly agree that the proper planning and collaboration was building skills realized 89 respondents representing 29.7 percent with mean score of (3.9528) and standard deviation of (.14778) Agree, 7 were neutral respondents representing 2.3 percent with mean score of (2.9714) and standard deviation of (.07559) that proper planning and collaboration was building skills realized. 43 respondents representing 14.3 percent with mean score of (1.8651) and standard deviation of (.31988) disagree. 31 respondents representing 10.3 percent with mean score of (2.3161) and standard deviation of (.94907) strongly disagree that the proper planning and collaboration was building skills realized. Total mean score of (3.7313) and standard deviation of (1.15104).

Table 4.3.3.5 Response on the statement that the Social skills allow improving attributes and qualities vital to effective organization performance

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Mean(\bar{x})	Std.
Strongly Agree	117	39.0	39.0	4.5248	.71618
Agree	104	34.7	34.7	3.7596	.64965
Neutral	15	5.0	5.0	3.8133	.78728
Disagree	25	8.3	8.3	2.7680	1.18979
Strongly disagree	39	13.0	13.0	1.8615	.67145
Total	300	100.0	100.0	3.7313	1.15104

Source: Field Survey, 2023

Table 4.3.3.5, indicates that 117 respondents out of 300 representing 39.0 percent with mean score of (4.5248) and standard deviation of (.71618) strongly agree that the Social skills allow improving attributes and qualities vital to effective organization performance. 104 respondents representing 34.7 percent with mean score of (3.7596) and standard deviation of (.64965) Agree, 15 were neutral respondents representing 5.0 percent with mean score of (3.8133) and standard deviation of (.78728) that Social skills allow improving attributes and qualities vital to effective organization performance. 25 respondents representing 8.3 percent with mean score of (2.7680) and standard deviation of (1.18979) disagree. 39 respondents representing 13.0 percent with mean score of (1.8615) and standard deviation of (.67145) strongly disagree that Social skills allow improving attributes and qualities vital to effective organization performance. Total mean score of (3.7313) and standard deviation of (1.15104).

4.3.4 The effect of motivation on employee inspirational motivation of pharmaceutical manufacturing firms in south east, Nigeria

Table 4.3.4.1 Response on the statement that a well motivated workforce is loyal and employee has the power to do more.

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Mean(\bar{x})	Std.
Strongly Agree	124	41.3	41.3	4.5258	.68169
Agree	93	31.0	31.0	3.7613	.55581
Neutral	16	5.3	5.3	3.3000	1.20444
Disagree	22	7.3	7.3	2.8000	.59841
Strongly disagree	45	15.0	15.0	2.1422	.98130
Total	300	100.0	100.0	3.7393	1.11430

Source: Field Survey, 2023

Table 4.3.4.1, indicates that 124 respondents out of 300 representing 41.3 percent with mean score of (4.5258) and standard deviation of (.68169) strongly agree that a well motivated workforce is loyal and employee has the power to do more. 93 respondents representing 31.0 percent with mean score of (3.7613) and standard deviation of (.55581) Agree, 16 were neutral respondents representing 5.3 percent with mean score of (3.3000) and standard deviation of (1.20444) that a well motivated workforce is loyal and employee has the power to do more. 22 respondents representing 7.3 percent with mean score of (2.8000) and standard deviation of (.59841) disagree. 45 respondents representing 15.0 percent with mean score of (2.1422) and standard deviation of (.98130) strongly disagree that a well motivated workforce is loyal and employee has the power to do more. Total mean score of (3.7393) and standard deviation of (1.11430).

Table 4.3.4.2 Response on the statement that the employees disputes and strike are reduced with motivation

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Mean($\bar{\chi}$)	Std.
Strongly Agree	132	44.0	44.0	4.4545	.78267
Agree	80	26.7	26.7	3.9775	.11471
Neutral	10	3.3	3.3	2.7200	.10328
Disagree	35	11.7	11.7	2.4286	.49739
Strongly disagree	43	14.3	14.3	2.4047	1.21772
Total	300	100.0	100.0	3.7393	1.11430

Source: Field Survey, 2023

Table 4.3.4.2, indicates that 132 respondents out of 300 representing 44.0 percent with mean score of (4.4545) and standard deviation of (.78267) strongly agree that the employees disputes and strike are reduced with motivation 80 respondents representing 26.7 percent with mean score of (3.9775) and standard deviation of (.11471) Agree, 10 were neutral respondents representing 3.3 percent with mean score of (2.7200) and standard deviation of (.10328) that the employees disputes and strike are reduced with motivation 35 respondents representing 11.7 percent with mean score of (2.4286) and standard deviation of (.49739) disagree. 43 respondents representing 14.3 percent with mean score of (2.4047) and standard deviation of (.1.21772) strongly disagree that the employees disputes and strike are reduced with motivation. Total mean score of (3.7393) and standard deviation of (1.11430).

Table 4.3.4.3 Response on the statement that the employee turnover is reduced and organization costs of hiring new people

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Mean(\bar{x})	Std.
Strongly Agree	95	31.7	31.7	4.7453	.48592
Agree	113	37.7	37.7	4.0389	.30102
Neutral	31	10.3	10.3	2.9032	.45861
Disagree	5	1.7	1.7	2.2000	.00000
Strongly disagree	56	18.7	18.7	2.0286	.72506
Total	300	100.0	100.0	3.7393	1.11430

Source: Field Survey, 2023

Table 4.3.4.3, indicates that 95 respondents out of 300 representing 31.7 percent with mean score of (4.7453) and standard deviation of (.48592) strongly agree that the employee turnover is reduced and organization costs of hiring new people 113 respondents representing 37.7 percent with mean score of (4.0389) and standard deviation of (.30102) Agree, 31 were neutral respondents representing 10.3 percent with mean score of (2.9032) and standard deviation of (.45861) that the employee turnover is reduced and organization costs of hiring new people. 5 respondents representing 1.7percent with mean score of (2.2000) and standard deviation of (.00000) disagree. 56 respondents representing 18.7 percent with mean score of (2.0286) and standard deviation of (.72506) strongly that the employee turnover is reduced and organization costs of hiring new people. Total mean score of (3.7393) and standard deviation of (1.11430).

Table 4.3.4.4 Response on the statement that the motivation facilitates direction and leads to profitable operation

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Mean(\bar{x})	Std.
Strongly Agree	117	39.0	39.0	4.3316	.98547
Agree	113	37.7	37.7	4.0389	.30102
Neutral	14	4.7	4.7	2.9429	.54591
Disagree	40	13.3	13.3	2.4650	.57715
Strongly disagree	16	5.3	5.3	1.1750	.30000
Total	300	100.0	100.0	3.7393	1.11430

Source: Field Survey, 2023

Table 4.3.4.4, indicates that 117 respondents out of 300 representing 39.0 percent with mean score of (4.3316) and standard deviation of (.98547) strongly agree that the motivation facilitates direction and leads to profitable operation. 113 respondents representing 37.7 percent with mean score of (4.0389) and standard deviation of (.30102) Agree, 14 were neutral respondents representing 4.7 percent with mean score of (2.9429) and standard deviation of (.54591) that the motivation facilitates direction and leads to profitable operation. 40 respondents representing 13.3 percent with mean score of (2.4650) and standard deviation of (.57715) disagree. 16 respondents representing 5.3 percent with mean score of (1.1750) and standard deviation of (.30000) strongly disagree that the motivation facilitates direction and leads to profitable operation. Total mean score of (3.7393) and standard deviation of (1.11430).

Table 4.3.4.5 Response on the statement that the high level of productivity and satisfaction of employees are recoded

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Mean(\bar{x})	Std.
Strongly Agree	95	31.7	31.7	4.7453	.48592
Agree	113	37.7	37.7	4.0389	.30102
Neutral	21	7.0	7.0	2.8952	.48834
Disagree	35	11.7	11.7	2.2571	.68526
Strongly disagree	36	12.0	12.0	2.0778	.76834
Total	300	100.0	100.0	3.7393	1.11430

Source: Field Survey, 2023

Table 4.3.4.5, indicates that 95 respondents out of 300 representing 31.7 percent with mean score of (4.7453) and standard deviation of (.48592) strongly agree the high level of productivity and satisfaction of employees are recoded. 113 respondents representing 37.7 percent with mean score of (4.0389) and standard deviation of (.30102) Agree, 21 were neutral respondents representing 7.0 percent with mean score of (2.8952) and standard deviation of (4.8834) the high level of productivity and satisfaction of employees are recoded. 35 respondents representing 11.7 percent with mean score of (2.2571) and standard deviation of (.68526) disagree. 36 respondents representing 12.0 percent with mean score of (2.0778) and standard deviation of (.76834) strongly disagree that the high level of productivity and satisfaction of employees are recoded. Total mean score of (3.7393) and standard deviation of (1.11430).

4.4 Test of hypotheses

4.4.1 Test of hypothesis One: Self awareness has no effect on the intellectual stimulation of employees of pharmaceutical manufacturing firms in South East, Nigeria

Table 4.4.1.1 shows the contingency table of Self awareness has no effect on the intellectual stimulation of employees of pharmaceutical manufacturing firms in South East, Nigeria

Table 4.4.1.1 Contingency table for test of hypothesis one

S/N		SA	A	N	D	SD
1.	The power to influence outcomes was due competent leader to continuously encourage team members to think	122	92	16	29	41
2.	better decision makers enhanced the new ways we perform in the organization plus problem-solving	99	92	25	18	66
3.	More self confidence of the employees supports new and innovative ways of actions in the organizations	100	114	26	20	40
4.	communicatively with clarity and intention creates an active and engaged team	114	106	7	42	31
5.	The assumptions and biases are freed and healthy tem that grows together is ensured in the organization	108	106	18	20	48
	Total	543	510	92	129	226

4.4.1.2 Shows Pearson correlation of Self awareness has no effect on the intellectual stimulation of employees of pharmaceutical manufacturing firms in South East, Nigeria

Table 4.4.1.2 Pearson correlation of Self awareness has no effect on the intellectual stimulation of employees of pharmaceutical manufacturing firms in South East, Nigeria

One-Sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test

	The power to influence outcomes was due competent leader to continuously encourage team members to think.	Better decision makers enhanced the new ways we perform in the organization plus problem-solving.	More self confidence of the employees supports new and innovative ways of actions in the organizations	Communicative ly with clarity and intention creates an active and engaged team.	Assumptions and biases are freed and healthy tem that grows together is ensured in the organization
N	300	300	300	300	300
Uniform Parameters ^{a,b}	Minimum 1 Maximum 5	1 5	1 5	1 5	1 5
Most Extreme Differences	Absolute .463 Positive .137 Negative -.463	.387 .220 -.387	.463 .133 -.463	.483 .103 -.483	.463 .160 -.463
Kolmogorov-Smirnov Z	8.025	6.697	8.025	8.372	8.025
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000

a. Test distribution is Uniform.

b. Calculated from data.

Decision Rule

If the calculated Z-value is greater than the critical Z-value (i.e $Z_{cal} > Z_{critical}$), reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternative hypothesis accordingly.

Result

With Kolmogorov-Smirnon Z – value ranges from 6.697 to 8.372 and on Asymp. Significance of 0.000, the responses from the respondents as display in the table is normally distributed. This affirms the assertion of the most of the respondents that self awareness had significant positive effect on the intellectual stimulation of employees of pharmaceutical manufacturing firms in South East, Nigeria

Decision

Furthermore, comparing the calculated Z- value ranges from 6.697 to 8.372 against the critical Z- value of .000(2-tailed test at 97percent level of confidence) the null hypothesis were rejected. Thus the alternative hypothesis was accepted which states that self awareness had significant positive effect on the intellectual stimulation of employees of pharmaceutical manufacturing firms in South East, Nigeria

4.4.2 Test of hypothesis two: Team work does not have a significant effect on the idealized influence of pharmaceutical manufacturing firms in South East, Nigeria

Table 4.4.2.1 shows the contingency table of team work does not have a significant effect on the idealized influence of pharmaceutical manufacturing firms in South East, Nigeria

Table 4.4.2.1 Contingency table for test of hypothesis two

S/N		SA	A	N	D	SD
1.	The efficient planning helps leaders to becomes to become a role model for those around them in the organization	103	131	7	44	15
2.	proper organizing in the company gives direction to the individual efforts and promotes work ethics	84	131	1	38	46
3.	The fulfillment of organizational goals were achieved through controlling and promotion of values	92	133	6	40	9
4.	the effective directing integrates the resources in proper manner creating a dynamic environment	100	109	23	6	62
5.	the developing the organization and society maximizes efficiency through management	124	91	14	43	28
	Total	503	595	51	171	160

4.4.2.2 Shows Pearson correlation of team work does not have a significant effect on the idealized influence of pharmaceutical manufacturing firms in South East, Nigeria

Table 4.4.2.2 Pearson correlation of team work does not have a significant effect on the idealized influence of pharmaceutical manufacturing firms in South East, Nigeria

		One-Sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test				
		Efficient planning helps leaders to becomes to become a role model for those around them in the organization.	The proper organizing in the company gives direction to the individual efforts and promotes work ethics	The fulfillment of organizational goals were achieved through controlling and promotion of values	The effective directing integrates the resources in proper manner creating a dynamic environment	Developing the organization and society maximizes efficiency through management.
N		300	300	300	300	300
Uniform Parameters ^{a,b}	Minimum	1	1	1	1	1
	Maximum	5	5	5	5	5
Most Extreme Differences	Absolute Positive	.530	.467	.500	.447	.467
	Absolute Negative	-.530	-.467	-.500	-.447	-.467
Kolmogorov-Smirnov Z		9.180	8.083	8.660	7.736	8.083
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.000	.000	.000	.000

a. Test distribution is Uniform.

b. Calculated from data.

Decision Rule

If the calculated Z-value is greater than the critical Z-value (i.e $Z_{cal} > Z_{critical}$), reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternative hypothesis accordingly.

Result

With Kolmogorov- Smirnon Z – value ranges from 7.736 to 9.180 and on Asymp. Significance of 0.000, the responses from the respondents as display in the table is normally distributed. This affirms the assertion of the most of the respondents that team work had significant effect on the idealized influence of pharmaceutical manufacturing firms in South East, Nigeria

Decision

Furthermore, comparing the calculated Z- value ranges from 7.736 to 9.180 against the critical Z- value of .000(2-tailed test at 97percent level of confidence) the null hypothesis were rejected. Thus the alternative hypothesis was accepted which states that team work had significant effect on the idealized influence of pharmaceutical manufacturing firms in South East, Nigeria

4.4.3 Test of hypothesis three: Effective communication has no effect on employee’s Individual consideration of pharmaceutical manufacturing firms in South East, Nigeria

Table 4.4.3.1 shows the contingency table of effective communication has no effect on employee’s Individual consideration of pharmaceutical manufacturing firms in South East, Nigeria

Table 4.4.3.1 Contingency table for test of hypothesis three

S/N		SA	A	N	D	SD
1.	Social skills have assisted the provision of services to the customers	96	105	12	30	57
2.	The collaboration with colleagues in the organization was possible through these social skills	124	97	14	13	52
3.	The experiencing job satisfaction was achieved through listening skills	111	116	8	29	36
4.	proper planning and collaboration was building skills realized	130	89	7	43	31
5.	Social skills allow improving attributes and qualities vital to effective organization performance	117	104	15	25	39
	Total	503	595	51	171	160

4.4.3.2 Shows Pearson correlation of Effective communication has no effect on employee’s Individual consideration of pharmaceutical manufacturing firms in South East, Nigeria

Table 4.4.3.2 Pearson correlation of Effective communication has no effect on employee’s Individual consideration of pharmaceutical manufacturing firms in South East, Nigeria

One-Sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test

	Social skills have assisted the provision of services to the customers.	Collaboration with colleagues in the organization was possible through these social skills	Experiencing job satisfaction was achieved through listening skills.	Proper planning and collaboration was building skills realized	Social skills allow improving attributes and qualities vital to effective organization performance.
N	300	300	300	300	300
Uniform Parameters ^{a,b}	Minimum 1	1	1	1	1
	Maximum 5	5	5	5	5
Most Extreme Differences	Absolute .420	.487	.507	.480	.487
	Positive .190	.173	.120	.103	.130
	Negative -.420	-.487	-.507	-.480	-.487
Kolmogorov-Smirnov Z	7.275	8.429	8.776	8.314	8.429
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000

a. Test distribution is Uniform.

b. Calculated from data.

Decision Rule

If the calculated Z-value is greater than the critical Z-value (i.e $Z_{cal} > Z_{critical}$), reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternative hypothesis accordingly.

Result

With Kolmogorov-Smirnon Z – value ranges from 7.725 to 8.776 and on Asymp. Significance of 0.000, the responses from the respondents as display in the table is normally distributed. This affirms the assertion of the most of the respondents that effective communication had significant positive effect on employee’s Individual consideration of pharmaceutical manufacturing firms in South East, Nigeria

Decision

Furthermore, comparing the calculated Z- value ranges from 7.725 to 8.776 against the critical Z- value of .000(2-tailed test at 97percent level of confidence) the null hypothesis were rejected. Thus the alternative hypothesis was accepted which states that effective communication had significant positive effect on employee’s Individual consideration of pharmaceutical manufacturing firms in South East, Nigeria

4.4.4 Test of hypothesis four: Motivation has no effect on employee inspirational motivation of pharmaceutical manufacturing firms in South East, Nigeria

Table 4.4.4.1 shows the contingency table of Motivation has no effect on employee inspirational motivation of pharmaceutical manufacturing firms in South East, Nigeria

Table 4.4.4.1 Contingency table for test of hypothesis three

S/N		SA	A	N	D	SD
1.	A well motivated workforce is loyal and employee has the power to do more.	124	93	16	22	45
2.	the employees disputes and strike are reduced with motivation	132	80	10	35	43
3.	the employee turnover is reduced and organization costs of hiring new people	95	113	31	5	56
4.	the motivation facilitates direction and leads to profitable operation	117	113	14	40	16
5.	the high level of productivity and satisfaction of employees are recoded	95	113	21	35	36
	Total	563	512	92	137	196

4.4.4.2 Shows Pearson correlation of Motivation has no effect on employee inspirational motivation of pharmaceutical manufacturing firms in South East, Nigeria

Table 4.4.4.2 Pearson correlation of motivation has no effect on employee inspirational motivation of pharmaceutical manufacturing firms in South East, Nigeria

		One-Sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test				
		A well motivated workforce is loyal and employee has the power to do more.	Employees disputes and strike are reduced with motivation.	Employee turnover is reduced and organization costs of hiring new people	Motivation facilitates direction and leads to profitable operation	High level of productivity and satisfaction of employees are recoded.
N		300	300	300	300	300
Uniform Parameters ^{a,b}	Minimum	1	1	1	1	1
	Maximum	5	5	5	5	5
Most Extreme Differences	Absolute Positive	.473	.457	.443	.517	.443
	Absolute Negative	.150	.143	.187	.053	.120
Kolmogorov-Smirnov Z		8.198	7.910	7.679	8.949	7.679
	Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000

a. Test distribution is Uniform.

b. Calculated from data.

Decision Rule

If the calculated Z-value is greater than the critical Z-value (i.e $Z_{cal} > Z_{critical}$), reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternative hypothesis accordingly.

Result

With Kolmogorov-Smirnon Z – value ranges from 7.679 to 8.949 and on Asymp. Significance of 0.000, the responses from the respondents as display in the table is normally distributed. This affirms the assertion of the most of the respondents that motivation had significant positive effect on employee inspirational motivation of pharmaceutical manufacturing firms in South East, Nigeria

Decision

Furthermore, comparing the calculated Z- value ranges from 7.679 to 8.949 against the critical Z- value of .000(2-tailed test at 97percent level of confidence) the null hypothesis were rejected. Thus the alternative hypothesis was accepted which states that motivation had significant positive effect on employee inspirational motivation of pharmaceutical manufacturing firms in South East, Nigeria

4.5 Discussion of findings

4.5.1 Self-awareness had significant positive effect on the intellectual stimulation of employees of pharmaceutical manufacturing firms in South East, Nigeria

The result of hypotheses one showed that the calculated Z- value ranges from 6.697 to 8.372 against the critical Z- value of .000, which states that self-awareness had significant positive effect on the intellectual stimulation of employees of pharmaceutical manufacturing firms in South East, Nigeria. In line with these hypotheses Subhasree and Vishvakarma (2015) examined the impact of self-awareness on eight states of personality. A cognitive assessment survey was made for measuring the time duration of past, present and future thinking of participants within India for 15 hours per day in order to inculcate self-awareness. A sample of (N=40)female participants were taken by using purposive sampling, out of which 20 were residential college students of age 18-25 and 20 were housewives of age 30-45. Eight state questionnaire (8SQ) was administered (pre-test) on them, then exposed to continuous self-awareness for a week and again post-test was taken. The data was analyzed by using t-test. It was observed that there were some states of personality which found to be significant at 0.01 and 0.05, like anxiety, repression, fatigue and arousal. Also, the study of Sancher-Cardona, Salanova and Llorens-Gumbau (2018) on how leadership intellectual stimulation relates to team positive affect and team learning. The results provide evidence of the strong relationship that intellectual stimulation has on team learning and team positive affect, as well as the potential of positive affect for stimulating team learning. Team positive affect serves as a partial mediator between intellectual stimulation and team learning, contributing to explain significant additional variance. Leadership intellectual stimulation is a relevant team social resource that provides support for team learning.

4.5.2 Team work had significant positive effect on the idealized influence of pharmaceutical manufacturing firms in South East, Nigeria

Hypotheses tow revealed that the calculated Z- value ranges from 7.736 to 9.180 against the critical Z- value of .000 which states that team work had significant positive effect on the idealized influence of pharmaceutical manufacturing firms in South East, Nigeria. Emotional intelligence has a more potent drive to any accomplishment than monetary rewards. Sahibzada, Kakakhel and

Khan (2016) examined the impact of idealized influence and inspirational motivation of leaders on employees' job satisfaction. Data was collected through a well-established questionnaire from 330 employees of 10 different private sector universities located in KPK. The results using descriptive statistics confirmed a non-zero relationship of the two dimensions of leadership with employees' job satisfaction. Idealized Influence showed significant association with employee's job satisfaction. The study brought out important findings to bring about behavioral improvements in leadership style of education sector that will eventually enhance levels of Job Satisfaction of employees.

4.5.3 Effective communication had significant positive effect on employee's Individual consideration of pharmaceutical manufacturing firms in South East, Nigeria

Employee engagement has a statistical significant relationship with charisma, ethical leadership, and teamwork. Ogola, Sikalieh and Linge (2017) investigated the influence of Idealized Influence leadership behavior on employee performance in Small and Medium Enterprise in Kenya. This study targeted the KPMG top 100 SMEs of 2014 in Kenya. Global emotional intelligence as well as its components, self-awareness, self-management and relationship management correlated positively with achievement motivation. But social awareness was not found to be associated with achievement motivation. The results showed that adolescents with high emotional intelligence hold more realistic perceptions in interpersonal relationships and this ability probably helps them develop achievement motivation. Higher achievement motivation may help enhance feelings of self-efficacy as well as academic motivation (Sobhi-Gharamaleki, 2012). The study found that Idealized Influence leadership behavior and Employee Performance in SMEs in Kenya had a strong positive and significant correlation $r(194) = .829, p < .000$ and a positive and significant relationship ($\beta = .829, t(194) = 20.503, p < .000$). Results show that if a leader inculcates trust in employees, practices high ethical values, acts as a role model to the employees and encourages employees to take risks; these will positively affect employees work and hence high performance levels. In line with this theory, the result of hypotheses three showed that calculated Z- value ranges from 7.725 to 8.776 against the critical Z- value of .000 which states that effective communication had significant positive effect on employee's Individual consideration of pharmaceutical manufacturing firms in South East, Nigeria

4.5.4 Motivation had significant positive effect on employee inspirational motivation of pharmaceutical manufacturing firms in South East, Nigeria

The calculated Z- value ranges from 7.679 to 8.949 against the critical Z- value of .000 which states that motivation had significant positive effect on employee inspirational motivation of pharmaceutical manufacturing firms in South East, Nigeria. Njiraini, K'Aol and Linge (2018) determined the extent to which idealized influence and inspirational motivation influence job satisfaction among employees in commercial banks in Kenya. The study adopted a positivist research philosophy and a descriptive correlation research design. The target population consisted of 10,310 managerial employees in commercial banks in Kenya. A sample of 424 employees was obtained from the population using a stratified random sampling technique. Data were collected using structured questionnaires. A response rate of 82% was obtained. Data was analyzed using descriptive statistics and inferential statistics. Inferential statistical methods used to analyze the data were Chi-square, Pearson's correlation, ANOVA, and multiple linear regressions. The Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) tool version 22 was used to analyze the data. Correlation analysis found that idealized influence, inspirational motivation and job security were positively and significantly correlated to job satisfaction $r(346) = .496, p < .05$, $r(347) = .587, p < .05$, $r(347) = .697, p < .05$ respectively. Multiple linear regression results showed that idealized influence significantly influenced job satisfaction of the employees ($R^2 = .246, F(1, 97.750) = 112.421, p < .05$). Similarly, multiple linear regression results showed that inspirational motivation significantly influenced job satisfaction of the employees ($R^2 = .344, F(1, 126.302) = 180.980, p < .05$). Job security was found to significantly moderate the relationships between idealized influence, inspirational motivation and job satisfaction ($R^2 = .431, F(3, 44.688) = 86.330, p < .05$).

CHAPTER FIVE

SUMMARY OF FINDINGS, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

5.1 Findings

- i. Self-awareness had significant positive effect on the intellectual stimulation of employees of pharmaceutical manufacturing firms in South East, Nigeria, $Z (95, n = 300)$ from $6.697 < 8.372, p < 0.05$.
- ii. Team work had significant positive effect on the idealized influence of pharmaceutical manufacturing firms in South East, Nigeria, $Z (95, n = 300)$ from $7.736 < 9.180, p < 0.05$.
- iii. Effective communication had significant positive effect on employee's Individual consideration of pharmaceutical manufacturing firms in South East, Nigeria, $Z (95, n = 300)$ from $7.725 < 8.776, p < 0.05$.
- iv. Motivation had significant positive effect on employee inspirational motivation of pharmaceutical manufacturing firms in South East, Nigeria, $Z (95, n = 300)$ from $7.679 < 8.949, p < 0.05$.

5.2 Conclusion

The study concluded that self-awareness, relationship management, social skill and motivation had significant positive effect on intellectual stimulation, idealized employees, and employee's individual consideration and employee inspirational motivation. Emotions play a significant role in decision-making, trust-building, employee engagement, and conflict management. When it comes to laying the foundations of a human-centric workforce, the role of Emotional Intelligence is essential. Leading organizations involves interactions with individuals and a person with higher levels of EI may be better at interacting appropriately with others than a person with low levels of EI. A highly emotional intelligent leader is likely to be quite self-aware. Leaders with high emotional intelligence respond in ways that their employees can relate better to, thereby improving team performance, mitigating clashes, and addressing issues when required the most.

5.3 Recommendations

The following recommendations were made by the study

- i. There is need for self-awareness to communicate with clarity and intention, this will give the power to influence outcomes; helps become better decision-makers and give more self-confidence.
- ii. The pharmaceutical firms should endeavour to have strong relational management S it allow organizations to identify and track individuals or groups interested in the organisation's success or failure.
- iii. For success of any organisations the need for Social skills are inevitable to communicate more effectively and efficiently and, as a result, help build, maintain and grow relationships with colleagues, clients and new contacts.
- iv. Motivation should be inculcated into management value system to allow gain valued outcomes like improved performance, enhanced wellbeing, personal growth, or a sense of purpose. It will provide the goals to work towards and helps solve problems.

5.4 Contribution of knowledge

The studies were carried outside effect of emotional intelligence on transformational leadership in pharmaceutical manufacturing firms in South East, Nigeria and did not focus to best of my knowledge on the self-awareness and intellectual stimulation of employees; teamwork and idealized influence; effective communication and employee's Individual consideration; motivation and employee inspirational motivation in South East, Nigeria. Most of the studies reviewed were analysed using different statistical tool such as sampling technique, Descriptive statistics and appropriate inferential statistics, Purposive Sampling technique, Multiple sampling technique, Partial Least Square Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM), Multiple Regression Analysis (MRA) method while the present study made use of Z test to test the hypotheses. Therefore, the study aimed at filling this research gap by evaluating the emotional intelligence on transformational leadership in South East, Nigeria.

Fig 5.1: Contribution to knowledge model

5.5 Suggestion for further studies

The following areas were suggested for further studies

1. Inspirational motivation on the academic performance of selected universities in south west, Nigeria.
2. Job motivation and performance manufacturing firms in south East, Nigeria
3. Transformational style of leadership and job satisfaction of civil servants in Enugu state

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APPENDIX A

EFFECT OF EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE ON TRANSFORMATIONAL LEADERSHIP OF PHARMACEUTICAL MANUFACTURING FIRMS IN SOUTH EAST, NIGERIA

Department of Business Administration,
Faculty of Management Sciences
Enugu State University of Science and Technology
(ESUT) Enugu
5th April 2023

Dear Respondents,

Appeal to Respondents for Information

I am a Ph.D. Student of Business Administration Department, Faculty of Management Sciences, Enugu State University of Science and Technology (ESUT), Enugu. I am carrying out a research on the Effect of Emotional Intelligence on Transformational Leadership of Pharmaceutical Manufacturing Firms in South East, Nigeria.

I am therefore, soliciting your kind and honest answers to the attached questionnaire questions. I assure you that your response will be treated confidentially and will be used for the stated purpose only.

Thank you for your co-operation.

Emecheta, Jude Okechukwu

PG/EPh.D/2020/0037

APPENDIX B

EFFECT OF EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE ON TRANSFORMATIONAL LEADERSHIP OF PHARMACEUTICAL MANUFACTURING FIRMS IN SOUTH EAST, NIGERIA

SECTION A: BIOGRAPHICAL INFORMATION

INTRODUCTION: please tick (✓) appropriately against whichever answer is chosen.

1. What is your Sex?
 - a. Male
 - b. Female

2. Indicate your marital status?
 - a. Single
 - b. Married
 - c. Widowed
 - d. Divorced

3. What is your highest Educational Qualification?
 - a. WASC/GCE
 - b. HND/NCE
 - c. HND/B .S.Sc
 - d. M.Sc./MBA
 - e. Ph.D

4. How many Years of Experience do you have as a student?
 - a. 2 years of less
 - b. 3-5 years
 - c. 6-10 years
 - d. 11 years and above

5. What is your Age range?
 - a. Below 31 years
 - b. 31-40 years
 - c. 41-50 years

SECTION B: QUESTIONNAIRE PROPER

INSTRUCTION:

	Questionnaire items	Strongly agree	Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly disagree
OBJECTIVE I: The relationship between self-awareness and intellectual stimulation of employee of leaders of pharmaceutical companies in Enugu state.						
1.	The power to influence outcomes was due competent leader to continuously encourage team members to think.					
2.	Better decision makers enhanced the new ways we perform in the organization plus problem-solving.					
3.	More self confidence of the employees supports new and innovative ways of actions in the organizations					
4.	Communicatively with clarity and intention creates an active and engaged team.					
5.	Assumptions and biases are freed and healthy tem that grows together is ensured in the organization					
OBJECTIVE II: The relationship between management and idealized influence of employee of leaders of pharmaceutical companies in Enugu state.						
6.	Efficient planning helps leaders to becomes to become a role model for those around them in the organization.					
7.	The proper organizing in the company gives direction to the individual efforts and promotes work ethics					
8.	The fulfillment of organizational goals were achieved through controlling and promotion of values					

9.	The effective directing integrates the resources in proper manner creating a dynamic environment					
10.	Developing the organization and society maximizes efficiency through management.					
OBJECTIVE III: The relationship between social skill and employees individual consideration of leaders of pharmaceutical companies in Enugu state.						
11	Social skills have assisted the provision of services to the customers.					
12	Collaboration with colleagues in the organization was possible through these social skills					
13	Experiencing job satisfaction was achieved through listening skills.					
14	Proper planning and collaboration was building skills realized					
15	Social skills allow improving attributes and qualities vital to effective organization performance.					
OBJECTIVE IV: The relationship between motivations and employee inspirational motivation of leaders of pharmaceutical companies in Enugu state.						
16	A well motivated workforce is loyal and employee has the power to do more.					
17	Employees disputes and strike are reduced with motivation.					
18	Employee turnover is reduced and organization costs of hiring new people					
19	Motivation facilitates direction and leads to profitable operation					
20	High level of productivity and satisfaction of employees are recoded.					